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**THE NUMBER Π AS A STRUCTURAL INVARIANT
OF SELF-CONSISTENT OBSERVATION IN THE OBSERVER-
DEPENDENT THEORY OF EVERYTHING (ODTOE)**

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ABSTRACT. *Within the framework of the Observer-Dependent Theory of Everything (ODTOE; in the context of this article – a metatheoretical framework parameterizing the space of candidate physical theories through observer coherence; not a unified field equation program), which posits the conscious observer as the primary agent of reality formation, the role of the number π as a structural invariant of self-consistent observation configurations is investigated. Four mutually independent mathematical arguments are developed, each grounded in a distinct discipline: algebraic topology (the fundamental group of the observation loop), spectral theory (eigenvalues of the linearized operator Φ), measure theory (normalization of a Gaussian measure on infinite-dimensional Hilbert space), and the theory of nonlinear feedback (the oscillation period of the $\mathbf{R} \leftrightarrow \mathbf{B}$ coupling). Each argument yields a quantitative emergence of the factor 2π or $\sqrt{2\pi}$. The connection between the transcendence of π and the structural incompleteness of the metatheory is examined separately and motivates an interpretation of the reduced Planck constant $\hbar = h/(2\pi)$ as a multiplier of one complete revolution of the self-observation loop. Additionally, it is shown that within the discrete iterative dynamics of self-reference a second structural invariant emerges, namely the golden ratio $\varphi = (1 + \sqrt{5})/2$, complementing at the discrete layer. The principal conclusion: the presence of physical constants follows from the cyclicity of the act of observation itself, not from the geometry of physical space.*

Keywords: *number, observer, self-reference, fixed point, ODTOE, Gaussian measure, strange loop, golden ratio.*

I. INTRODUCTION

In the fundamental equations of physics the number appears in places where its geometric interpretation (the ratio of circumference to diameter) appears inessential: it fixes the scale of the reduced Planck constant $h = h/(2\pi)$, forms the phase factor of the wave function $\exp(2\pi i \cdot kx)$, lower-bounds the uncertainty product $\Delta x \Delta p \geq h/(2\pi)$, and provides the correct normalization of Gaussian probability distributions through the factor $\sqrt{2\pi}$ [1, 2]. An explanation relying on the periodicity of trigonometric and exponential functions is technically valid but leaves open the ontological question: what exactly distinguishes cyclic structures in the physical description of reality.

For brevity the approach developed here is denoted by the abbreviation OD-TOE (Observer-Dependent Theory of Everything; in the context of this article – a metatheoretical framework parameterizing the space of candidate physical theories through observer coherence; not a unified field equation program). All key relations are derived directly in Sections II–IV and rely on no external source. The conceptual link between self-referential loops and the formation of observer identity is discussed in particular by Hofstadter [15]. The central axiom asserts: observer and observable are mutually constituted in the act of observation. The claim of the existence of a self-consistent configuration $\Psi^* = \Phi(\Psi^*)$ as a fixed point of the self-observation map is formulated in § II, and the thesis of structural incompleteness is discussed in § IV.1.

The present work poses the task: to show that the number necessarily appears in any formalism satisfying the axiom of constructive observation and the self-consistency condition, and thereby to substantiate its status as a structural invariant of observation.

II. ELEMENTS OF THE ODTOE FORMALISM

We reproduce the key formulas of ODTOE in the notation of the present work. **Axiom (A).** Reality is determined by application of the observation operator to the field of potential states:

$$R = \hat{O}(\Psi), \quad \Psi \in \mathcal{H} \quad (\text{A.1})$$

where \mathcal{H} is an infinite-dimensional Hilbert space, formalized in a strict setting as a rigged Hilbert space [3].

Observation operator. Each observer O_i is described by the state vector $O_i = (B_i, A_i, H_i)$. Here $B_i \in [0,1]$ denotes contextual belief (cognitive coherence), specifies the archetype of attentional focus, H_i records the history of observations.

Contextual belief.

$$B(O, C) = F^{w_F} \cdot E^{w_E} \cdot (1 - \sigma)^{w_\sigma} \cdot \Lambda^{w_\Lambda} \quad (\text{D1.1})$$

where F is attentional focus, E is emotional coherence, σ is internal contradiction, Λ is empirical reinforcement; the weights sum to unity.

Self-observation map.

$$\Phi(\Psi) = \iota(\hat{O}_\Psi(\Psi)) \tag{U4.1}$$

where ι is the embedding operator. The fixed point $\Psi^* = \Phi(\Psi^*)$ defines the self-consistent configuration.

III. FOUR ARGUMENTS FOR THE EMERGENCE OF π

3.1. Topological argument

The sequence $\Psi \rightarrow \hat{O}(\Psi) \rightarrow R \rightarrow \iota(R) \rightarrow \Psi'$ traces a closed trajectory in \mathcal{H} when $\Psi' = \Psi$, that is, at the fixed point. Denote this trajectory by $\gamma: [0, 1] \rightarrow \mathcal{H}$ with $\gamma(0) = \gamma(1) = \Psi^*$. Then γ defines an element of the fundamental group $\pi_1(\mathcal{H}, \Psi^*)$.

Let $\mathcal{H} = \mathcal{H}_{\text{obc}} \oplus \mathcal{H}_{\text{ort}}$ where \mathcal{H}_{obc} denotes the subspace actualized by observation. The operator \hat{O} projects Ψ onto \mathcal{H}_{obc} ; the irreversibility of the projection (the collapse of the wave function) restricts the effective dynamics to a subspace homotopically equivalent to the circle S^1 . The fundamental group of the circle $\pi_1(S^1) = \mathbb{Z}[4]$, and its generator is given by one full circumnavigation of length 2π . Consequently, the topological constant for the closure of the self-observation loop is 2π .

3.2. Spectral argument

Let Φ be Fréchet-differentiable [5] in a neighborhood of Ψ^* . The linearization $D\Phi|_{\Psi^*} = L$ generally has complex spectrum:

$$\lambda_j = |\lambda_j| \cdot e^{i\theta_j} \tag{P.1}$$

where $|\lambda_j| < 1$ ensures decay (Banach's theorem [6]) and θ_j specifies the angular frequency. The condition that the system returns to its initial phase $\theta_j = 2\pi m$ is for integer n, m . The return $T_j = 2\pi / \theta_j$ period contains the factor 2π in any non-trivial oscillatory regime.

3.3. Measure-theoretic argument

For the determination of probabilities in ODTOE a measure on the infinite-dimensional \mathcal{H} is required. By Minlos's theorem [7], on a nuclear space there exists a σ -additive Gaussian measure μ_G . In a finite-dimensional projection onto, \mathbb{R}^n its density is:

$$d\mu_G = (2\pi)^{-n/2} \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{\|x\|^2}{2}\right) dx_1 \dots dx_n \tag{P.2}$$

The normalization $(2\pi)^{-n/2}$ factor is generated by the fundamental Gaussian integral

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \exp\left(-\frac{x^2}{2}\right) dx = \sqrt{2\pi} \tag{P.3}$$

proved by Laplace [8]. Essentially, the necessity of a π -containing factor is dictated not by the spatial geometry of the observable world but by the structure of the infinite-dimensional space of potential states.

3.4. Dynamical argument

In ODTOE reality and contextual belief B are linked by nonlinear feedback (formulas (A.1) and (D1.1) of § II). Linearization in a neighborhood of the stationary state (B^*, R^*) yields a characteristic equation for the Jacobian matrix with complex roots $\lambda = \alpha \pm i\omega$ at negative discriminant. The oscillation period:

$$T = \frac{2\pi}{\omega} \tag{P.4}$$

Friedmann and Hagen [9] showed that comparison of a variational estimate of the energy levels of the hydrogen atom with the exact quantum-mechanical solution reproduces the Wallis formula $\pi/2 = \prod_{n=1}^{\infty} 4n^2/(4n^2 - 1)$, indicating a connection of with quantum-oscillatory dynamics at the fundamental level.

IV. CONSEQUENCES AND INTERPRETATION

4.1. Transcendence of and spiral dynamics

The number π is transcendental (Lindemann, 1882 [10]). In the context of ODTOE transcendence acquires a substantive interpretation. The observation-coherence parameter S is bounded above: the limit $S \rightarrow 1$ (a unified configuration) is unattainable, expressing the structural incompleteness of the self-referential system. If the angular step $\Theta = 2\pi(p/q)$ were rational, q iterations would return the system exactly to its initial phase, and the cycle would close in a finite number of steps; such an outcome would mean a finite, fully describable reality. The consistency condition requires the angular step to be transcendental: then no finite number of iterations returns the system to the initial phase point, and the observation loop remains open. The decimal approximations of (3; 3.1; 3.14; 3.141; ...) define decreasing radial corridors in which the configuration is refined without achieving full closure; geometrically this is equivalent to a spiral asymptotically approaching the ideal circle.

4.2. Triadic architecture and Archimedes's lower bound

The integer part of π equals; Archimedes's lower bound $\pi > 3$ [11] is established through a hexagon inscribed in a circle. The minimal self-consistent act of observation by axiom (A) includes three components: observer $O = (B, H, A)$, observable R , observation operator \hat{O} . Without any of the three components self-consistency is impossible. The exact value $\pi = 3,14159$ reflects the "curvature" of the act of observation, exceeding the minimal triadicity.

4.3. The Planck constant as the observer's signature

The Planck constant $h = h/(2\pi)$ contains the factor traditionally explained by convenience in angular-frequency notation. ODTOE permits a nontrivial interpretation.

By argument 3.3, normalization of distributions on the infinite-dimensional \mathcal{H} requires the factor $\sqrt{2\pi}$. By argument 3.1, closure of the full observation cycle has topological length 2π . Division of h by 2π converts action into angular momentum: the factor 2π in the denominator of \hbar is the quantitative expression of one complete revolution of the self-observation loop. The minimal action is divided by the length of one cycle, generating the minimal angular momentum \hbar .

4.4. The golden ratio as a complementary invariant

The discrete iterative dynamics of self-reference generates a second structural invariant, namely the golden ratio $\varphi = (1 + \sqrt{5})/2$. The map $f(x) = 1 + 1/x$ is contracting on with Lipschitz constant $4/9$, and its unique positive fixed point is φ [12]. The same mechanism of Banach's theorem [6] that grounds the existence of Ψ^* generates as the invariant of discrete dynamics. At the quantum critical point of the Ising chain CoNb_2O_6 the ratio of the two smallest resonance frequencies equals φ , which is a signature of hidden E_8 symmetry [13]. The two invariants complement each other: π governs continuous phase dynamics (rotations, normalization of measures, oscillations), whereas φ governs discrete recurrent structures (fixed points, orbital stability). The transcendence of π is necessary for non-closure of continuous trajectories, whereas the algebraic irrationality φ of is sufficient for maximal stability of discrete orbits (Kolmogorov–Arnold–Moser theorem [14]).

V. CONCLUSION

Summing up, in the formalism of ODTOE the number emerges not as an imported constant but as the result of four independent formal requirements. The topological layer yields the length of the self-observation loop through the homotopy of a closed trajectory. The spectral layer reproduces in the oscillation period of the linear approximation of Φ . The measure-theoretic layer requires the factor $\sqrt{2\pi}$ for normalization of the Gaussian measure on infinite-dimensional space. The dynamical layer yields $2\pi/\omega$ in the period of the $R \leftrightarrow B$ coupling. The transcendence of corresponds to the fact that the limiting configuration of observation is structurally unattainable. The factor 2π in the formula $\hbar = h/(2\pi)$ is interpreted as the length of one complete revolution of self-observation, and the minimal angular momentum arises through division of the minimal action by this revolution. In parallel with π , the discrete iterative dynamics generates the golden ratio φ , acting at the discrete level through the same Banach contraction map. The program of further work includes refinement of the analytic properties of $\hat{\mathcal{O}}$ and \mathfrak{u} , as well as numerical modeling of the spiral trajectory in a neighborhood of the fixed point Ψ^* .

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CLARIFICATION OF BELASHOV'S LAW OF UNIVERSAL GRAVITATION

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Abstract. *This article is devoted to a refinement of Belashov's law of universal gravitation, which enables significantly more accurate measurement of the gravitational force between two material bodies situated within the space of our Universe. In this interpretation of Belashov's law of universal gravitation, only the denominator of the law is refined: for precise calculations of gravitational forces between two material bodies within the space of our Universe, it is necessary to treat each distance between the objects as distinct, since they may take on different values. When the spatial position of one material body changes, not only does the interaction angle between these bodies change, but also the distance between them. Calculations revealed that at apogee, the gravitational force between Earth and its satellite, the Moon, is 11.0707% greater than that between the Moon and Earth situated at the average distance from the Sun's surface. At perigee, the gravitational force between Earth and its satellite, the Moon, is 10.3750% less than that between the Moon and Earth situated at the average distance from the Sun's surface. These calculations reveal contradictions in the reasoning of certain scientists who assert that the gravitational force should be greater at perigee than at apogee. The current Newtonian law of universal gravitation, with its 'gravitational constant,' is incapable of determining the true gravitational force between the planet Earth and its satellite the Moon, when located at aphelion and perihelion, since it does not account for the distance from the surface of the planet Earth and its satellite the Moon to the surface of the Sun, nor the interaction between the planet Earth and its satellite the Moon.*

Keywords: *law of universal gravitation, gravitational constant, new laws of physics, substance of cosmic space, gravitation.*

Following an in-depth scientific and technical analysis of the origin of gravitational forces between two material bodies situated within the substance of cosmic space of the Solar system, Newton's law of universal gravitation was critically

reassessed, leading to the discovery of new laws of physics. The new physical laws elucidate the formation of gravitational forces between two material bodies in space, which have been mathematically demonstrated.

Isaac Newton, the English physicist, astronomer, mathematician, and mechanic, is credited as the discoverer of the law of gravitation; however, this concept was actually advanced earlier by prominent scholars such as the Italian scientist Galileo Galilei and the ancient Greek philosopher Epicurus.

In 1687, Isaac Newton, in his book 'Mathematical Principles of Natural Philosophy', asserted that 'Gravitation exists between all bodies always; under any conditions, bodies attract each other with a force whose magnitude is proportional to the product of their masses and inversely proportional to the square of the distance between them.' Isaac Newton's strategic thought was correct, as he derived this law of gravitation from the foundations of Kepler's empirical laws, which initially took the following form.

$$F = \frac{m_1 m_2}{r^2}$$

where:

F – gravitational force,

m_1 – mass of the first object,

m_2 – mass of the second object,

r – distance between the centers of mass.

However, this law did not conform to the dimensional units of physical quantities and did not represent the true value of the gravitational force between two material bodies in space. Consequently, the scientific community introduced the «gravitational constant» into Isaac Newton's law of gravitation, which then took the following form.

$$F = G \frac{m_1 m_2}{r^2}$$

where:

F – gravitational force, N

m_1 – mass of the first object, kg

m_2 – mass of the second object, kg

G – gravitational constant, N·m²/kg²

r – distance between centers of mass, m

For example, according to the current law of universal gravitation, let us determine the gravitational force between the Moon and the Earth.

$$F = G \frac{m_1 m_2}{r^2}$$

$$F_T = \frac{6,6743 \cdot 10^{-11} \cdot 5,9722 \cdot 10^{24} \text{ кг} \cdot 7,342 \cdot 10^{22} \text{ кг}}{384400000 \text{ м}^2} = 198055856502802859924,1H$$

where:

FG – force of universal gravitation, N

m_M – mass of the Moon $\approx 7.342 \times 10^{22}$ kg

m_E – mass of the planet Earth $\approx 5.9722 \times 10^{24}$ kg

G – gravitational constant $\approx 6.674 \times 10^{-11}$ N·m²/kg²

L – the distance from the surface of the Earth to the surface of the Moon $\approx 384,400,000$ m.

Newton's current law of universal gravitation does not correspond to the true values of gravitational forces, as it does not account for the level of activity of each material body present in space.

The law of activity of a material body in space was discovered by A. N. Belashov and formulated as follows:

The activity of a material body in space is directly proportional to the maximum phase of free-fall acceleration of the material body in space and inversely proportional to the minimum phase of free-fall acceleration of the material body in space.

$$Ag = \frac{g \text{ max}}{g \text{ min}}, \text{ или } Ag = \frac{g \text{ max}}{g \text{ min}} \cdot 100 \%$$

where:

$A g$ – the activity of a material body in space, m/s²

$g \text{ min}$ – the minimum phase of free-fall acceleration of a material body located in space, m/s²

$g \text{ max}$ – the maximum phase of free-fall acceleration of a material body located in space, m/s².

The evidence that there is no «gravitational constant» in the universe lies in the fact that it is a static value. When the distance from the surface of the Sun to the surface of the measured material bodies changes, or when the degree of activity between the measured bodies varies, the gravitational force should change accordingly; however, Newton's law of universal gravitation does not account for these parameters.

A new law of universal gravitation has long been established, which corresponds to the dimensional units of physical quantities and does not require a «gravitational constant.» This law was discovered by A. N. Belashov and published in the Scientific-Analytical Journal «Scientific Perspective», No. 1 (35), 2013, pp. 53–57. Published by «Infinity» Publishing House, in the city of Ufa, under the title «The Law of Gravitation Between Two Material Bodies Located in the Space of the Solar (or Another) System.»

The new law of universal gravitation was formulated as follows:

The gravitational force between two material bodies located in the space of the Solar system is equal to the sum of (the product of the mass of the first material body and the magnitude of the free fall acceleration of the first material body) and (the product of the mass of the second material body and the magnitude of the free fall acceleration of the second material body), multiplied by the square of the distance from the surface of the first material body to the surface of the second material body, and is inversely proportional to twice the product of the distance from the surface of the Sun to the surface of the first material body and the distance from the surface of the Sun to the surface of the second material body.

$$F_T = \frac{[(m_1 \cdot g_1) + (m_2 \cdot g_2)] \cdot L \cdot M^2}{2 \cdot (L c_1 \cdot L c_2)} = \frac{H \cdot M^2}{M^2} = H$$

where:

F_T – gravitational force between two material bodies within the Solar system, N

$L s_1$ – distance from the surface of the Sun to the surface of the first material body, m

$L s_2$ – distance from the surface of the Sun to the surface of the second material body, m

$L m$ – distance from the surface of the first material body to the surface of the second material body, m

g_1 – magnitude of the free-fall acceleration of the first material body, m/s²

g_2 – magnitude of the free-fall acceleration of the second material body, m/s²

m_1 – mass of the first material body, kg

m_2 – mass of the second material body, kg.

For example, according to the new law of universal gravitation by A. N. Belashov, the gravitational force between the planet Earth and its satellite the Moon, located at the average distance from the surface of the Sun, is determined.

$$F_T = \frac{[(m_1 \cdot g_1) + (m_2 \cdot g_2)] \cdot L \cdot M^2}{2 \cdot (L c_1 \cdot L c_2)} = \frac{H \cdot M^2}{M^2} = H$$

$$F_T = \frac{[(5,9722 \cdot 10^{24} \text{ kg} \cdot 9,8 \text{ m/c}^2) + (7,342 \cdot 10^{22} \text{ kg} \cdot 1,62 \text{ m/c}^2)] \cdot 384400000 \text{ m}^2}{2 \cdot (149500000000 \text{ m} \cdot 149500000000 \text{ m})} = 193863691711397948568,8 \text{ H}$$

where:

F_T – gravitational force between the planet Earth and its satellite the Moon, N

$L c_1$ – average distance from the surface of the Sun to the surface of the planet Earth ≈ 149500000000 m

L_{c_2} – average distance from the surface of the Sun to the surface of the Moon’s satellite ≈ 149500000000 m

$L_{\{m\}}$ – average distance from the surface of the Earth to the surface of the Moon $\approx 384,400,000$ m

$g_{\{1\}}$ – magnitude of free-fall acceleration of the Earth ≈ 9.8066 m/s²

$g_{\{2\}}$ – magnitude of free-fall acceleration of the Moon ≈ 1.62 m/s²

$m_{\{L\}}$ – mass of the Moon $\approx 7.342 \times 10^{22}$ kg

m_E – mass of the planet Earth $\approx 5.9722 \times 10^{24}$ kg.

We will determine the calculation error between the current Newtonian law of universal gravitation, which uses the ‘gravitational constant,’ and the new law of universal gravitation discovered by A. N. Belashov.

$$198,055,856,502,802,859,924.1 \text{ N} = 100\%$$

$$193,863,691,711,397,948,568.8 \text{ N} = X\%$$

$$X = 97.883\%$$

where:

F_T – force according to Newton’s law of universal gravitation using the ‘gravitational constant’ $\approx 198,055,856,502,802,859,924.1$ N

F_T – force according to Belashov’s law of universal gravitation with the current acceleration of free fall bodies in lunar space ≈ 1.62 m/s² $\approx 193,863,691,711,397,948,568.8$ N

This error arose due to the fixed value of the «gravitational constant,» since it is unknown to which point in cosmic space it applies, as well as due to inaccurate data on the acceleration of free fall of bodies on the Moon.

The acceleration of free fall of bodies in space on the Moon and on the planet Earth can be determined according to another law of Belashov.

The law for determining the distance from the surface of the Sun to the surface of a measured material body located in the Solar System was discovered by A. N. Belashov and is formulated as follows:

The distance from the surface of the Sun to the surface of the planets in the Solar System is directly proportional to the acceleration of free fall of bodies in the space of the measured material body divided by the diameter of the measured material body, and inversely proportional to the acceleration of antigravitational interaction and the Sun’s counteraction.

$$L_u = \frac{g_u \cdot D_u}{g_c} = \frac{M}{c^2} \cdot \frac{c^2}{M} \cdot \frac{M}{M}$$

where:

L and m – the distance from the surface of the Sun to the surface of the studied material body, m

g and g – gravitational attraction of the measured material body, m/s²

g_c – antigravitational interaction and counteraction of the Sun, m/s²

D_u – diameter of the measured material body, m.

For example, based on the law determining the distance from the surface of the Sun to the surface of the measured material body, we calculate the acceleration of free fall of bodies on the Moon, which is located at an average distance from the surface of the Sun approximately at the Earth's orbital level.

$$g_n = \frac{L \cdot g_c}{D_n} = \frac{M}{c^2} \cdot \frac{M}{m} \cdot \frac{m}{c^2}$$

$$g_n = \frac{149500000000 \text{ м} \cdot 0,00083675979083612040133779264214 \text{ м/с}^2}{3476280 \text{ м}} = 35,98547548816551 \text{ м/с}^2$$

where:

g_n – acceleration of free fall of bodies on the Moon, m/s²

g_c – acceleration of antigravitational interaction and counteraction of the Sun
 $\approx 0.0008367597908361204013390488452674 \text{ м/с}^2$

L – distance from the surface of the Sun to the surface of the Moon $\approx 1,49500000000 \text{ м}$

D_m – diameter of the Moon $\approx 3,476,280 \text{ м}$.

When calculating gravitational forces between the planet Earth and its satellite the Moon, it is necessary to take into account the sensational discovery concerning the properties and composition of the Moon, published in the scientific-practical journal «Higher School», No. 2, 2018, pages 27–33. Publishing House «Infinity», city of Ufa.

The Moon is a gaseous satellite composed of a solid shell of frozen gas, covered by a multi-meter layer of cosmic dust. Based on the average density of the Moon, it is difficult to determine the internal composition of gas, since the Moon's overall density is approximately $0.31260053456501934 \text{ кг/м}^3$.

The gas within the Moon's sphere may consist of many chemical components, but even gas mixtures composed of helium and hydrogen can form the Moon's outer sphere and remain solid at the temperature of outer space, which is $-270.45 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

Inside the solid shell, the gas mixture containing cosmic dust particles remains in constant motion, as one side of the Moon is continuously heated. The Sunlit side of the Moon can heat up to $+107 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, while the side in shadow may reach a temperature of $-268.9 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, causing the gas mixture inside the Moon's sphere to perpetually circulate through natural convection. During this process, internal energy is transferred by jets and gas flows and arises spontaneously within the substance due to uneven heating within the gravitational field. When rotating a gas mixture inside a sphere, an acceleration of free fall of bodies in space is generated, which exceeds the Earth's by 3.6 times.

For example, according to the law determining the distance from the surface of the Sun to the surface of the measured material body, we will verify the acceleration of free fall of bodies in space on the planet Earth.

$$g_3 = \frac{L \cdot g_c}{D_3} = \frac{M}{c^2} \cdot \frac{M}{M} \cdot \frac{M}{c^2}$$

$$g_3 = \frac{149500000000,000 \text{ m} \cdot 0,00083675979083612040133904884526 \text{ M/c}^2}{12756200 \text{ m}} = 9,80665000000 \text{ M/c}^2$$

where:

g_z – acceleration of free fall of bodies in space on the planet Earth, m/s²

g_c – acceleration of antigravitational interaction and counteraction of the Sun
 $\approx 0.0008367597908361204013390488452674 \text{ m/s}^2$

L – average distance from the surface of the Sun to the surface of the Earth $\approx 149500000000 \text{ m}$

D_z – diameter of the Earth $\approx 12,756,200 \text{ m}$.

According to the law formulated by A. N. Belashov, the acceleration of anti-gravitational interaction and the Sun’s counteraction within the Solar System is approximately $0.00083675979083612040133779264214048 \text{ m/s}^2$.

The refined law of universal gravitation by Belashov can be expressed as follows:

$$F_T = \frac{[(m_1 \cdot g_1) + (m_2 \cdot g_2)] \cdot L \cdot M^2}{(L_{c3} \cdot L_{c1}) + (L_{c1} \cdot L_{c3})} = \frac{H \cdot M^2}{M^2} = H$$

In this interpretation of Belashov’s law of universal gravitation, only the denominator of the law is refined; for precise calculations of gravitational forces between two material bodies within the space of our Universe, it is necessary to treat each distance between the objects as distinct, since they may take on different values. When the spatial position of one material body changes, not only does the interaction angle between these material bodies change, but also the distance between them, as illustrated in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1

where:

pos.1 m_c – Sun,

pos.2 m_z – Earth,

pos.3 m_l – Moon,

pos.4 L_{c3} – distance from the surface of the Sun to the surface of the Earth,

pos.5 L_{cl} – distance from the surface of the Sun to the surface of the Moon,

pos.6 L_m – distance from the surface of the Earth to the surface of the Moon,

pos.7 L_{rsl} – the horizontal distance from the surface of the Sun to the surface of the Earth,

pos.8 L_{rsl} – the horizontal distance from the surface of the Sun to the surface of the Moon.

For example, according to the refined law of universal gravitation, let us determine the gravitational force between the Earth and its satellite, the Moon, which are at the average distance from the surface of the Sun.

Preliminarily, it is necessary to determine, using the Pythagorean theorem, the horizontal distance from the surface of the Sun to the surfaces of both the Moon and the Earth, which is formulated for a right triangle where the square of the hypotenuse equals the sum of the squares of the two legs.

$$L_{cl} = \sqrt{(L_{c3})^2 + L_m^2}$$

$$L_{cl} = \sqrt{(149500000000 \text{ m}^2 + 384400000^2 \text{ m}^2)} = 149500494191,02 \text{ m}$$

where:

L_{rsl} – horizontal distance from the surface of the Sun to the surface of the Moon, m

L_{sz} – average distance from the surface of the Sun to the surface of the Earth ≈ 149500000000 m

L_m – distance from the surface of planet Earth to the surface of the Moon $\approx 384,400,000$ m.

Knowing the exact distances from the surface of planet Earth to the surface of the Sun, from the surface of the Moon to the surface of planet Earth, and from the surface of the Sun to the surface of the Moon, the refined law of universal gravitation allows obtaining a sufficiently accurate value of the gravitational force exerted by planet Earth on its satellite, the Moon.

For example, using the refined law of universal gravitation, we determine the gravitational force of planet Earth on its satellite, the Moon, which experiences an acceleration of free fall of approximately $35.98547548816 \text{ m/s}^2$ in space, located at an average distance from the surface of the Sun.

$$F_T = \frac{[(m_1 \cdot g_1) + (m_2 \cdot g_2)] \cdot L \cdot M^2}{(L_{cs} \cdot L_{cl}) + (L_{cl} \cdot L_{cs})} = \frac{H \cdot M^2}{M^2} = H$$

$$F_T = \frac{[(5,9722 \cdot 10^{24} \text{ кг} \cdot 9,8 \text{ м/с}^2) + (7,342 \cdot 10^{22} \text{ кг} \cdot 35,9 \text{ м/с}^2)] \cdot 363300000 \text{ м}^2}{(149500000000 \text{ м} \cdot 149133223720 \text{ м}) + (149500000000 \text{ м} \cdot 149133223720 \text{ м})} = 181223606979454576053,5 \text{ Н}$$

where:

F_T – gravitational force between the planet Earth and its satellite the Moon, N

L_{sz} – the average distance from the Sun’s surface to the Earth’s surface ≈ 1495 million km

L_{sl} – the average distance from the surface of the Sun to the surface of the Moon ≈ 149500000000 m

L_{rsl} – horizontal distance from the surface of the Sun to the surface of the Earth $\approx 149,500,494,191.02$ m

L_{rsl} – horizontal distance from the surface of the Sun to the surface of the Moon $\approx 149,500,494,191.02$ m

$L_{\{m\}}$ – average distance from the surface of the Earth to the surface of the Moon $\approx 384,400,000$ m

g_1 – free-fall acceleration magnitude of planet Earth ≈ 9.80665 m/s²

g_2 – free-fall acceleration magnitude of the Moon ≈ 35.98547548 m/s²

$m_{\{L\}}$ – mass of the Moon $\approx 7.342 \times 10^{22}$ kg

m_E – mass of the planet Earth $\approx 5.9722 \times 10^{24}$ kg

For example, let us determine the difference in gravitational force calculations between planet Earth and its satellite the Moon, situated at the average distance from the surface of the Sun, according to the simplified law of universal gravitation and the refined law of universal gravitation proposed by A. N. Belashov.

$$202202175737265429431.03 \text{ N} = 100 \%$$

$$193863691711397948568.8 \text{ N} = X \%$$

$$X = 95.876 \%$$

where:

F_T – gravitational force according to Belashov’s refined law of universal gravitation with acceleration of free fall of bodies in lunar space ≈ 35.98547548 m/s², amounting to $\approx 202202175737265429431.03$ N

F_T – gravitational force according to Belashov’s simplified law of universal gravitation with acceleration of free fall of bodies in lunar space ≈ 1.62 m/s², amounting to $\approx 193863691711397948568.8$ N

The difference in gravitational force readings between Belashov’s refined law of universal gravitation and the simplified law of universal gravitation can be calculated in Newtons using different free-fall accelerations of bodies on the Moon.

202202175737265429431.03 N – 193863691711397948568.8 N =
8338484025867480862.23 N

where:

F_T – gravitational force according to Belashov’s refined law of universal gravitation with free-fall acceleration on the Moon $\approx 35.985 \text{ m/s}^2 \approx 202202175737265429431.03 \text{ N}$

F_T – gravitational force according to Belashov’s simplified law of Universal Gravitation

with free-fall acceleration on the Moon $\approx 1.62 \text{ m/s}^2 \approx 193863691711397948568.8 \text{ N}$

This calculation was made using the Moon’s mass $\approx 7,342,000 \text{ kg}$, but 00000000000000000000 based on new findings concerning the Moon’s properties and composition, which is covered by a multi-meter layer of cosmic dust, the Moon should have a mass $\approx 6,875,948,070,714,670,189.932 \text{ kg}$ with the free-fall acceleration of bodies in space $\approx 35.98547548816551 \text{ m/s}^2$.

However, at present, it is difficult to convince the scientific community that the Moon is a gaseous satellite of our planet, which is enveloped by a multi-meter-thick layer of cosmic space substance emanating from the surface of the Sun, and this understanding will require not only time but also additional evidence.

Figure 2 shows the Earth 2 located at an average distance 4 from the surface of the Sun 1. The Moon 3, located at perigee at a distance 12 from the surface of the Sun 1, with a diameter of 11, is positioned at a distance 10 from the surface of the Earth 2, which has a diameter of 13. The Moon 9, located at apogee at a distance of 14 from the surface of the planet Earth, is at a distance of 15 from the surface of the Sun 1.

Fig. 2

For example, using the refined law of universal gravitation, we determine the gravitational force between the planet Earth and its satellite the Moon located at perigee.

Determine the distance from the surface of the Sun to the surface of the Moon located at perigee.

$$L_{sz} = L_{sz} - L_m - D_l$$

$$L_{sz} = 149500000000 \text{ m} - 363,300,000 \text{ m} - 3,476,280 \text{ m} = 149,133,223,720 \text{ m}$$

where:

L_{cn} – distance from the surface of the Sun to the surface of the Moon at perigee, m

L_{sz} – the average distance from the Sun’s surface to the Earth’s surface ≈ 1495 million km00000000 m

D_l – diameter of the Moon $\approx 3,476,280$ m

L_m – distance from the surface of planet Earth to the surface of the Moon at perigee $\approx 363,300,000$ m

For example, by the refined law of universal gravitation, the gravitational force exerted by planet Earth on its satellite, the Moon at perigee, is determined.

$$F_T = \frac{[(m_1 \cdot g_1) + (m_2 \cdot g_2)] \cdot L \cdot M^2}{(L_{cz} \cdot L_{cn}) + (L_{cn} \cdot L_{cz})} = \frac{H \cdot M^2}{M^2} = H$$

$$F_T = \frac{[(5,9722 \cdot 10^{24} \text{ kg} \cdot 9,8 \text{ m/c}^2) + (7,342 \cdot 10^{22} \text{ kg} \cdot 35,9 \text{ m/c}^2)] \cdot 363300000 \text{ m}^2}{(149500000000 \text{ m} \cdot 149133223720 \text{ m}) + (149500000000 \text{ m} \cdot 149133223720 \text{ m})} = 181223606979454576053,5 \text{ H}$$

where:

F_T – gravitational force between the planet Earth and its satellite the Moon, N

L_{sz} – the average distance from the Sun’s surface to the Earth’s surface ≈ 1495 million km00000000 m

L_{cn} – average distance from the surface of the Sun to the surface of the Moon at perigee $\approx 149,133,223,720$ m

L_{rsl} – horizontal distance from the surface of the Sun to the surface of the Earth ≈ 0 m

L_{rsl} – horizontal distance from the surface of the Sun to the surface of the Moon ≈ 0 m

L_m – distance from the surface of planet Earth to the surface of the Moon at perigee $\approx 363,300,000$ m

g_1 – magnitude of the acceleration due to gravity on planet Earth $\approx 9.80665 \text{ m/s}^2$

g_2 – magnitude of the acceleration due to gravity on the Moon $\approx 35.98547548 \text{ m/s}^2$

m_l – mass of the Moon $\approx 7347700000000000000000 \text{ kg}$

m_z – mass of the planet Earth $\approx 59,73600000000000000000000 \text{ kg}$.

For example, let us determine the percentage difference between the gravitational force of the planet Earth on its Moon satellite at perigee and the gravitational force of the planet Earth on its Moon satellite at an average distance from

the surface of the Sun, according to the refined law of universal gravitation by A. N. Belashov.

$$\begin{aligned} 202202175737265429431.03 \text{ N} &= 100\% \\ 1.8122360697945458 \times 10^{20} \text{ N} &= X\% \\ 89.6249539 &= X\% \end{aligned}$$

where:

FT- gravitational force between the planet Earth, having an acceleration of free fall in space $\approx 9.80665 \text{ m/s}^2$, and the Moon, having an acceleration of free fall on the Moon $\approx 35.98547548 \text{ m/s}^2$, according to the refined law of universal gravitation, both located at an average distance from the surface of the Sun $\approx 202202175737265429431.03 \text{ N}$.

FT – gravitational force of universal gravitation between the planet Earth, which has an acceleration of free fall of bodies in space $\approx 9.80665 \text{ m/s}^2$, and the Moon, which has an acceleration of free fall on the Moon $\approx 35.98547548 \text{ m/s}^2$, according to the refined law of universal gravitation; these bodies are located at perigee with a force of $\approx 18122360697945457053.5 \text{ N}$.

We will determine by what percentage the gravitational force exerted by the Moon on the planet Earth at perigee is less than the gravitational force of the Moon positioned at the average distance from the surface of the Sun.

$$100\% - 89.6249539\% = 10.375\%$$

Let us determine the distance from the surface of the Sun to the surface of the Moon at apogee.

$$L_{sz} = L_{c3} + L_m + D_{\oplus}$$

$$L_{sz} = 149500000000 \text{ m} + 405500000 \text{ m} + 12756200 \text{ m} = 149918256200 \text{ m}$$

where:

Lsz – distance from the surface of the Sun to the surface of the Moon at apogee, m

Lsz – average distance from the surface of the Sun to the surface of the Earth $\approx 149500000000 \text{ m}$

Dz – diameter of the Earth $\approx 12,756,200 \text{ m}$

Lm – distance from the surface of the Earth to the surface of the Moon at apogee $\approx 405,500,000 \text{ m}$

For instance, according to the refined law of universal gravitation, we determine the gravitational force of the Earth on its satellite, the Moon, located at apogee.

$$F_T = \frac{[(m_1 \cdot g_1) + (m_2 \cdot g_2)] \cdot L \cdot M^2}{(L_{c3} \cdot L_{c\oplus}) + (L_{c\oplus} \cdot L_{c3})} = \frac{H \cdot M^2}{M^2} = H$$

$$F_T = \frac{[(5,9722 \cdot 10^{24} \text{ кг} \cdot 9,8 \text{ м/с}^2) + (7,342 \cdot 10^{22} \text{ кг} \cdot 35,9 \text{ м/с}^2)] \cdot 363300000 \cdot \text{м}^2}{(149500000000 \text{ м} \cdot 149133223720 \text{ м}) + (149500000000 \text{ м} \cdot 149133223720 \text{ м})} = 181223606979454576053,5 \text{ Н}$$

where:

F_T – gravitational force between the planet Earth and its satellite the Moon, N

L_{sz} – the average distance from the Sun's surface to the Earth's surface ≈ 1495 million km

L_{rsl} – average distance from the surface of the Sun to the surface of the Moon at apogee $\approx 149,918,256,200$ m

L_{rsl} – horizontal distance from the surface of the Sun to the surface of the Earth ≈ 0 m

L_{rsl} – horizontal distance from the surface of the Sun to the surface of the Moon ≈ 0 m

L_m – the distance from the surface of the Earth to the surface of the Moon at apogee $\approx 405,500,000$ m

g_1 – magnitude of the acceleration due to gravity on planet Earth ≈ 9.80665 m/s²

g_2 – magnitude of the acceleration due to gravity on the Moon ≈ 35.98547548 m/s²

m_n – the mass of the Moon $\approx 7.3477 \times 10^{22}$ kg

m_z – mass of Earth $\approx 5.9736 \times 10^{24}$ kg.

For example, we determine the percentage difference between the gravitational force exerted by planet Earth on its satellite the Moon when located at apogee and the gravitational force exerted by Earth on the Moon at the average distance from the surface of the Sun, according to the refined law of universal gravitation by A. N. Belashov.

$$202202175737265429431.03 \text{ N} = 100\%$$

$$224587497162173227485.2 \text{ N} = X\%$$

$$X = 111.0707\%$$

where:

F_T – gravitational force between the planet Earth, having an acceleration of free fall in space ≈ 9.80665 m/s², and the Moon, having an acceleration of free fall on the Moon ≈ 35.98547548 m/s², according to the refined law of universal gravitation, both located at an average distance from the surface of the Sun $\approx 202254308209171407206.79$ N

F_T – the gravitational force between the planet Earth, having an acceleration of free fall of bodies in space ≈ 9.80665 m/s², and the Moon, having an acceleration of free fall on the Moon ≈ 35.98547548 m/s², according to the refined law of universal gravitation, when they are located at apogee, $\approx 224587497162173227485.2448$ N.

Let us determine by what percentage the gravitational force exerted by the Moon on the planet Earth at apogee exceeds the gravitational force of the Moon at the average distance from the surface of the Sun.

$$111.0707\% - 100\% = 11.0707\%$$

Calculations show that at apogee the gravitational force between the planet Earth and its satellite the Moon is 11.0707% greater than the gravitational force

between the Moon and the Earth located at the average distance from the surface of the Sun.

Calculations show that at perigee the gravitational force between the planet Earth and its satellite the Moon is 10.375% less than the gravitational force between the Moon and the Earth located at the average distance from the surface of the Sun.

It is particularly necessary to emphasize that the gravitational force between the planet Earth and its satellite the Moon, when in aphelion and perihelion, will have significantly different values, which cannot be determined by Newton's law of Universal Gravitation with the 'gravitational constant.' This law does not account for the distance from the surface of planet Earth and its satellite the Moon to the surface of the Sun, nor the interactions between planet Earth and its satellite the Moon.

In conclusion, it can be stated that the Moon, having a free-fall acceleration in space 3.6 times greater than that on Earth, exerts a greater influence on the gravitational force towards planet Earth than the Earth exerts on the Moon. It should be noted that all existing calculations must be reconsidered, since our material world is highly heterogeneous, and all processes occurring within it – resulting from randomly arising circumstances that unfold over time – mutually influence one another to varying degrees. Consequently, a new theory of multifaceted dependence is proposed. In this world, everything is interconnected, and each natural phenomenon depends on others to varying extents. More active material bodies dominate less active ones; therefore, truly independent and constant constants, laws, or physical quantities cannot exist. For example, the new law of antigravitational interaction and counteraction between two material bodies located within the space of the Solar or another system is closely connected to the new law of gravitational attraction of a single material body situated in the Solar system space toward the central star, the Sun. Simultaneously, the laws of gravitational attraction, cosmic interaction, and counteraction are continuously dependent on the new law of activity of a material body located in space and on the new law governing the free fall acceleration of bodies in space. The listed laws are closely connected with the new law of energy between two material bodies within the Solar system, as well as the new law describing the energy of a single material body within the Solar system relative to the central star Sun, among others...

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THE USE OF THE DECISION TREE METHOD FOR AUTOMATED WATER QUALITY ANALYSIS

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Abstract. *The article describes applicability of the machine learning methods for the problem of automatic water quality analysis. All research manipulations were performed using available Python libraries, such as Pandas, Seaborn, scikit-learn etc. The results suggest, that machine learning became a valuable tool for water quality determination, despite such analysis requires certain preparations.*

Keywords: *water quality, decision trees, gradient boosting, machine learning, pandas, scikit-learn.*

Access to safe drinking water remains a pressing global issue. According to the 2022 UNESCO report, 26% of the world's population lacks access to safe drinking water, while 46% lack access to basic sanitation services [1]. This challenge can be addressed either by identifying new sources of potable water or by treating existing water supplies to meet acceptable quality standards.

Water quality is characterized by a range of physicochemical parameters, including pH, hardness, total dissolved solids (TDS), organic matter content, heavy metals, insoluble impurities, and others [2]. If water were valued solely as a source of H₂O molecules, quality assessment would be straightforward: the lower the concentration of any substances other than water itself, the better. However, water also serves as an important source of essential trace elements and ions (sodium, potassium, magnesium, calcium, sulfates, chlorides, fluorides, etc.) required for normal human physiological function. Consequently, assessing water quality based on its trace element and ion composition is a highly relevant task. This objective can be effectively achieved using machine learning methods [3, 4].

This study demonstrates the applicability of decision tree algorithms for predicting drinking water quality. Additionally, a comparative analysis is conducted between the decision tree model and an ensemble method built upon decision trees – gradient boosting. The analytical toolkit comprises the Python libraries for statistical and scientific computing: pandas, scikit-learn, NumPy, Seaborn, and Matplotlib.

The dataset was obtained from the online platform Kaggle and is available at: <https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/adityakadiwal/water-potability/data>

The dataset contains information on 3,276 water samples, including the following parameters:

- pH – hydrogen ion concentration;
- Hardness – water hardness (mg/L);
- Solids – insoluble particles content (ppm);
- Chloramines – chloramine concentration (ppm);
- Sulfates – sulfate concentration (mg/L);
- Conductivity – electrical conductivity ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$);
- Organic_carbon – total organic carbon content (ppm);
- Trihalomethanes – trihalomethane concentration ($\mu\text{g}/\text{L}$);
- Turbidity – turbidity (NTU);
- Potability – suitability for human consumption (target variable).

Unfortunately, the dataset author did not specify the measurement protocols or sampling locations; however, based on the accompanying description, it can be inferred that the data were collected at the Hawassa University campus in WondoGenet, Ethiopia. All variables are quantitative, with no categorical features present. For computational efficiency and memory optimization, the Potability variable was immediately converted to a boolean type upon import, as it contains only binary values (1 and 0). Exploratory data analysis was performed using descriptive statistics tools, specifically the pandas `describe()` function.

	ph	Hardness	Solids	Chloramines	Sulfate	Conductivity	Organic_carbon	Trihalomethanes	Turbidity	Potability
count	2785.000000	3276.000000	3276.000000	3276.000000	2495.000000	3276.000000	3276.000000	3114.000000	3276.000000	3276.000000
mean	7.080795	196.365496	22014.092526	7.122277	333.775777	426.205111	14.284970	66.396293	3.966786	0.390110
std	1.594320	32.879761	8768.570828	1.583085	41.416840	80.824064	3.308162	16.175008	0.780382	0.487849
min	0.000000	47.432000	920.942611	0.952000	129.000000	181.483754	2.200000	0.739000	1.450000	0.000000
25%	6.093092	176.800638	19666.690297	6.127421	307.699498	365.734414	12.065801	55.844536	3.439711	0.000000
50%	7.036752	196.967627	20927.833607	7.130299	333.073546	421.884968	14.218338	66.622485	3.955026	0.000000
75%	8.062066	216.667406	27332.762127	8.114887	359.960170	481.792304	16.557652	77.337473	4.500320	1.000000
max	14.000000	323.124000	61227.196008	13.127000	481.030642	753.342620	28.300000	124.000000	6.739000	1.000000

Decision tree classifier

Initial data preprocessing involved: identifying missing values and duplicates, imputing missing data, and examining inter-variable correlations. Missing values were imputed using the column-wise median. Class balancing was performed using undersampling (truncating the majority class to match the size of the minority class), SMOTE (Synthetic Minority Over-sampling Technique), and ADASYN (Adaptive Synthetic Sampling). Consequently, six distinct datasets were generated from the initial split: three with missing values removed (Undersampling, SMOTE, ADASYN) and three with median imputation (Undersampling, SMOTE,

ADASYN). Decision tree-based classifiers were trained on these datasets, followed by hyperparameter optimization using «RandomizedSearchCV».

	Accuracy		
	Undersampling	SMOTE	ADASYN
Missing values removal	0.5839	0.6086	0.6059
Median imputation	0.5656	0.5709	0.5959

Without hyperparameter optimization, the best performance with missing values removed was achieved using SMOTE balancing, whereas median imputation yielded optimal results with ADASYN. Examination of the confusion matrix reveals that these synthetic data-based balancing methods shift class prediction balance toward the generated samples, which is suboptimal.

Conversely, undersampling shifts the class balance toward the negative class (i.e., zero). In practice, accuracy values in the range of 0.5–0.7 for this dataset indicate that the classifier predominantly assigned samples to a single class, yielding high precision for one class but low precision for the other. Following hyperparameter optimization via «RandomizedSearchCV», the highest accuracy achieved with undersampling was 0.588. This result is considered unsatisfactory, despite improvements in true positives (TP) and true negatives (TN), which now exceed false positives (FP) and false negatives (FN). Median imputation did not improve classification performance across any of the balancing methods (undersampling, SMOTE, ADASYN).

Gradient Boosting

To enhance analytical performance, an ensemble method – gradient boosting – was employed. A histogram-based variant was utilized due to its computational efficiency and native support for NaN values. Several experiments were conducted: the classifier was trained on (1) undersampled data, (2) unbalanced data without prior preprocessing, (3) SMOTE-balanced data, and (4) ADASYN-balanced data. The resulting performance metrics are as follows:

UndersampledHistGB	HistGB	SMOTE HistGB	ADASYN HistGB:
0.6035	0.6643	0.7	0.6815

1. While undersampling improves class balance (TP and TN exceed FP and FN), overall accuracy decreases by approximately 6% compared to unbalanced data.

2. As expected, unbalanced data yielded high accuracy for the negative class but low accuracy for the positive class.

3. SMOTE balancing produces a confusion matrix distribution similar to that of undersampling, yet overall accuracy is higher, surpassing even unbalanced data and reaching 0.70.

4. ADASYN exhibits a pattern comparable to SMOTE, but with slightly lower overall accuracy.

The same experimental protocol was repeated for the median-imputed dataset. The results indicate that ADASYN balancing yields the best performance with median imputation (accuracy: 0.662), which is comparable to unbalanced data (0.664) but lags behind SMOTE-balanced data with missing values removed.

Notably, hyperparameter optimization via «RandomizedSearchCV» on the SMOTE dataset does not yield significant improvements in accuracy. The final optimized result is 0.7028, marginally superior to the unoptimized algorithm.

In conclusion, machine learning-based water quality assessment is feasible but demands rigorous data preprocessing and preparation. Decision tree algorithms achieve acceptable accuracy in pattern recognition within the dataset; however, ensemble methods such as gradient boosting demonstrate superior performance for this task.

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NATURAL RAW MATERIALS OF ENDEMIC MEDICINAL WORMWOODS OF KOPETDAG AND THEIR RATIONAL USE

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Abstract. *The purpose of this work is to make a preliminary assessment of the resource potential of useful and promising wild-growing wormwoods of mountainous Turkmenistan on the example of Kopetdag. According to the generally accepted methodology, the raw materials of endemic wormwoods of Kopetdag were determined. The data of oral questioning of the local population on the use of endemic and subendemic medicinal wormwoods in Turkmen folk medicine (“Ethnobotanical” and “Ethnomedical questionnaire”). The results obtained expand and complement the information about the chemical composition of wormwood growing in the Kopetdag region and provide an opportunity to expand the raw material base of plants containing essential oils.*

Keywords: *raw materials, phytochemistry, essential oils, wormwood, operational reserve, Kopetdag.*

Introduction. The medicinal properties of wormwood and its wide distribution have determined a sustained interest in its study [1; 4–6]. The study of the characteristics of natural resources and the chemical composition of wormwood species dominating the vegetation cover of the Kopetdag territory is a necessary condition for their rational use [5; 6]. Due to the unique composition of biologically active substances, essential oils, and a wide spectrum of pharmacological effects, some endemic and subendemic wormwood species require thorough investigation for their broad application in medical practice, as well as in other sectors of the national economy.

The resources of wild medicinal plants of the Central Kopetdag are of great interest for the medical, food, and other industries of Turkmenistan. On their basis, new effective medicinal preparations have already been developed, and they are also used in the production of soft drinks, etc.

Relevance. The ecosystems of the Central Kopetdag are associated with the most important industrially valuable wormwood species, whose raw material resources are practically unlimited. In total, 11 wormwood species grow here, 4 of which are of the greatest economic interest (in terms of occupied area and raw material reserves). Among them, the greatest economic importance in terms of area and raw material resources belongs to 4 endemic species: Kopetdag wormwood, Turkmen wormwood, santonica-like wormwood, and Badhyz wormwood [2; 8; 10].

The wide spectrum of pharmacological activity of biologically active substances and the unique composition of essential oils of Turkmenistan wormwoods make them exceptionally promising for in-depth research and wide application in various sectors of Turkmenistan's industry.

The study of wormwood species growing in the territory of the Central Kopetdag provides grounds to confidently assert that they may be economically profitable medicinal plants. In this regard, the study of the resources and chemical composition of endemic and subendemic wormwood species is highly relevant.

Methods. According to the generally accepted methodology [12], the raw material resources of some Kopetdag wormwood species were determined.

During expedition trips in 2024–2025, factual material and data from oral interviews with the local population regarding the use of endemic and subendemic medicinal wormwood species in Turkmen folk medicine were collected (“Ethnobotanical” and “Ethnomedical Questionnaire”).

Taking into account the peculiarities of the landscape, lithological, and natural conditions of the Kopetdag, the raw material resources of wormwoods were studied in different gorges. A system of conventional symbols and a topographic base at a scale of 1:50,000 were used for mapping.

The purpose of the present work is the preliminary assessment of the resource potential of useful and promising wild-growing wormwood species of mountainous Turkmenistan using the example of the Kopetdag.

Kopetdag wormwood (*Artemisia kopetdagensis* Krasch. ex Poljak.) from the Asteraceae Dumort. family is an endemic semi-shrub 35–40 cm high [2; 7; 8; 10]. At the beginning of vegetation, the plant is whitish-woolly, later becoming grayish-green. The root is vertical and woody. Fruiting stems are numerous and branched in the upper third. Leaf length is 1.5–2 cm. The panicle is oblong. Flower heads are sessile. It flowers in August and bears fruit in November [10]. The key area of the massif is located in the low mountains, where, compared with the foothill plain, plant development and productivity are 3–5 times higher (Table 1). It grows

on clayey and gravelly slopes of foothills and the lower mountain belt, forming extensive thickets, and is characterized as a plant forming an independent formation.

The distribution area extends from Gyndyvar to Archman with a total area of no less than 300 thousand hectares [1; 5; 10]. Flowering branches are harvested as medicinal raw material. Collection, drying, and procurement of raw materials are carried out according to the generally accepted methodology.

The aboveground mass contains up to 1.85% essential oil, which includes pinene, limonene, cineole (20), camphor (35), borneol, terpineol (15%), as well as inulin and mucilage [6; 9]. The high camphor content makes it possible to use this plant as a source of raw material on an industrial scale.

In Turkmen folk medicine, it is widely used in the form of infusions, decoctions, and ointments for heart diseases, rheumatism, sore throat, and also as an emetic and anthelmintic remedy [6].

One of the commercial massifs occupies a vast territory of the foothill plain and low foothills within the area between the settlements of Baherden and Bami in the western part of the Central Kopetdag.

The key section of the massif is located in the low mountains, where, compared with the foothill plain, plant development and productivity are 3–5 times higher (Table 1). Here, the plants are divided (according to bush habitus) into the following classes: I – large (height 48–50 cm, diameter 60×65 cm); II – medium (35–40 cm and 35×30 cm); III – small (respectively 25–30 cm and 20×25 cm).

Table 1. Yield of raw material mass of Kopetdag wormwood in the Archman massif

Class	Number of plants per 100 m ²	Weight of raw material from a model plant, g		Raw material yield, c/ha		Raw material reserve, t/100 ha
		1	2	1	2	
I	14	164	61	2.3	0.9	9
II	22	112	41	2.5	1.0	10
III	20	4	27	1.5	0.6	6
Total	56			6.3	2.5	25

Note. 1 – fresh weight; 2 – dry weight.

Thus, the exploitable reserve of raw material here amounts to 25 t/100 ha, while the volume of possible annual harvesting (90% thereof) is 22.5 t.

Turkmen wormwood (*A. turcomanica* Gand.) from the Asteraceae family is an endemic semi-shrub 30–50 cm high [8; 10]. Endemic to Turkmenistan [2; 7; 10].

The root is taproot and woody. Sterile shoots are brownish-gray, while the fruiting stems are numerous, up to 50 cm high, straight, rigid, rod-like, grayish-felted

at the beginning of vegetation, later becoming grayish-green. The leaves vary in color from whitish-felted to grayish-green, and their length is 1.2–1.5 cm. It flowers in August and bears fruit in November [10].

For medicinal purposes, the tops of the stems (with leaves and flowers) of wormwood are harvested. Their collection should be carried out during the flowering period (August–September); drying and procurement should be conducted under a canopy in the open air according to the generally accepted methodology or in a well-ventilated room, spreading the material in a thin layer on paper or cloth. Artificial drying is carried out in dryers with artificial heating at temperatures up to 40°C. The yield of dry raw material is 25%. The finished raw material is packed into canvas or paper bags. It is stored in a dry, ventilated place protected from direct sunlight.

A dominant species of ephemeroïd-wormwood communities involving halophytic elements of the lower and middle mountain belts, it occupies the territory from the western border of the Central Kopetdag (Bami station) to Kurtusuv, covering an area of more than 500 thousand hectares [5]. It sometimes grows together with *santonica*-like wormwood.

We investigated the raw material reserves in two massifs – Sayvan and Germab (Table 2).

Table 2. Yield of raw material mass of Turkmen wormwood in the Central Kopetdag

Class	Number of plants per 100 m ²	Weight of raw material from a model plant, g		Raw material yield, c/ha		Raw material reserve, t/100 ha
		1	2	1	2	
Sayvan massif						
I	7	180	67	1.3	0.5	5
II	15	155	57	2.3	0.9	9
III	8	86	32	0.7	0.3	3
Total	30			4.3	1.7	3
Germab massif						
I	20	112	41	2.2	0.8	8
II	26	83	31	2.2	0.8	8
III	15	50	19	0.8	0.3	3
Total	61			5.2	1.9	19

Note. 1 – fresh weight; 2 – dry weight.

The content of essential oil amounts to 1.95%, and it, in turn, contains pinene (20%), camphene, limonene, cineole, phellandrene (35), linalool (15), camphor (10), terpineol (10%), etc. [9].

We classified these plants according to their habitus: I – large (height 45–50 cm, diameter 60×65 cm); II – medium (35–40 cm and 35×35 cm); III – small (respectively 25–30 cm and 20×20 cm).

The exploitable reserve of raw material in the Sayvan massif amounts to 17 t, and in the Germab massif – 19 t. We adopted a value equal to 90% of the exploitable reserve as the volume of possible annual harvesting and, thus, 15.3 t of raw material mass may be harvested annually here, while in the Germab massif – 17.1 t.

Santonica-like wormwood (*A. ciniformis* Krasch. et M. Pop. ex Poljak.) from the Asteraceae family is an almost glabrous semi-shrub 30–45 cm high. Endemic to Turkmenistan [2; 10]. The root is taproot, thickened, and woody. Perennial shoots are shortened, woody, ascending, with grayish-brown peeling bark. The number of fruiting branches is 10–20; they are more or less straight or arcuately curved at the base, initially pubescent and later glabrous. Leaf length is 1.5–3 cm, oval in outline, doubly to triply pinnately dissected. The panicle is narrow and many-flowered. It flowers in September and bears fruit in November [10]. It occupies an area of more than 800 thousand hectares.

It grows on clayey and gravelly soil up to an altitude of 2500 m above sea level, often together with Turkmen wormwood, but unlike it does not form large massifs. In the medical industry, the aboveground part and inflorescences are harvested as medicinal raw material for the preparation of “wormwood seed.” Collection, drying, and procurement of raw material are carried out according to the generally accepted methodology. It should be stored in paper bags protected from direct sunlight.

The content of essential oil in the aboveground mass amounts to 0.4–0.5%, and it contains up to 15% aldehydes and a small amount of santonin [9]. The biometric characteristics of the plants are similar to those of Turkmen wormwood.

In Turkmen folk medicine, the inflorescences are used for preparing wormwood tea with anthelmintic properties. In addition, wormwood oil is produced and used for fever, dropsy, and bites of scorpions or black widow spiders [3; 6]. The raw material is also used in the food and perfume industries.

The productivity of the raw material mass was determined by us in the area of the Dushakerekdag mountain massif (Table 3).

The exploitable reserve of raw material is 9 t/100 ha, while the volume of possible annual harvesting (90% thereof) is 8.1 t.

Badkhyz wormwood (*A. badhys* Krasch. et Lincz. ex Poljak.) from the Asteraceae family is a semi-shrub 30–45 cm high. A subendemic species of Turkmenistan [2; 7].

Table 3. Yield of raw material mass of santonica-like wormwood in the Dushakerekdag massif

Class	Number of plants per 100 m ²	Weight of raw material from a model plant, g		Raw material yield, c/ha		Raw material reserve, t/100 ha
		1	2	1	2	
I	4	131	48	0.5	0.2	2
II	11	104	39	1.1	0.4	4
III	13	68	25	0.9	0.3	3
Total	28			2.5	0.9	9

Note. 1 – fresh weight; 2 – dry weight.

The root is taproot and woody. Sterile shoots are shortened and woody with gray bark. Fruiting shoots are numerous, white-felted, rigid, and rod-like. Leaves are densely cobweb-pubescent, 1–2 cm long. The panicle is narrowly pyramidal. It flowers in August and bears fruit in November [10]. The total area occupied by this wormwood is estimated at no less than 300 thousand hectares.

It grows abundantly in sandy and clay deserts, on foothill plains and in the mountains. In the Central Kopetdag, it has been recorded in its extreme southeastern part, whereas in the Eastern Kopetdag it dominates everywhere, occupying an area of more than 200 thousand hectares.

For medicinal purposes, the tops of the stems (with leaves and flowers) of wormwood are harvested. Their collection should be carried out during the flowering period (August–September), tying them into bundles; drying and procurement should be conducted under a canopy in the open air according to the generally accepted methodology or in a well-ventilated room, hanging or spreading them in a thin layer on paper or cloth. Artificial drying is carried out in dryers with artificial heating at temperatures of 40–50°C. The yield of dry raw material is 23–24%. The finished raw material is packed into canvas or paper bags. It is stored in a dry, ventilated place protected from direct sunlight.

The chemical composition has been studied insufficiently. The aboveground mass of the plant is used in the production of soft drinks. In Turkmen folk medicine, the green parts are used for anemia and other diseases. Fresh crushed leaves are used to treat severe bruises; they are applied to dislocation sites as an analgesic, as well as to abscesses, tumors, and ulcers, to the forehead and temples for insomnia, and are also used for pain caused by tendon sprains. Wormwood powder strengthens gastric juices and eliminates bad breath [6; 11].

The productivity of the raw material mass in the Manysh area, where the plant forms almost pure thickets against the background of ephemeral vegetation, amounts to 8 t/100 ha, while the volume of possible annual harvesting is 8.2 t.

Thus, these endemic and subendemic wormwood species contain macro- and microelements necessary for the human body in their chemical composition, with the lowest content of harmful substances. The above-mentioned wormwood species are environmentally clean, highly effective, and may be applied in medicine, as well as used in industrial production as valuable products.

The medicinal and technical raw material of the described wormwood species consists of the upper parts of the aboveground shoots with leaves and flower heads.

Harvesting is carried out during the budding phase: in August–September. In monospecific, “pure” wormwood stands, raw material collection may be carried out mechanically, while in areas heavily overgrown with other vegetation it is performed manually. The stems are cut at a height of 5–10 cm above the soil so that the length of the cut shoots does not exceed 25 cm. The collected raw material is first pre-dried (1–2 days) in small windrows and then finally dried in the shade with good ventilation.

The yield of dry raw material amounts to 34–40% of the harvested mass. Its moisture content should not exceed 13%, while organic and mineral impurities should be no more than 2%. The raw material has a bitter taste and a characteristic smell. The reserves of raw material of many wormwood species (provided they are rationally exploited) are practically inexhaustible.

However, it should be remembered that, by their nature and bioecological characteristics, wormwoods are predominantly mesothermic plants with a clearly expressed stage of summer dormancy and existing solely due to atmospheric moisture. Therefore, the condition of wormwood communities (annual production, biological reserve of raw material mass) depends on the meteorological conditions of the year.

The productivity of the aboveground phytomass of many species in humid years may be 10 or more times higher compared with low-water and dry years. In this regard, it is exceptionally important to forecast the productivity of wormwood communities and the strategy of their use in different years, to properly carry out raw material harvesting, regulate livestock grazing in the areas of their growth, etc.

The obtained results expand and supplement information on the chemical composition of wormwood growing in the territory of the Kopetdag and make it possible to broaden the raw material base of plants containing essential oils.

Thus, the brief scientific ethnobotanical and ethnomedical review, together with the results of bioecological and therapeutic studies of a number of endemic and subendemic medicinal wormwood species of the region, may serve as valuable natural raw material for obtaining new environmentally friendly medicinal preparations in the pharmaceutical industry of Turkmenistan. These may subsequently be used in gastroenterology, oncology, immunology, urology, cardiology, parasitology, epidemiology, dermatology, and other fields of traditional medicine.

However, when developing plans for their exploitation, it is necessary to take into account the condition and developmental characteristics of each plant

community and individual specimens. At the present stage, a number of new requirements for raw material harvesting operations have emerged, the most important of which are:

- ensuring the possibility of forecasting the dynamics of raw material reserves of plants possessing industrial resource potential;
- comprehensive coverage of all major resource indicators for a specific plant species;
- development of effective practical measures for the protection and rational use of the studied species;
- introduction into practice of remote research methods and comprehensive study of the resources of medicinal wormwoods of the Kopetdag.

A comprehensive study of the resources of medicinal plants of the Kopetdag is a reliable prerequisite for the implementation of this principle.

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**GEOLOGICAL AND STRUCTURAL FEATURES
AND THE GOLD-SULFIDE DEPOSIT OF THE GEDABEK
ORE OF THE LESSER CAUCASUS (AZERBAIJAN)**

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Abstract. *The article considers the geological and structural conditions of the placement and localization of the Gosha gold-sulfide deposit of the Gedabek ore field in the north-eastern part of the Lesser Caucasus. It has been established that the system of faults of submeridional and sublatitudinal strike plays an important role in the spatial distribution and localization of gold mineralization. Gold ore bodies are represented by three morphological types: zones of hydrothermally altered rocks, quartz-sulfide veins and veinlets. Comparison of the conducted analyses of gold-bearing metasomatites gold-bearing accumulations of pyrite, less often chalcopyrite, galenites and sphalerite are confined to the chloritization zone and quartz veinlets.*

Keywords: *Gosha deposit, gold, Lesser Caucasus, metasomatites, monoquartzites.*

The Gosha gold-sulfide deposit of the Gedabek ore field in the Lesser Caucasus is localized within the Gosha-Itkyrlan anticline of the second order, occupying the western part of the Ahmedabad-Gosha anticline in the zone of conjugation of the eponymous deep fault with fault systems oriented submeridionally and sublatitudinally. Within the deposit area (Fig. 1), the most widespread rocks are those of the basalt-andesite subformation of the lower Bajocian age from the Dzhegamchay suite, which exhibits the following stratigraphic structure from bottom to top:

1. Zeolitized andesitic porphyrites; 2. Fine- and medium-grained andesite-basalt and andesite with zeolite amygdules; 3. Andesitic porphyrites containing quartz-carbonate amygdules; 4. Intercalation of andesite lavas, andesite-basalt lavas, and agglomerate breccias with isolated magnetite grains; 5. Horizon of andesite and andesite-basalt clastolavas; 6. Alternation of agglomerate breccias, tuffs, and thin andesitic porphyritic lava flows. The total thickness of the deposits is 1345 m.

On the western flank of the deposit, Lower Bayois rocks are unconformably overlain by the Gosha-Itkyran subvolcanic body composed of rhyolitic and rhyodacitic porphyrites of the Upper Bayois, which are characterized by an acidic composition. The contact of the subvolcanic body is active, leading at the exocontact [1,123–126] to the formation of crushed, kaolinized, sulphidized, hornfels-like metasomatites, and at the endocontact – to secondary quartzites of monquartz and quartz-kaolinite facies. Secondary quartzites form the studied ore zones along major fracture systems and fault dislocations. All described rocks are intersected by numerous mafic dikes oriented predominantly sublatitudinally, less frequently submeridionally, and by acidic dikes oriented northeastward, as well as by small cross-cutting, layered, and stock-shaped quartz-diorite intrusions. Determining the age of these intrusions, given their association with mineralization, is a crucial aspect for developing a prospecting criterion.

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Tectonic fault dislocations within the deposit area are developed in four directions: 1. The regional Ahmedabad-Gosha deep fault, aligned along the sublatitudinal and northwestern directions, crosses the entire ore district and controls the position of three subparallel fault zones (northern, central, and southern) and the ore-bearing zones No. 1, 2, 3, 5, 5^a, along with their associated dike belts; 2. The Shikheibat deep-seated fault, oriented near-meridionally and to the northeast, controls the location of submeridional ore zones No. 4, 10, 11, 12, and 13, as well as the dikes and intrusive bodies that intersect them.

Fig. 1. Geological-structural map of the Gosha gold-sulfide deposit (scale 1:2000).

Legend: 1 – Upper Quaternary and modern deposits – loams, sandy loams, clays with angular rock fragments; 2 – Upper Baiossian formations – light gray with a brownish hue fine-grained quartz rhyolites and rhyolite-dacites; Lower Baiossian: 3 – horizon of andesite porphyrites with lenses and interlayers of agglomerate lavas, lava breccias, and gravel tuffs; 4 – horizon of clastolavas of fine- and medium-grained andesites; 5 – horizon of andesite porphyrites; 6 – horizon of fine-grained andesites with lenses of magnetite sandstones and interlayers of andesite-basalt; in the section: 7-amygdaloidal andesitic

porphyrites, amygdales filled with quartz-carbonate mass; 8-fine- and medium-grained andesites with rare amygdales filled with zeolite; 9-zeolitized andesitic porphyrites; 10-dikes of andesites and diabase porphyrites; 11-secondary quartzites: a) monoquartz facies and b) quartz-kaolin facies; 12-quartzification; 13-kaolinization; 14-epidotization; 15-chloritization; 16-sericitization; 17-limonitization; *disruptive faults*: 18-sub-latitudinal zones; 19-sub-meridional zones; 20-tectonic fault zones; 21-boundaries: 1-of rocks of different ages, Two distinct rock facies and three profile lines.; *Legend for structural diagrams*: 22 – orientation of the axial plane of the Shikheibat ore-controlling fault; 23 – orientation of the axial plane of the Gosha-Ahmedabad ore-controlling fault; 24 – dip planes of near-meridional zones; 25 – dip planes of near-latitudinal zones; 26 – isolines of fracturing; 27 – post-ore faults of various orientations; 28 – intersection nodes of ore-controlling faults with the Ahmedabad-Gosha anticline; 29 – maxima of ore-hosting fracture systems; 30 – orientation of the axis of the Ahmedabad-Gosha anticline.

Faults of the first group are the most widely developed. In the northern, central, and southern parts of the deposit, these are represented by subparallel, extensive fault zones. They are interconnected by lower-order faults and fault-adjacent ex-kinetic fracture systems.

The fault in the northern part of the deposit is traced by underground and surface mine workings over a distance of more than 2 km, with a thickness ranging from 78 to 125 m. The dip angles of the fault lie within $215\text{--}290^\circ$ and $75\text{--}80^\circ$. The internal structure is quite complex, characterized by the presence of branchings and their intersections, forming nodes. On the western flank of the deposit, the fault comprises four subparallel zones. Among these, the zone elongated linearly from west to east has been studied as ore zone No. 2. To the east, the faults merge, forming a prominent ore zone No. 1. In the central part of the deposit, the fault consists of three branches and is represented as ore zone No. 3.

The southern fault is oriented sublatitudinally with relatively stable geological parameters, extending across the entire eastern and central parts of the deposit for 500 meters. In the west, it branches into several small faults and then merges again, forming a lens-shaped ore zone No. 5, which is characterized by relatively high gold content.

In the central part of the deposit, sub-meridional faults are extensively developed. Their strike is NW 355 with a near-vertical dip, featuring frequent branching 0.2–1.5 m thick, clustered into a coherent zone of enhanced fracturing, mylonitization, and hydrothermal alteration with an overall thickness of 200 m.^o

All dislocations are represented by zones of brecciation and fracturing, as well as, to varying extents, pyritized, kaolinized, and sulfide-bearing rocks with gold mineralization, constituting ore bodies. Gold-rich zones are confined to thin

submeridional fault zones, which are later structures intersecting major northwest- and sublatitudinal-oriented faults.

The study of morphological features of ore deposits facilitated the reconstruction of the initial lithological-structural conditions of ore localization and clarified the reasons for the formation of varying ore body morphologies: lenses, stocks, tabular deposits, and stockworks. The Gosha deposit is characterized by shutter-shaped, spatially arranged subparallel veins and vein zones with varying degrees of mineralization, allowing for the detailed characterization of the internal structure of individual ore zones, which we have accomplished through the construction of structural fracturing diagrams.

Previous researchers have identified and studied approximately 20 ore zones [2,32], among which are: sublatitudinal zones Nos. 1, 2, 3, 5, and 5a, associated with the Akhmedabad-Gosha deep fault intersecting the dome of the Shamkhor uplift; as well as near-meridional zones Nos. 4, 10, 11, 12, and 13, spatially linked to the zone of the transverse Shikheibat deep-seated fault. Both faults are ore-controlling structures of the Gosha ore field, spatially associated with the granitoid intrusion. The presence of low-order endokinetic (internal) fracture systems in the studied area is confirmed by their abraded surfaces with slickensides, frictional clay, and the occurrence of cataclasites and mylonites formed later under the influence of exokinetic (external) disturbances. Ore zones are characterized by sporadically occurring stockwork structures, branching ore veins and veinlets, horse-tail type ore bundles, and reticular systems of veins and veinlets. Based on composition, they are classified into four groups: 1) quartz-sulfide (quartz-pyrite, quartz-chalcopyrite, quartz-pyrite-chalcopyrite-galena-sphalerite) vein bodies filling open cavities within the enclosing volcanoclastic-pyroclastic formations of the Bayos; 2) quartz-carbonate bodies with sulfide mineralization of later stages; 3) hydrothermally altered (chloritized, kaolinitized, pyritized) rocks, subjected to deformation in subsequent processes under the influence of exokinetic fault and fracture systems; 4) loosened clay-carbonate material containing fragmented quartz and pyrite corresponding to the final stage of formation of the Gosha gold-sulfide deposit.

Mineralized veins and their suites at the deposit form relatively extensive zones (3.5–13.0 m) with varying degrees of sulfide saturation, which comprise nests, veinlet-included, and fracture-bound accumulations. Accordingly, based on their fabric, ore accumulations are subdivided into: disseminated sulfide inclusions, cluster-included, sulfide nests, aggregate-massive lens-shaped bodies, and veins.

The main ore mineralization is localized within the chloritization zone up to tens of meters thick and quartz veins [2,28]. In the first case, gold-bearing pyrite, chalcopyrite, galena, and sphalerite are distributed rather uniformly along major fault zones and their associated shear fractures. In the second case, ore inclusions occur as isolated to clustered aggregates (18–20%) and, alongside pyrite, contain

chalcopyrite (5–6%); sphalerite and galena (1–2%) as well as other minor sulfides within the ore body.

The most widespread are massive-clustered ores, typically polymetallic in composition and confined to irregular, stepped fissure cavities of small size. These curtain-shaped lenticular and vein-type bodies are cut by late-stage quartz-carbonate veins. The thickness of the ore bodies and the distribution of ore components within them are highly uneven.

In general, the ore zones of the Gosha deposit are represented in section as a columnar, relatively massive, elongated stock with dip angles of 25–35° both to the NE and SW. The vertical extent of mineralization ranges from 240 to 270 m. It is controlled by inherited complex fault structures containing two (or three) discrete ore bodies or ore zones in paragenesis with dikes of various compositions (diabases, diabase porphyrites, spessartite-type lamprophyres, and diorite porphyrites). Diorite-porphyrite and diabase dikes of these compositions are widely developed within the deposit. Spatially, the relationship between ore zones and dikes is expressed as follows: 1. Ore zones intersect dikes (in some cases the reverse occurs); 2. Gold-sulfide quartz veins and veinlets penetrate fracture systems within the dikes; 3. Ore zones develop along the margins of dikes and flank them.

Thus, most dikes in the deposit area are pre-ore and often act as barriers for ore localization. In the first case, simple fault structures are present, whereas in the second and third cases, complex inherited structures are observed, which are long-lived and intermittently reactivated. Wall-rock metasomatic alterations are widespread and are mainly represented by secondary quartzites. Based on composition, four facies of gold-bearing secondary quartzites are distinguished: monoquartz, kaolinite, chlorite, and propylitic. In inherited faults at the contacts with dikes, the ore forms the greatest concentrations, which gradually narrow and transition into non-ore-bearing fractures with increasing distance. The association of dikes and ore-bearing veins within these structures is one of the key factors in the formation of the morphology of ore deposits. Among those described above, metasomatites – predominantly secondary quartzites formed from rhyolites and rhyodacites – are extensively developed within the ore zones of the deposit. Quartz-kaolinite assemblages of secondary quartzites are also well-developed along near-meridional and near-latitudinal faults, with which the gold ore mineralization of the deposit is closely associated.

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COMPARATIVE ASSESSMENT OF THE CIRCADIAN RHYTHM OF OXYGEN SATURATION IN CHILDREN WITH SEVERE COMBINED TRAUMATIC BRAIN INJURY

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Abstract. *Fluctuations in oxygen saturation (SC) during the first 10 days, throughout the entire observation period following SCTBI in children, remained within acceptable normal ranges. No significant changes were observed in the mean mesora values, SC levels during acrophase and bathyphase, circadian rhythm amplitude dynamics, or daily fluctuations of the indicator. In Group 1, fluctuations in SCR SC were observed at a higher level in children of Subgroup 1, somewhat lower fluctuations were noted in Subgroup 3, and the lowest SCR SC values were recorded in Subgroup 2 during the first 10 days following injury. In Group 2, SCR SC levels were highest among children of Subgroup 3, somewhat lower in Subgroup 2, and relatively low in children of Subgroup 1. The dynamics of CRSC are influenced by multiple factors, including the effect of MRP, pharmacological therapy, and specific aspects of patient care. Despite this, continuous monitoring of the SC parameter allows for preventive and timely corrective interventions, which substantially impact the effectiveness of comprehensive intensive therapy and optimize the treatment outcomes in pediatric patients with SCTBI.*

Keywords: *circadian rhythm, oxygen saturation, severe combined traumatic brain injury, children.*

Relevance

Saturation is a parameter that reflects the oxygen level in the blood expressed as a percentage. Oxygen enters the bloodstream from the lungs and is transported to all body systems. A decreased level indicates hypoxemia, which is highly likely associated with respiratory system impairment. A saturation level of 100% is considered normal for the adequate functioning of the lungs and other organs. During nighttime, saturation levels decrease, and the deviation from the norm can be significant. The nadir occurs between 03:00 and 07:00 hours. This period represents the most critical time for affected patients, during which the highest mortality rates are recorded.

The clinical presentation and prognosis in acute combined traumatic brain injuries are determined by the localization, severity, and extent of brain and extracranial traumatic lesions. Treatment of severe SCTBI is based, alongside comprehensive intensive therapy, on meticulous hemodynamic support, mandatory respiratory assistance, fluid regulation, and other therapeutic measures aimed at preventing secondary brain injury. Given the direct correlation between the incidence of secondary brain injuries and both the adequacy of oxygenation and the severity of hypoxia, the primary objectives of intensive therapy are to optimize cerebral oxygenation, prevent and treat intracranial hypertension and secondary brain injuries, and maintain cerebral perfusion pressure. It has been established that an increase in the depth and frequency of external breathing in SCTBI functions as a compensatory mechanism for developing hypoxia; an increase in cardiac output and intensification of tissue metabolism aimed at mobilizing additional energy resources may lead to secondary injury of the traumatized brain and the development of multiple organ dysfunction syndrome (1–5). In this regard, we considered it appropriate to study and evaluate changes in the circadian rhythm of oxygen saturation (CRSC) in children depending on the severity of traumatic brain injury.

Objective

To investigate and provide a comparative evaluation of the circadian rhythm of oxygen saturation in children with severe combined traumatic brain injury.

Materials and methods

Patients hospitalized at the Republican Scientific Center for Emergency Medical Care (RSC EMC) between 2018 and 2021 (Group 1) for SC TBI were admitted to the clinic due to road traffic accidents (23 cases) and falls from height (7 cases). In Group 2 (2022–2024), traffic accidents accounted for 32 cases, and polytrauma involved 4 children. Circadian rhythms of oxygen saturation (CRSC) in each group were studied within 3 subgroups. In Group 1: patients in Subgroup 1 (n=10) received conservative therapy based on indications; children in Subgroup 2 (n=11) underwent extracranial surgical corrective procedures; 9 patients in Subgroup 3 underwent simultaneous cranial and extracranial surgical interventions according to indications. In group 1, patients in subgroup 1 without surgery spent 26 days in the ICU, subgroup 2–30 days, and subgroup 3–30 days. Patients in group 2 were also examined in three subgroups: subgroup 1 consisted of injured children who received conservative therapy without surgery for 29 days (n=13); subgroup 2 underwent comprehensive intensive therapy including extracranial surgery for 20 days (n=15); and subgroup 3, who spent 28 days in the ICU, underwent both extracranial and traumatic brain surgeries as indicated (n=8). Procedures in the second group were performed within the first hours following the children's admission to the clinic. A statistically significant difference in the initial severity of injury among the groups was identified. Thus, in the second subgroup according to the ISS scale, children were 42% more critically affected, and in the

third subgroup 78% more critically affected ($p < 0.05$, respectively), than those in the first subgroup. In contrast, no statistically significant differences were found according to the GI scale. With clinical improvement, stabilization of hemodynamics and respiration, and restoration of reflexes and consciousness, patients were transferred to the specialized department. Given the pivotal role in the outcome and prognosis of the severity of the pathological status during the first cycle of the acute systemic inflammatory response, we aimed to study, identify specific characteristics, and evaluate the influence of the stress-inflammatory response occurring within the first 10 days in children with SCTBI. To provide a comparative evaluation of the detected deviations during the acute phase: within the first 10 days and over the entire duration of intensive therapy in the ICU (up to 30 days). We attempted to analyze and provide a comparative assessment of comprehensive intensive therapy during different periods from 2018–2021 and 2022–2024, when significant organizational measures were introduced to enhance emergency services aimed at maximizing the reduction in time from injury to provision of urgent specialized care.

Results and Discussion

Fluctuations in oxygen saturation (SC) during the first 10 days, throughout the entire observation period, remained within acceptable normal ranges. No significant alterations were observed in the mean mesora indicators, SC values during acrophase and bathyphase, the dynamics of circadian rhythm amplitude, and fluctuations of the parameter throughout the day (Table 1).

Table 2. Mean values of the phase structure of the oxygen saturation circadian rhythm in groups 1 and 2, %.

	Mesora	During acrophase	During bathyphase	Amplitude	Daily range
Group 1, subgroup 1, 10 days	98.8±0.2	99.2±0.2	98.4±0.3	0.3±0.1	0.8±0.3
Group 2 Subgroup 1 10 days	98.2±0.4	98.8±0.4	97.4±0.4*	0.7±0.1*	1.4±0.2*
Group 1 Subgroup 2 10 days	98.5±0.3	99.1±0.2	97.5±0.6	0.6±0.2	1.7±0.7
Group 2 Subgroup 2 10 days	98.4±0.3	99.3±0.4	97.6±0.3	0.9±0.4	1.7±0.5
Group 1, Subgroup 3, 10 days	98.7±0.2	99.3±0.2	97.8±0.3	0.6±0.2	1.5±0.2
Group 2, Subgroup 3, 10 days	98.8±0.4	99.5±0.4	98.0±0.5	0.7±0.2	1.5±0.3
Group 1, Subgroup 1, 26 days	98.5±0.4	99.2±0.3	97.5±0.8	0.7±0.4	1.6±0.8
Group 2, Subgroup 1, 29 d	98.2±0.5	99.1±0.4	96.8±1.1	0.9±0.4	2.2±1.2
Group 1, Subgroup 2, 30 d	98.2±0.3	99.0±0.2	97.1±0.5	0.8±0.2	1.9±0.6
Group 2, Subgroup 2, 21 d	98.1±0.4	99.0±0.3	97.2±0.6	0.9±0.3	1.8±0.5
Group 1, Subgroup 3, 30 d	98.6±0.3	99.2±0.2	97.8±0.5	0.6±0.2	1.4±0.4
Group 2, Subgroup 3, 28 days	98.8±0.5	99.5±0.4	97.6±0.8	0.7±0.4	1.9±0.9

* – statistically significant difference relative to the indicator in Group 1

A statistically significantly lower SC value was observed during the bathy-phase in children of Group 2, Subgroup 1, within the first 10 days by 1%, which resulted in a significant increase in the amplitude by 0.4% and daily fluctuation by 0.6% in the children of Group 2 (Table 1). Conservative management of patients during the first 10 days in Group 2 was accompanied by an enhancement of the stress response of the circadian rhythm of SC, manifested by an increase in both amplitude and daily fluctuation of the CRSC.

Table 2. Comparative Assessment of the Dynamics of Mesora CRSC in %.

Days	Group 1, Subgroup 1	Group 2, Subgroup 1	Group 1, Subgroup 2	Group 2, Subgroup 2	Group 1, Subgroup 3	Group 2, Subgroup 3
1	99.2±0.2	99.0±0.3	98.8±0.5	98.5±0.4	99.1±0.3	98.8±0.5
2	99.3±0.1	98.5±0.4	98.6±0.2	98.5±0.3	98.7±0.3	98.4±0.3
3	98.7±0.2*	97.8±0.3***	98.3±0.2	97.6±0.9	98.9±0.2	99.3±0.2
4	99.0±0.2	97.5±0.3***	98.4±0.2	98.2±0.2	98.6±0.3	98.3±0.3
5	98.6±0.4	97.5±0.4* "	98.8±0.2	98.4±0.3	98.9±0.2	98.2±0.3
6	98.9±0.2	98.2±0.3* "	98.8±0.2	98.7±0.2	98.2±0.5	98.4±0.4
7	98.7±0.2*	98.3±0.3*	98.3±0.4	98.8±0.3	98.5±0.4	98.6±0.3
8	98.9±0.1	98.4±0.2*	98.8±0.2	98.7±0.2	98.4±0.3	99.1±0.3 "
9	98.7±0.2*	97.9±0.3*	98.2±0.4	98.2±0.5	98.7±0.3	99.5±0.4 "
10	98.8±0.2	98.7±0.2	98.0±0.3	98.2±0.2	98.5±0.2*	99.0±0.3
11	98.5±0.2*	98.5±0.3	98.3±0.3	98.9±0.2 "	98.6±0.3	99.2±0.2 "
12	97.2±0.6*	98.6±0.4 "	98.0±0.3	98.3±0.3	98.7±0.2	98.7±0.4
13	97.8±0.4*	98.8±0.3 "	97.5±0.4*	97.7±0.6	98.9±0.2	98.4±0.5
14	98.2±0.2*	98.7±0.4	98.6±0.3	98.4±0.3	98.5±0.3	98.9±0.3
15	98.7±0.2*	98.7±0.8	98.0±0.5	98.6±0.3	98.7±0.2	97.2±0.4* "
16	98.9±0.4	99.3±0.1	98.2±0.3	97.9±0.4	98.2±0.2	98.6±0.7
17	98.7±0.3	96.3±3.6	98.8±0.3	97.7±0.4	98.2±0.3	99.0±0.8
18	98.1±0.3*	98.5±0.4	98.4±0.4	97.6±0.3	98.6±0.2	97.9±0.6
19	98.5±0.4*	98.5±0.3	97.6±0.3*	97.2±0.7	98.6±0.3	98.3±0.7
20	98.6±0.4	98.7±0.3	97.8±0.4	96.8±0.8	98.4±0.3	99.3±0.5
21	98.3±0.4*	99.0±0.3	97.9±0.6	98.1±0.6	98.0±0.4	99.0±0.1
22	98.0±0.6*	98.3±0.4	98.2±0.5		98.3±0.2	98.0±0.3
23	98.2±0.5*	98.0±0.4	97.7±0.3		97.9±0.3	99.8±0.4
24	98.7±0.4	98.1±0.6	98.0±0.6		98.6±0.4	98.9±0.7
25	97.0±1.2*	98.0±0.4	98.0±0.5		98.7±0.6	99.5±0.5
26	97.7±1.0*	97.4±0.6	98.4±0.4		99.1±0.2	99.1±0.9
27		96.9±0.8	98.1±0.5		98.9±0.2	100.0±0.0
28		98.3±0.8	98.1±0.6		99.3±0.5	98.4±0.8
29		97.6±0.5	97.8±0.5		99.2±0.3	

Days	Group 1, Subgroup 1	Group 2, Subgroup 1	Group 1, Subgroup 2	Group 2, Subgroup 2	Group 1, Subgroup 3	Group 2, Subgroup 3
30			97.9±0.5		98.1±0.2	

* – change is significant relative to the value on day 1.

™ – significant relative to the indicator in group 1.

As presented in Table 2, in the absence of surgical intervention, a decrease in the mesora of the CRSC was observed in both groups on day 3 by 0.5% and 1.2%, respectively. In subsequent days, only in group 2 did a decrease in the mesora of the CRSC relative to the indicator on day 1 persist, amounting to 1.5%, 1.5%, 0.8%, 0.7%, 0.6%, and 1.1% on days 4 through 9 ($p < 0.05$, respectively). A decrease in the mesora of CRSC in group 2 compared with group 1 was identified on days 3, 4, and 5 by 0.9%, 0.5%, and 1.1%, respectively. However, on days 12 and 13, the mesora level of CRSC was higher than in group 1 by 1.4% and 2%, respectively. It is noteworthy that in group 1, the mesora indicator of CRSC remained significantly lower than the value on day 1 by 11–15% up to day 26 of ICU treatment, yet within acceptable values above 96%. In the 2nd subgroup of the 1st group on days 13 and 19, a decrease in the mesora of the CRSC by 1.3% and 1.2%, respectively, was observed. Meanwhile, in the 2nd group, a statistically significant increase of 0.6% compared to the 1st group was detected on day 11. In the 3rd subgroup of the 1st group on day 10, a decrease in the indicator by 0.6% was identified, whereas in the 2nd group, statistically significantly higher values of 0.7%, 0.8%, and 0.6% were recorded on days 8, 9, and 11, respectively, as well as on day 15, compared to the 1st group. However, on the 15th day, the studied parameter was 1.5% lower than in group 1.

Fig.1. SCR SC during the first 10 days in group 1.

Fig.1. SCR SC during the first 10 days in group 1.

Fig.1. SCR SC during the first 10 days in group 1. A comparative assessment of the dynamics of the average circadian rhythm (SCR) revealed the following differences. In group 1, fluctuations in the SCR SC were observed at a higher level in children of subgroup 1, slightly lower levels were noted in subgroup 3, and even lower SCR SC values were found in subgroup 2 during the first 10 days after injury (Fig.1). In group 2, the SCR SC was highest among children of subgroup 3, somewhat lower in subgroup 2, and relatively low in children of subgroup 1 (Fig.2).

Fig. 3. Amplitude of CR SC in group 1

4. Amplitude of CR SC in group 2

A tendency toward an increase in the amplitude of CRSC fluctuations was observed in group 1 after 19 days of intensive therapy in subgroups 1 and 2, which was attributable to the gradual transition of children to spontaneous breathing. In subgroup 3, the absence of observed changes was due to more prolonged mechanical ventilation (Fig. 3). The increase in amplitude up to 3.4% in subgroup 1 of group 2 was associated with reintubation (Fig. 4). The dynamics of the mean level of CR SC are related to multiple factors, including oxygen concentration in the oxygen-air mixture, persistence of pulmonary inflammatory response, and interventions such as tracheobronchial tree sanitation, reintubation, changes in parameters and modes of mechanical respiratory support, and inflammatory response of the lung parenchyma. Nevertheless, continuous monitoring of the SC parameter allows for preventive and timely corrective interventions, significantly affecting the effectiveness of comprehensive intensive therapy and optimizing treatment outcomes in pediatric patients with SCTBI.

Fig. 5. Circadian fluctuations of CRSC.

Fig. 6. Circadian fluctuations of SC in the second group.

The dynamics of circadian fluctuations of oxygen saturation paralleled changes in the amplitude of CRSC in both groups of children receiving conservative therapy, with extracranial and combined cranial plus extracranial surgical interventions (Figs. 5, 6).

Conclusions

Fluctuations in oxygen saturation (SC) during the first 10 days, throughout the entire observation period following SCTBI in children, remained within the limits of normal accepted ranges. No significant changes were observed in the mean mesora values, SC levels during acrophase and bathyphase, circadian rhythm amplitude dynamics, or daily fluctuations of the indicator. In Group 1, fluctuations in SCR SC were observed at a higher level in children of Subgroup 1, somewhat lower fluctuations were noted in Subgroup 3, and the lowest SCR SC values were recorded in Subgroup 2 during the first 10 days following injury. In Group 2, SCR SC levels were highest among children of Subgroup 3, somewhat lower in Subgroup 2, and relatively low in children of Subgroup 1. The dynamics of CRSC are influenced by multiple factors, including the effect of MRP, pharmacological therapy, and specific aspects of patient care. Despite this, continuous monitoring of the SC parameter allows for preventive and timely corrective interventions, which substantially impact the effectiveness of comprehensive intensive therapy and optimize the treatment outcomes in pediatric patients with SCTBI.

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AGE-RELATED FEATURES OF THE CIRCADIAN RHYTHM OF SYSTOLIC BLOOD PRESSURE IN RENAL FAILURE IN CHILDREN

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Abstract. During replacement therapy for acute renal failure in the oligo/anuric phase, a somewhat more pronounced tendency toward elevation of the mesor of the circadian rhythm of systolic arterial pressure relative to normal values was observed in younger children compared to the older age group. In the older age group (7.1–18 years), a less pronounced increase of 5% in this parameter was observed during the specified period, compared to a 10% difference in the younger age group. In younger children, a lower threshold for cardiac function sensitivity and more pronounced overall hemodynamic lability were identified, characterized by increased amplitude, circadian fluctuations, and mesor of the circadian rhythm of systolic blood pressure. A more pronounced stress response of the circadian rhythm of systolic blood pressure in younger children was evidenced by an inversion of the daily biorhythm during the first 10 days in 60% of intensive therapy cases, whereas no inversion was noted in the older group.

Keywords: circadian rhythm, systolic blood pressure, renal failure, children

Relevance

Beginning with rudimentary methods for the removal of exo- and endotoxins from the body (such as bloodletting, and the use of laxatives and diuretics), efferent medicine has evolved into the most effective approach within the comprehensive treatment of exogenous and endogenous intoxication syndrome. Renal oliguria is caused

by parenchymal renal failure and can develop as a consequence of damage to the renal parenchyma by various injurious factors. However, in most cases, acute renal failure with oligoanuria is caused by two conditions: acute tubular necrosis and acute interstitial nephritis. Unfortunately, the number of children requiring hemodialysis due to oligoanuria developing during the exacerbation of chronic kidney disease – frequently diagnosed for the first time – is increasing. Acute tubular necrosis (ATN) results from a variety of causes, including ischemia, sepsis, surgical procedures, medications, toxins of plant and animal origin, and pigments (such as myoglobin). Acute interstitial nephritis (AIN) results from a hypersensitivity reaction developing in the kidneys following exposure to medications. Acute renal failure (ARF) with oliguria in patients admitted to intensive care units typically indicates systemic involvement (sepsis, multiple organ failure, toxic effects of drugs, contrast media). Renal replacement therapy (RRT) is a collection of diverse procedures, based on fundamentally different principles, performed to sustain the life of a patient who has lost the function of their native kidneys. Each of these functions can be partially compensated for by dialysis methods. Moreover, the kidney secretes hormones that stimulate hematopoiesis, activates vitamin B metabolism, and regulates blood pressure: these functions can be partially or fully supplemented by additional pharmacological therapy, whereas functions such as the inactivation of excess hormones can only be performed by a normally functioning kidney. Hemodynamic overload, venous congestion, activation of neurohormonal systems, natriuretic peptides, inflammation, endothelial dysfunction, oxidative stress and its effects on the remodeling of the heart and blood vessels, as well as mechanisms of cellular maladaptation, are currently regarded as the primary causes in the pathogenesis of acute heart failure. Cystatin C (Cys C) – a reliable laboratory marker for the early diagnosis of kidney function impairment and for assessing the glomerular filtration rate (GFR). In contrast to creatinine, the blood concentration of cystatin C is less influenced by age, sex, muscle mass, and diet, rendering it a more sensitive indicator of early renal insufficiency [1–7]. Due to limited information regarding patient management during replacement therapy, we undertook an investigation to study and evaluate the age-related characteristics of the circadian rhythm dynamics of systolic blood pressure (SBP) in children throughout this period.

Objective of the study

To study and evaluate age-related features of the circadian rhythm of systolic blood pressure in renal failure in children.

Materials and methods of the study

Hemodynamic and respiratory system monitoring data were analyzed in 16 children with diseases complicated by renal failure during the oligoanuric phase. Comprehensive intensive therapy included, alongside etiopathogenetic therapy, prosthetic replacement of respiratory and urinary system functions. Continuous hourly monitoring was performed in two age groups. Group 1 included children

aged 0.8 ± 0.4 years, with 5 boys and 4 girls. In Group 2, clinical data of patients aged 13.9 ± 3.2 years were examined, comprising 2 boys and 5 girls. In Group 1, the following diagnoses were identified: pneumonia – focal in 4 cases, polysegmental in 1; bilateral pneumonia complicated by sepsis in 2 cases; systemic inflammatory response syndrome (SIRS); acute kidney injury at the oligo-anuric stage in 3 patients; hemolytic-uremic syndrome (HUS) in 2; toxic-metabolic encephalopathy in 4; and acute respiratory failure (ARF) stages 2–3 in 6 patients. Background in 4 children: polycystic kidney disease; congenital nephrotic syndrome; nephromegaly; acute kidney injury in the recovery phase. In group 2: systemic lupus erythematosus – 3; Stevens-Johnson syndrome – 1; pneumonia – 6; sepsis – 4; rhabdomyolysis complicated by acute kidney injury – 1; acute nephritis – 1; chronic kidney disease in exacerbation phase – 6; sepsis – 1; SPON – 2; congenital malformation – solitary kidney – 1. All patients underwent extracorporeal blood purification (ECBP). The age-related difference was reflected in the duration of comprehensive intensive therapy: patients in Group 1 remained in the intensive care unit (ICU) for an average of 21.2 ± 12.2 days, whereas Group 2 stayed on average 12 days less (Table 1). Patients in Group 1 received 12 ± 7 sessions, while those in Group 2 received 6 ± 1.7 sessions, i.e., 50% fewer. In all patients, the CYSC parameter was assessed during the first 2 days.

Results and Discussion

A somewhat more pronounced tendency toward an increased mesor level of the circadian rhythm of systolic blood pressure (SBP) relative to the norm was observed in younger children compared to the older group. The age-related difference in the mesor of the SBP circadian rhythm in the older group during the first 10 days was 15% ($p < 0.05$).

Table 1. Mean Values of the Phase Structure of the SBP Circadian Rhythm

	Mesor	During Acrophase	During Bathyphase	Amplitude	24-hour Fluctuation
Group 1, 10 days	107 ± 3	118 ± 4 "	96 ± 4 "	11 ± 3	22 ± 6
Group 2, 10 days	123 ± 2 *	129 ± 4 *	117 ± 2 *	6 ± 2	12 ± 3 *
Group 1 (11–37 days)	111 ± 4	124 ± 7	98 ± 5	13 ± 4	26 ± 7
Group 2 (11–13 days)	123 ± 2 *	129 ± 4	116 ± 2 *	6 ± 2 *	13 ± 4 *

* – the difference in the indicator is statistically significant relative to group 1.

" – the difference is statistically significant relative to the mesor of the SBP circadian rhythm.

During the first 10 days in group 1, the acrophase value of systolic blood pressure was significantly higher than the mesor of the SBP circadian rhythm by 10%

($p < 0.05$), maintaining a tendency toward hypertension throughout the observation period. In the older age group during this period, a less pronounced increase of 5% was observed ($p > 0.05$). A statistically significant decrease in systolic blood pressure (SBP) during the bathyphase was observed within the first 10 days in both groups, amounting to 10% and 4% ($p < 0.05$, respectively). As is known, the stress response of central hemodynamic regulation is also characterized by an increase in the amplitude and circadian variability of this parameter. A statistically significant decrease in the amplitude and circadian range of SBP fluctuations was identified depending on age. Specifically, in older children, the circadian range of SBP fluctuations during the first 10 days was 45% lower; throughout intensive care in the ICU, the amplitude and daily variation of SBP were 100% lower compared to younger children ($p < 0.05$). The findings indicate a comparatively lower sensitivity threshold of cardiac function and overall hemodynamic lability in renal dysfunction at an early age, manifested by increased amplitude, daily variation, and mesor of the circadian rhythm of systolic blood pressure. These compensatory hemodynamic responses to renal ischemia occur earlier; the labile nature of hemodynamic function results in more rapid depletion of energy resources, causing therapeutic correction to be less effective in younger children compared to those older than 7 years. This extends the duration of intensive corrective and replacement renal therapy and significantly prolongs hospital stay.

Fig. 1. Dynamics of the mesor of the circadian rhythm of SBP, mmHg.

Fluctuations in the mesor of the SBP circadian rhythm at early age (Group 1) ranged from 100 mmHg on day 9 to 123 mmHg on day 27. In contrast, fluctuations in the mesor in the older group ranged between 120 and 130 mmHg (Fig. 1). It is noteworthy that the approximately weekly biorhythm is preserved in older children, whereas in early age this parameter was more disrupted, reflecting more

pronounced fluctuations in the average daily SBP level before 3 years of age. This underlies the vulnerability and rapid energetic depletion of cellular energy resources upon kidney injury at an early age.

Table 2. Circadian rhythm of systolic arterial pressure depending on age in mmHg.

Hours	Group 1, 10 days	Group 2, 10 days	Group 1, days 11–37	Group 2, days 11–13
8	109±7	123±5*	113±6	123±3*
9	107±6	124±4*	115±5	122±4
10	109±7	125±5*	112±7	121±3
11	105±6	126±5*	112±8	120±4
12	103±5	125±4*	113±8	123±4
13	106±7	124±3*	114±8	122±4
14	106±7	124±2*	112±7	124±3*
15	107±7	123±3*	114±8	123±4
16	107±8	123±2*	115±6	124±1*
17	104±6	123±2*	114±6	125±6
18	106±6	123±2*	118±7	123±2
19	105±4	124±2*	115±5	124±1*
20	109±3	122±2*	112±6	125±3*
21	107±5	123±2*	112±7	125±3*
22	106±5	123±2*	111±6	124±4*
23	107±5	124±3*	113±7	124±1*
24	107±4	122±2*	110±6	122±2*
1	109±4	121±3*	111±8	121±3
2	107±4	120±3*	111±7	122±4
3	106±4	120±3*	109±8	121±5
4	108±4	121±3*	112±9	127±4*
5	106±4	123±3*	112±6	122±1*
6	107±3	122±3*	113±7	121±4
7	108±2	122±3*	114±6	123±5

* – significant difference relative to the parameter in Group 1.

No statistically significant differences in systolic arterial pressure were identified between daytime and nighttime. A statistically significant age-related difference in systolic arterial pressure was observed over the 24-hour period, amounting to 15±2% during the first 10 days; during the following days of intensive combined therapy, the difference was 9±2%. A statistically significant increase

in the systolic arterial pressure (SAP) response of 6% ($p < 0.05$) was observed in the younger age group compared to older children. During daytime hours (10:00–18:00), this difference increased to 20% (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Dynamics of the age-related SAP response in %.

Notably, a dynamic increase in the amplitude of the circadian rhythm (CR) of SAP exceeding 20 mmHg was observed in Group 1 in a child after 28 days, which corresponded to acute heart failure under conditions of energy-deficit-related impairment of myocardial contractility in early childhood (Fig. 3). Additionally, unlike the pattern of daily SAP fluctuations in the older group, daily SAP variations reached 35 mmHg, and after 30 days, increased up to 48 mmHg (Fig. 4).

Fig. 3. Amplitude of the circadian rhythm of systolic blood pressure (SBP) in mmHg.

Fig. 4. Daily range of SBP fluctuations in mmHg.

During the first 10 days in Group 1, inversion of the circadian rhythm of systolic blood pressure (SBP) was detected in 60% of examined patients, whereas in Group 2 no inversion of the circadian rhythm of SBP was observed in any patient. In the subsequent observation period, inversion of the circadian rhythm of SBP

in Group 1 was present during 22% of the time over the following 27 days of extended intensive therapy, while it was absent in all patients in the older group. Thus, the comparatively more pronounced stress response of the circadian rhythm of systolic blood pressure (CR SBP) in early age was manifested as an inversion of the daily biorhythm during the first 10 days for 60% of the time throughout intensive therapy, whereas no inversion was detected in the older group, in which a normal acrophase projection of CR SBP was observed for 60% of the time during the first 10 days.

Table 3. Projection of the acrophase depending on age

Age groups	9–11 h	12–22 h	23–8 h
Group 1: 10 days	10%	30%	60%
Group 2: 10 days	60%	40%	0
Group 1: 11–37 days	15%	63%	22%
Group 2: 11–13 days	0%	100%	0

Fig. 5. Mean circadian rhythm of SBP, mmHg

Fig. 6. Correlation relationships of SBP.

As shown in Fig. 5, fluctuations in the mean circadian rhythm of SBP during the first 10 days were at 107 ± 1 mmHg, increasing to 113 ± 2 mmHg during the following 11–37 days (6 mmHg higher). In group 2, during the first 10 days, fluctuations in the mean circadian rhythm of SBP averaged 123 ± 1 mmHg; during the subsequent 3 days, these fluctuations remained practically unchanged (Fig. 5).

During the first 10 days, a tendency of inverse feedback between systolic blood pressure (SBP) changes and body temperature dynamics was observed, amounting to (-0.59) , alongside a direct correlation between SBP and body temperature in group 2 (0.67) (Fig. 6).

Fig. 7. Correlation relationships of SBP.

A strong direct correlation of SBP with white blood cell count (0.87) , cystatin C level (0.55) , and AST index (0.65) characterizes the hyperdynamic influence of the inflammatory response on cardiac output in early age children (group 1). In the older age group, a direct stimulating effect on SBP was observed for segmented neutrophils (0.8) and an inverse relationship with leukocyte count (-0.66) , blood creatinine (-0.77) , and blood urea (-0.49) (Fig. 7). Age-related differences in the inflammatory response affecting cardiac output were identified, reflecting the diversity of compensatory mechanisms arising in renal failure among children.

Conclusion

A slightly more pronounced tendency toward increased mesor levels of the circadian rhythm of systolic blood pressure relative to the norm was observed in younger children compared to the older age group. In the older age group, during the specified period, a less significant increase of 5% was observed, whereas in younger children the difference reached 10%. In younger children, a lower threshold of sensitivity of cardiac function and overall hemodynamic lability in renal dysfunction were observed, manifested by increases in the amplitude, circadian variation, and mesor of the circadian rhythm of systolic blood pressure. A more pronounced stress response of the circadian rhythm of systolic blood pressure at an early age was manifested by inversion of the daily biorhythm during the first 10 days, occurring in 60% of the intensive therapy period, whereas no inversion was

observed in the older group. Age-related differences in the inflammatory response to cardiac output were identified, characterizing distinct compensatory mechanisms arising in renal failure in children.

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REGULAR PHYSICAL EXERCISE IN THE FORM OF WALKING TO MAINTAIN HUMAN HEALTH

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Abstract. *It has been scientifically established that hypodynamia accounts for more than 20% of cardiovascular diseases and is one of the causes of type 2 diabetes mellitus. Regular physical activity in the form of walking not only improves metabolism but also enhances the functions of the cardiovascular, neuroendocrine, and immune systems of the human organism. The recommended activity level is 2500–2800 steps per day, and for optimal effect – 7200–8800 steps, which supports the maintenance of metabolism and cardiopulmonary function. This review provides a comparative characterization of aerobic, strength, high-intensity interval, and combined exercise modalities and grounds the prospects for employing personalized physical activity alongside digital monitoring.*

Keywords: *physical activity, hypodynamia, walking, cardiovascular diseases, adaptation mechanisms, prevention.*

Introduction

Modern lifestyle is characterized by a global reduction in habitual physical activity [1]. Hypodynamia ranks among the five leading risk factors for premature mortality [2]. Insufficient physical activity accounts for more than 20% of cases of cardiovascular diseases and type 2 diabetes mellitus [3]. This review examines molecular mechanisms of adaptation to exercise, including myokine production and activation of the AMPK/mTOR/PGC1 α signaling pathway [4]. It has been demonstrated that even moderate walking (optimal 7200–8800 steps per day) reduces the risk of all-cause mortality by 60% and cardiovascular diseases by 51% [5]. A comparative characterization of aerobic, strength, high-intensity interval, and combined training modalities has been presented [6]. The prospects of personalized physical activity and digital monitoring have been justified [7].

In the 21st century, the gap between the evolutionary-driven human need for movement and the actual level of everyday physical activity has reached critical proportions [1]. The urbanization of lifestyle, automation of labor, and widespread use of transportation have resulted in pervasive hypodynamia [2]. According to the World Health Organization, insufficient physical activity ranks as the fourth leading cause of global mortality [3]. Each year, millions of deaths and substantial healthcare expenditures are attributed to hypodynamia [4]. Reduced human mobility is recognized as an independent risk factor for the development of major non-communicable diseases [5]. Therefore, the issue of hypodynamia is currently regarded not only as a medical problem but also as a systemic social challenge [1]. Understanding the precise mechanisms underlying the protective effects of physical exercise is essential for the development of effective preventive strategies [6].

Objective and tasks of the study

The objective of the present study is to analyze contemporary scientific data on the influence of regular physical exercise on human health [7].

Research methods

Selection of publications was conducted using the PubMed, Web of Science, eLIBRARY.RU, and CyberLeninka databases.

Research Findings

Prolonged sedentary behavior increases the risk of cardiovascular diseases by 34% (HR = 1.34; 95% CI: 1.26–1.43) [3]. Regular physical activity, conversely, reduces this risk by 29% (HR = 0.71; 95% CI: 0.66–0.77) [3]. Regular exercise promotes improvements in the lipid profile: an increase in high-density lipoprotein cholesterol by 2.38 mg/dL, a decrease in triglycerides by 7.27 mg/dL, and total cholesterol by 6.84 mg/dL [4]. Hypodynamia is also linked to the onset of obesity, type 2 diabetes mellitus, osteoporosis, and certain cancer types [2]. Moreover, insufficient physical activity impairs mental health by increasing the incidence of anxiety and depressive disorders [6]. Adaptation to regular exercise

involves physiological, hormonal, and epigenetic mechanisms [4]. During contraction, skeletal muscles produce myokines – cytokines exhibiting anti-inflammatory properties [4]. Key adaptive signaling pathways include AMP-activated protein kinase (AMPK), mTOR, and the transcriptional coactivator PGC-1 α [6]. Exerkines – signaling molecules synthesized in response to physical exertion – regulate metabolism, inflammation, and neuroplasticity [4]. Combined training modalities (aerobic plus resistance exercises) activate cardioprotective transcriptional programs, reduce arterial blood pressure, and enhance insulin sensitivity [6]. Epigenetic modifications (DNA methylation, microRNAs, telomere stability) are regarded as mechanisms of sustained protection against chronic diseases [4]. The largest meta-analysis, comprising data from more than 75,000 participants, demonstrated a dose-response relationship between daily step count and reduced mortality risk [5]. A daily count of 2500–2800 steps is already associated with a statistically significant reduction in mortality risk [5]. The optimal amount for maximal prevention of cardiovascular outcomes is 7,200–8,800 steps per day [5, 8, 9]; it is also necessary to account for the influence of cold exposure on the organism [10]. Moreover, walking pace confers additional benefits: brisk walking is more effective than slow walking [5]. A target range of 8,000–10,000 steps per day is recommended for population-level programs [7, 8, 9], as evidenced by the data presented in Table 1. These data demonstrate that aerobic exercise, particularly walking, is the most effective modality for cardioprotection [3, 5]. Strength training is essential for the preservation of muscle mass and metabolic health [6]. High-intensity interval training (HIIT) is time-efficient but requires medical supervision [6]. Combined programs demonstrate the greatest synergistic effect [6]. Mind-body practices (yoga) are valuable as an adjunct for stress reduction [7].

Table 1. Comparative analysis of different forms of physical training and their effects on health

Training type (reference)	Examples (reference)	Primary physiological effects (reference)	Effect on mortality and cardiovascular diseases (reference)	Characteristics and limitations (reference)	Recommended volume for health (reference)
Aerobic continuous exercise (moderate intensity) [6]	Walking, running, swimming, cycling [6]	Strengthening of cardiovascular and respiratory systems; Improvement of lipid profile and insulin sensitivity [3][4]	Reduction in cardiovascular disease risk by 29% (HR=0.71) [3]; Reduction in all-cause mortality by up to 37% [5]	Accessible, low injury risk; requires regular adherence [6]	At least 150 minutes per week of moderate-intensity or at least 75 minutes of vigorous-intensity activity [6]

Training type (reference)	Examples (reference)	Primary physiological effects (reference)	Effect on mortality and cardiovascular diseases (reference)	Characteristics and limitations (reference)	Recommended volume for health (reference)
Walking (specific modality) [5]	Daily walking monitored by a pedometer [5]	Reduction in risk of all-cause mortality; Accessible, requires no equipment [5][7]	Optimal dose of 7,200–8,800 steps per day; reduces cardiovascular disease risk by 51% and all-cause mortality by 60% [5]	The effect depends on step intensity [5]; A measurable target for populations [7]	Minimum of 7000 steps per day; Target range of 8000–10000 steps [5][7]
Strength (anaerobic) exercises [6]	Resistance exercises utilizing weights and body weight [6]	Increase in muscle strength and mass; Increase in bone tissue density; Improvement in metabolic health [6]	Reduction in cardiovascular disease risk through improved heart rate variability, lipid profile, and glycemia [6]	Necessitate technical preparation; risk of injury [6]	2–3 times per week, 8–12 repetitions, 2–3 sets [6]
High-intensity interval training (HIIT) [6]	Alternation of 30–60 seconds of intense exertion with rest periods [6]	Rapid enhancement of cardiorespiratory endurance; effective fat oxidation [6]	Efficacy comparable to continuous training with reduced time expenditure [6]	Significant load on the cardiovascular system; requires medical monitoring [6]	3 times per week, 20–30 minutes (including warm-up) [6]
Combined (aerobic and strength) training [4][6]	Combination of cardiovascular and strength training within a single session [6]	Synergistic effect: reduction in blood pressure, increased heart rate variability, and decreased inflammation [4][6]	Greatest efficacy in the prevention of cardiovascular diseases; activation of AMPK/mTOR/PGC1 α pathways [4][6]	Requires individualized planning [6]	Individually: 150 minutes of aerobic exercise plus 2 strength sessions per week [6]
Mind-body practices (yoga) [7]	Asanas, pranayama, meditation [7]	Reduction of anxiety and depression; Increase in serotonin and dopamine levels; improvement of flexibility [7]	Indirect effect: reduction of stress-induced inflammation [7]	Safe for the majority of individuals; Serves as a complement to primary training programs [7]	2–3 times per week for 30–60 minutes [7]

A promising direction is the personalization of physical activity based on genetic, epigenetic, and metabolic markers [4, 7]. Optimal combinations of intensity, volume, and character of load for patients with chronic diseases, elderly individuals, and people with obesity require further investigation [7]. The development and validation of digital tools (mobile applications, wearable devices) for monitoring and motivating physical activity represent a significant challenge [7]. Long-term randomized controlled trials are required to establish causal relationships between training regimens and long-term outcomes, particularly in the domain of cognitive health [4, 6, 8, 10]. Molecular mechanisms, in particular the role of exerkinases in the regulation of aging processes, open new opportunities for the pharmacological imitation of the effects of physical activity in patients with severe hypodynamia [4].

Conclusions

Insufficient physical activity (hypodynamia) constitutes a leading modifiable risk factor for premature mortality, surpassed only by smoking and arterial hypertension [2, 3].

Walking is the most accessible and effective type of aerobic activity [5]. A significant reduction in mortality risk is observed beginning at 2500–2800 steps per day, with the optimal range being 7200–8800 steps per day [5]. Different types of exercise complement each other: aerobic training (walking) is the most effective for cardiovascular prevention, while strength training contributes to the preservation of muscle mass and metabolic health. For the healthy adult population, it is recommended to sustain a minimum of 150 minutes per week of moderate-intensity aerobic activity in combination with strength training 2–3 times per week [6, 7]. A simple, clearly defined target of 8,000 to 10,000 steps per day is feasible and comprehensible for most individuals [5, 7, 9].

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CLINICAL AND FUNCTIONAL CHARACTERISTICS OF PATIENTS WITH DISEASES OF THE LUMBOSACRAL SPINE

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Abstract. *The main clinical and functional group of patients with spinal diseases consists of patients following uncomplicated trauma of the thoracolumbar junction and lumbar spine. Unlike patients with chronic nonspecific pain, this group is characterized not only by pain intensity and activity limitation, but also by the injury morphology, presence or absence of neurological deficit, degree of deformity, spinal canal compression, and indicators of spinal stability. The A. O. Spine classification is widely employed in contemporary studies to categorize such injuries, facilitating the association of fracture type with the selection of conservative or surgical treatment strategies.*

Keywords: *diseases of the lumbosacral spine, discogenic pain syndromes, radiculopathy*

Relevance

Diseases of the lumbosacral spine constitute a heterogeneous group of disorders. In clinical practice, nonspecific musculoskeletal pain, discogenic pain syndromes, facet joint pain, myofascial disorders, muscle-tonic responses, radiculopathy, spinal canal stenosis, spondylolisthesis, and sequelae of trauma and surgical interventions are commonly observed. In most cases, lower back pain lacks a single definitively established anatomical source and is therefore considered nonspecific pain.

A distinct clinical and functional group comprises patients following uncomplicated injury to the thoracolumbar junction and the lumbar spine. Unlike patients with chronic nonspecific pain, this group is characterized not only by pain intensity and activity limitation, but also by the injury morphology, presence or absence of neurological deficit, degree of deformity, spinal canal compression, and indicators of spinal stability.

The objective of the study is to provide a clinical and functional characterization of patients with diseases of the lumbosacral spine.

Materials and methods

A bibliosemantic analysis of the literature was conducted using the databases Scopus, Web of Science, MedLine, The Cochrane Library, EMBASE, Global Health, CyberLeninka, RSCI, and eLibrary.ru. Based on the keywords diseases of the lumbosacral spine and radiculopathy, 255 publications were selected, including 200 foreign and 55 Russian sources. This study presents a detailed analysis of 17 cases.

Results

In patients following lumbar microdiscectomy, the clinical-functional profile is determined not only by the initial discogenic radiculopathic syndrome but also by the degree of neurological deficit regression, recovery of muscle strength, residual pain, risk of recurrent disc herniation, and the condition of the operated spinal motion segment. Prospective follow-up of patients after microdiscectomy demonstrated that recovery of muscle strength within one year is achievable in most cases; however, severe baseline paresis is associated with a higher risk of incomplete recovery and poorer functional outcomes [1]. Recurrent disc herniation is considered one of the significant causes of repeat interventions following lumbar discectomy, with registry-based studies indicating that the outcomes of repeat surgery are generally inferior to those of the initial procedure [2]. Therefore, postoperative patient assessment should consider not only the fact of decompression performed but also the progression of pain, neurological status, motor function, and signs of recurrent discogenic conflict.

For the clinical and functional characterization of a patient, it is important to differentiate not only the nosological form of the disease but also the predominant symptom pattern. Patients with localized lumbar pain, pain radiating to the lower extremity, and clinical signs of radiculopathy differ in pain severity, levels of disability, recovery rates, and the need for ongoing monitoring. In the ATLAS study conducted in primary care, patients with lumbar and lower extremity pain were characterized by high pain intensity, significant limitation of activities, and frequent temporary work disability [3]. Subsequent observation of this cohort demonstrated that in pain associated with the lower limb, prognosis is determined not only by neurological signs but also by the duration of symptoms, patient perceptions of the disease, and baseline levels of functional limitations [4].

Pain is classified by symptom duration as acute, subacute, or chronic. According to Russian clinical guidelines, pain lasting up to 4 weeks is defined as acute, from 5 to 12 weeks as subacute, and 12 weeks or more as chronic. This is significant for rehabilitation because the goals of care may vary at different stages. In the case of acute pain, the primary focus is on excluding dangerous pathology, maintaining allowable activity, reducing pain, and preventing excessive limitation of movement. With a chronic course, the importance increases for restoring motor behavior, correcting persistent functional limitations, addressing psychoemotional factors, and gradually reintroducing physical load [5].

The duration of the pain syndrome alone does not reflect the full extent of the clinical picture. Patients with the same disease duration may exhibit considerable differences in walking ability, tolerance to sitting, ability to bend, sleep quality, confidence during household activities, and readiness to return to work. Therefore, the clinical-functional assessment of the patient should include not only the temporal characteristics of pain but also the extent of impairment in activities of daily living [4].

In the clinical-functional assessment of the patient, it is essential to recognize that pain is not limited to the mere documentation of tissue damage. The modern definition of pain emphasizes its sensory and emotional components, as well as the possibility of persistence of pain experience in the absence of ongoing tissue damage [6]. In diseases of the lumbosacral spine, an equal duration of symptoms does not necessarily correspond to an identical clinical profile. In one patient, pain may be predominantly associated with a peripheral nociceptive source; in another, sustained by a neuropathic component; and in a third, accompanied by signs of altered pain processing. It is necessary to describe not only the duration of pain but also its quality, distribution, association with movement, sensory disturbances, sleep, emotional responses, and patient behavior under load.

From a clinical perspective, it is important to differentiate local lumbar pain, pain radiating to the lower extremity, and radiculopathy. Radiculopathy is characterized not only by pain along the nerve root but also by neurological signs – sensory disturbances, diminished reflexes, and muscle weakness. In nonspecific pain, such signs are absent, with predominant clinical features including localized tenderness, restriction of movement, protective muscle tension, alteration of motor stereotype, and decreased load tolerance [5].

Localized skeletal-muscular pain often lacks a distinct dermatomal distribution and may be exacerbated by prolonged sitting, bending, or maintaining a static posture. In cases involving facet joints and the sacroiliac component, pain is frequently triggered by extension, prolonged standing, or axial loading. Worsening of pain, numbness, or weakness in the legs during walking and standing is more characteristic for spinal canal stenosis, with symptom relief during forward flexion of the trunk. In the radiculopathic variant, greater importance is given to pain along the

nerve root, paresthesias, decreased sensation, muscle weakness, and exacerbation of symptoms during coughing or sneezing [7].

The clinical and functional presentation in patients with diseases of the lumbosacral spine is determined not only by structural changes. Body weight, level of physical activity, nature of work, prolonged sitting, repetitive bending, load carrying, sleep quality, anxiety, depressive symptoms, and kinesiophobia are of significant importance. In the systematic review by L. K. Nieminen et al., it was shown that pain chronification is more often facilitated by high pain intensity, increased body weight, heavy physical labor, awkward working postures, and depression [8].

An additional component of the clinical-functional profile is the comorbid status. In patients with lower back pain, concomitant metabolic, cardiovascular, and respiratory disorders may exacerbate activity limitations, reduce exercise tolerance, and modify the safety requirements of the rehabilitation program. Therefore, during the initial patient evaluation, it is advisable to document not only neurological signs and pain intensity but also obesity, diabetes mellitus, arterial hypertension, respiratory dysfunction, and pharmacotherapy that may influence exercise tolerance [9].

Motor control impairments warrant particular attention. Experimental studies have demonstrated that in patients with lower back pain, the timing of activation of deep trunk muscles, especially the transverse abdominal muscle, may be altered, indicating impaired stabilization of the lumbopelvic region [10]. Subsequent studies have shown that nonspecific chronic pain is heterogeneous in its motor manifestations; different patients may be characterized predominantly by protective rigidity, excessive tension of superficial muscles, impaired control of trunk posture during sitting, and difficulty with active control of lumbar movements [11]. For these reasons, it is essential to evaluate not only muscle strength but also movement quality and the patient's ability to control the position of the pelvis, trunk, and lumbar spine during habitual actions.

Functional disorders in lumbosacral pathology are manifested by changes in range of motion, reduced control of the lumbopelvic complex, impaired coordination of trunk and lower limb muscles, and asymmetry of loading during walking and daily activities. In some patients, involuntary limitation of movement develops due to pain and anticipation of injury. This leads to reduced physical activity, decreased muscular endurance, and perpetuates a vicious cycle [8].

The behavioral component of pain frequently manifests in chronic conditions. Kinesiophobia, anticipation of injury, avoidance of loading, and low confidence in recovery may exacerbate disability regardless of the severity of pain. During the development of the Fear-Avoidance Beliefs Questionnaire, it was demonstrated that patients' beliefs about the harmfulness of physical activity and work are associated with limitations in daily activities and work disability [12]. In patients with acute pain related to occupational load, the severity of work-related fears predicted

prolonged work limitations [13]. In chronic pain, reduction of fear of movement and increased perceived control over pain were associated with decreased disability, even after adjusting for changes in pain intensity [14]. Therefore, psycho-emotional and behavioral characteristics should be regarded as integral components of the patient's clinical-functional profile, rather than as secondary manifestations accompanying the pain syndrome. This principle aligns with the International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health, wherein an individual's condition is evaluated through body functions, activities, participation, and environmental factors [15].

Conclusions

The A. O. Spine classification is extensively employed in contemporary research for the systematic categorization of spinal injuries, facilitating the correlation of fracture types with the selection of conservative or surgical treatment strategies [16]. In patients with uncomplicated compression and comminuted fractures without neurological deficit, multiple studies have demonstrated satisfactory clinical and radiological outcomes under conservative treatment [17].

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**RESEARCH ON THE MORBIDITY OF CHILDREN AT RISK
OF RETINOPATHY OF PREMATUREITY TO IMPROVE
THE EFFECTIVENESS OF OPHTHALMIC CARE**

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Abstract. This article presents a study of morbidity among 238 infants at risk of retinopathy of prematurity, aimed at subsequently developing measures to enhance the effectiveness of ophthalmologic care. Ophthalmologic abnormalities were identified in 78 (32.8%) of 238 examined children, with boys comprising 55.1% and girls 44.9%. The composition of ophthalmologic pathology was as follows: accelerated refractogenesis in 60.3% of patients, followed by refractive anomalies – hypermetropia at 19.2%, myopia at 10.3%, and other conditions at 10.2%. Astigmatism was recorded in 14.1%, binocular vision pathologies accounted for 14.1%, retinal vascular angiopathy for 6.4%, partial optic nerve atrophy for 5.1%, suspected glaucoma for 2.6%, and ptosis for 1.3%. Among patients with myopia, a high degree predominated (50% of all myopia cases). In the group of children with astigmatism, the hypermetropic form dominated (81.8%).

Keywords: premature infant, retinopathy of prematurity, refractive anomalies, pathology of the visual organ.

Relevance. Retinopathy of prematurity is the leading cause of preventable childhood blindness. The incidence of retinopathy of prematurity (ROP) is steadily increasing and causes blindness in approximately 20,000 premature infants annually worldwide, while another 12,300 children experience mild to moderate visual impairment [1]. According to various authors, the diagnosis of retinopathy of prematurity is established in 17 to 34% of surviving premature infants [2]. Thus, ROP dominates the nosological structure of ophthalmic pathology in children born prematurely. Most patients with ROP recover without complications or treatment; however, in severe cases, appropriate therapy is required [3]. Both prematurity itself and the treatment of ROP induce changes in the anterior and posterior segments of the eye, increasing the risk of serious complications. Premature infants may develop refractive anomalies due to alterations in the anterior segment, such as a shallow anterior chamber, steep cornea, or thick lens, as well as changes in the posterior segment, including an increased axial length of the eye. Studies have demonstrated that intravitreal injections of anti-VEGF agents and laser ablation of the peripheral retina induce myopia and astigmatism in patients with ROP. The ablative treatment methods employed can disrupt blood flow and cause ischemia of the anterior segment of the eye, potentially resulting in hypotony, iris atrophy, corneal edema, and cataract, which may ultimately lead to phthisis and loss of the eye. Thermal laser exposure can also induce cataract formation. Due to the fragility of the zonular fibers, the risk of complications in the anterior segment of the eye is increased during surgery. Scar membranes in ROP may extend to the posterior surface of the lens and cause progressive subluxation of the lens capsule and intraocular lens in the postoperative period [4]. ROP screening enables timely detection of infants requiring treatment and thereby significantly reduces the risk of severe visual impairment and blindness due to ROP. Currently, undiagnosed refractive errors are the leading cause of visual impairment in children. Since visual problems in children often develop asymptotically, regular medical check-ups including comprehensive ophthalmological examinations by an ophthalmologist are necessary for the detection of eye diseases. Such examinations play a particularly important role in the clinical follow-up of children who have experienced ROP. However, in many regions worldwide, access to specialized medical services remains limited. Accordingly, artificial intelligence (AI) has demonstrated significant potential in the diagnosis and treatment of pathologies, as well as in training medical staff to deliver high-quality medical care to patients [5]. The implementation of contemporary IT technologies requires differential diagnostic criteria that act as triggers for the subsequent development of ophthalmic pathologies in children [6, 7].

Objective of the study

To study the morbidity of children at risk of retinopathy of prematurity to improve the effectiveness of ophthalmologic care.

Materials and methods

In this study, a review of medical records (outpatient charts) of 238 prematurely born infants was conducted. These children were monitored in the consultative and diagnostic department of pediatric ophthalmology of the inpatient unit at the State Healthcare Institution of the Tula Region 'Regional Clinical Hospital No. 2' throughout 2021. From the entire cohort of patients at risk of developing retinopathy of prematurity (ROP) or already exhibiting this disease to a certain degree, a subgroup of 78 children diagnosed with ophthalmic pathologies was formed. For this group, the spectrum of identified diseases was studied in detail. The analysis included the most common visual impairments, such as refractive anomalies (including accelerated refractogenesis, hypermetropia, myopia, and astigmatism), binocular vision disorders, retinal angiopathy, optic nerve atrophy, glaucoma (including suspected cases), and ptosis.

Results of the study

Analysis of the collected data revealed ophthalmic disorders in 78 of the 238 examined children, representing 32.8% of the total sample. Among the children diagnosed with visual pathologies, male children constituted 55.1%, while female children accounted for 44.9%. Such close gender representation does not allow for establishing a direct correlation between sex and the development of visual impairments. It is important to note that an officially documented diagnosis of retinopathy of prematurity (ROP) was established in 15 children (19.2% of the total number of patients with pathologies). Among them, 7 children (47% of the group with ROP) were diagnosed with stage three of the disease, while stages one and two were observed with equal frequency – 26.7% each. The most common ophthalmic problem among the observed children was accelerated refractogenesis, documented in 60.3% of the patients. Next in frequency were other refractive anomalies: hypermetropia (19.2%), myopia (10.3%), and astigmatism (14.1%). Notably, among patients with myopia, a high degree of myopia predominated (50% of all myopia cases). In the group of children with astigmatism, the hypermetropic form predominated (81.8%). Besides refractive errors, patients were also diagnosed with binocular vision pathologies, including strabismus and amblyopia, which accounted for 14.1% of all identified conditions. Among other recorded pathologies were angiopathy (6.4%), partial optic nerve atrophy (5.1%), suspected glaucoma (2.6%), and ptosis (1.3%).

Conclusions

In a non-randomized prospective study, the condition of 238 premature infants was examined. Special attention was given to 15 infants who developed retinopathy of prematurity (ROP) in 2021 in the context of coronavirus infection. The analysis also included 63 premature infants from the ROP risk group who had ophthalmic pathology without a confirmed diagnosis of ROP. All these patients were followed up at the consultation and diagnostic office of the pediatric ophthalmology department of the State Healthcare Institution of the Tula Region 'Regional Clinical Hospital No.

2' in 2021. The collected data made it possible to conduct a detailed analysis of the structure of ophthalmic pathologies. The results of this analysis will form the basis for developing a predictive tool for the risk of refractive anomalies in adolescents who have experienced retinopathy of prematurity. Considering that, according to many researchers, myopia often manifests during school age, which explains its widespread prevalence among both children and adults, a significant increase in the number of individuals with myopia is predicted. It is estimated that by 2050, myopia will affect 5 billion people globally, with approximately half of the world's population experiencing this condition, and in Europe, this rate is expected to reach 56.2%.

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THE HISTORY OF MUSIC THERAPY

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Introduction

In modern medicine, there is a steady growth of interest in non-drug methods for restoring a person's psycho-emotional and physical well-being. One of the most promising and multidisciplinary approaches is music therapy – the clinically proven use of musical interventions for prevention, treatment, and rehabilitation [1].

The relevance of this area is due to the increase in psychosomatic disorders, stress, and the need for gentle, accessible methods of correcting the patient's condition.

Purpose of the study

Studying the history of the emergence and development of music therapy to form an understanding of its impact on the emotional and physical state of a person.

Materials and methods.

The work uses a set of qualitative analysis methods based on historical-comparative and retrospective approaches:

- a systematic review of scientific literature on the history and theory of music therapy;
- analysis of video materials demonstrating the practical application of methods;
- a critical assessment of the results of clinical trials conducted in Russia and abroad from the end of the 19th century to 2025.

Results and discussion. Music therapy is the targeted use of musical stimuli to achieve therapeutic effects – normalization of the emotional background, reduction of pain, improvement of cognitive functions, and regulation of autonomic processes [5]

The historical roots of music therapy reach deep into antiquity. In ancient medicine, even before the invention of musical instruments, healers used rhythmic sounds with rapidly changing dynamics. During treatment sessions, they would speed up and slow down the tempo of the sounds, which contributed to the development of involuntary reactions in the autonomic nervous system. After the invention of the first musical instruments, the forms of healing rituals diversified significantly, becoming similar to modern group music therapy sessions. In ancient China, the art of “pentatonics” was developed – a musical system of five tones that positively influences the nervous system. The five tones corresponded to five organs: the lungs, spleen, heart, liver, and kidneys. Ancient India had its own form of music therapy, “gandharvatherapy,” which altered the psychoemotional state and stabilized blood pressure. It was believed that special spiritual works, “ragas,” were the main approach to managing the human psyche, it was considered a powerful method of healing the body and soul, reducing anxiety and stabilizing the emotional background [2].

In Ancient Greece, music held a special place. Pythagoras laid the foundations of the theory of the mathematical nature of music and performed it for the sick. His musical works contributed to the purification of human emotions and subsequent recovery. Music as a medicine was also used by other scholars, such as Democritus and Homer, who confirmed the possibility of using music for pain relief. [2]

We owe the use of music therapy in Russia to I. M. Dogel (1830–1916), who was the first to study the effects of music on humans and animals, noting the influence of music on blood circulation, its dependence on volume, and the effect of music on muscle activity. I. M. Dogel’s experiments laid the foundations for Russian music therapy and inspired his contemporaries to conduct new research. In 1893, physiologist I. R. Tarkhanov published his work “On the Influence of Music on the Human Organism,” which described the impact of music on human physiological processes. According to experimental data, “It can powerfully influence one’s feelings and moods, and through this, the functions of various organs of the body and almost all aspects of one’s life.” I. R. Tarkhanov made a significant contribution to the dissemination of music therapy, confirming the potential for its development and application [3].

V. M. Bekhterev made a significant contribution to the development of music therapy. He noted the beneficial effects of music on a person’s psychoemotional state by reducing anxiety and stabilizing breathing and circulation. He established a psychophysiological laboratory where he conducted research on the effects of music on humans and animals. In the 1940s, music was used in the comprehensive treatment of patients in military hospitals. It was noted that music facilitated the rehabilitation of soldiers after injuries and increased their combat effectiveness by influencing consciousness on an emotional and cognitive level [2, 3].

In 1906, Dr. I. N. Spirto, a researcher in V. M. Bekhterev’s laboratory, published the results of research expanding on the experimental foundations of Dogel and Tarkhanov,

which provided scientific substantiation for the positive impact of music on the functional state of the circulatory system. His experiments laid the foundation for modern scientists' research into the use of music to train the body to withstand stress [3].

Research by scientists such as D. A. Petrov, S. V. Braitseva, and M. R. Artepyeva has proven that positive emotions evoked by listening to music cause changes in cerebral cortex activity. Modern research also examines the effects of music on the human endocrine system [2].

Furthermore, music therapy is a key component in the work of some rehabilitation centers for children with disabilities, facilitating their socialization and adaptation to the environment. Russian educator A. M. Borozdin empirically demonstrated the applicability of music therapy for the rehabilitation of children with developmental delays. In 1991, he opened a school for working with children with disabilities. In 2023, by decision of the Novosibirsk Region Department of Education, it was reorganized and renamed the Rehabilitation Center for Children and Adolescents with Disabilities [4].

At the same time, music activates relaxation processes, helping to reduce cortisol levels with subsequent normalization of hormonal levels, which is used as an effective means of combating pre-exam stress, as well as in the preparation of athletes [5].

In Russia, music therapy acquired official status in 2003.

Contemporary clinical data confirms the effectiveness of music therapy. In a study conducted at a clinical psychological clinic, patients underwent a single music therapy session followed by diagnostic assessment using the Luscher eight-color test. Positive results, manifested in reduced anxiety, improved mood, and emotional stability, were recorded in 70% of participants after the first session. Moreover, the most positive results were observed among adult patients. This study demonstrates the therapeutic value of music therapy in improving the quality of life of patients with mental disorders and borderline mental pathologies, as well as the need to develop differentiated programs for adults and children [6].

Conclusions. Music therapy has evolved from the empirical practices of ancient civilizations to a modern, evidence-based medical discipline. Its effectiveness is confirmed by both historical experience and the results of modern clinical and neurophysiological research. This method demonstrates significant potential for treating a wide range of psychosomatic disorders, combining high tolerability, minimal risk of side effects, and interdisciplinary applicability. Despite its recognition in scientific circles, music therapy, in need of improved methodological standards, is not a universally accepted method. A problem with music therapy in Russia is the almost complete absence of state educational institutions dedicated to training music therapy specialists. Disseminating knowledge about its potential will contribute to the development of a more humane model of medicine for the future, focused on the holistic well-being of the patient.

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**PREVENTION OF REPERFUSION COMPLICATIONS IN CASE
OF EXTENSIVE LESIONS OF THE AORTO-FEMORAL
AND FEMORO-POPLITEAL SEGMENTS**

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***Abstract.** Despite significant advances in modern vascular surgery, surgical treatment of patients with lesions of the aorta and arteries of the lower extremities remains an important medical and social problem up to the present time. In recent years, there has been an increase worldwide in the total number of vascular operations.*

Meanwhile, the outcomes of surgeries performed in patients with lesions of the aorto-femoral segment remain unsatisfactory, as evidenced by high mortality rates ranging from 1.9% to 9% (Spiridonov A. A. et al., 2005).

***Keywords:** Perforan, reperfusion complications, transcuteaneous oxygen tension, atherosclerotic lesions of the aorto-popliteal segments.*

One of the factors contributing to unfavorable surgical outcomes in aorto-femoral segment lesions is the development of reperfusion complications, which manifest as multi-organ dysfunction (Gavrilenko A. V., 2013).

However, the data in the literature regarding the incidence of these complications are limited in scope and often contradictory (Karpenko A. A. et al., 2013).

Fundamental studies by several specialists have demonstrated that the clinical manifestations of reperfusion injury to organs and tissues following abdominal

aortic surgery include cardiovascular, pulmonary, and renal insufficiency of varying severity (Shlyakhto E. V. et al., 2009).

Any open surgical intervention on the aorta involves its clamping and induces acute iatrogenic ischemia of the lower half of the body. Therefore, reperfusion complications are considered an anticipated and obligatory outcome of surgical interventions on the aorta; their development is associated with the primary procedural factor – the release of the aortic clamp and the resumption of blood flow to tissues that have endured a prolonged period of ischemia (Kazanchyan P. O. et al., 2008).

It is well known that the development of reperfusion complications is largely dependent on the initial condition of regional microcirculation, with tissue hypoxia being the key pathogenic factor (Ivanov K. P. 2014; Andreychuk K. A. et al., 2006).

One of the potential solutions to this problem is the use of perfluorochemical compounds, on the basis of which a plasma substitute preparation with gas-transport function – Perftoran – was developed. Perftoran can influence the main pathogenetic mechanism initiating the cascade of pathological reactions leading to reperfusion complications – tissue hypoxia (Volkov D. V. et al., 2013; Magomedov K. K., 2013).

Given that the issue of protecting the organs and tissues of the lower half of the body from ischemia during surgeries on the aorto-femoral segment remains unresolved, the further development of methods for anti-ischemic protection and the effective limitation of reperfusion injury to organs and tissues – which initiate a cascade of pathological processes leading to multiple organ damage – remains a pertinent area of research (Shcherbak N. S. et al., 2012; Zoloev G. K., 2012).

Research Objective

To improve the outcomes of surgical treatment of chronic atherosclerotic lesions of the aorto-femoral segment by preventing reperfusion complications through intravenous administration of Perftoran

Materials and Methods

This study was conducted in the vascular surgery department of the Kemerovo Regional Clinical Hospital, the clinical base of the Department of Faculty Surgery and Urology at Kemerovo State Medical Academy. The study included 49 patients who underwent surgical interventions on the aorto-femoral segment.

The comparison group consisted of 29 patients who received the standard protocol of preoperative preparation. The main group comprised 20 patients who received Perftoran according to our developed protocol for the prevention of reperfusion complications.

Inclusion criteria: presence of an infrarenal aortic aneurysm of type II or III according to the A. V. Pokrovsky classification, combined with chronic lower limb ischemia (CLLI) stage I–II A as per the A. V. Pokrovsky-Fontaine classification; stenotic-occlusive lesions of the aorto-femoral segment with bilateral

femoral artery occlusion accompanied by CLLI stage II B-IV according to the A. V. Pokrovsky-Fontaine classification. Arterial lesions of the lower half of the body according to the TASK II scale (2007) – Class D lesion.

Exclusion criteria: presence of chronic renal failure, cardiac arrhythmias.

Mean age of patients 65 ± 4 years. Men: 42 (85.7%), women: 7 (14.3%). Patients with infrarenal aortic aneurysm – 32 (65.3%); steno-occlusive lesions of the aorto-femoral segment with bilateral femoral artery occlusion – 17 (34.7%) patients.

The diagnostic workup of patients included: color duplex scanning of the abdominal aorta, visceral branches of the aorta, and arteries of the lower extremities, performed using the ACUSON 128/10 XP ultrasound scanner in color duplex scanning mode; aorto-arteriography of the lower extremities and multislice computed tomography with bolus contrast enhancement. The examination was performed on the digital X-ray system “RTS 612 Electron” equipped with an automatic syringe injector, operating in subtraction mode with intra-arterial contrast administration. The preferred method for assessing lesions of the aorta and lower limb arteries was computed tomography of the aorta with bolus contrast enhancement performed on the Tomoscan M/EG Philips (USA) CT scanner. All patients underwent examination by a cardiologist, nephrologist, and vascular surgeon.

To evaluate the stage of chronic kidney disease (CKD), the classification proposed by A. V. Pokrovskiy in 1976 was utilized.

Study results and discussion

Findings from transcutaneous oxygen tension monitoring

When measuring the TsRO₂ level before aortic clamping, no significant differences were found in TsRO₂ values between the main and comparison groups ($p = 0.068$). In the main group, the TsRO₂ value was 30.23 ± 2.85 mmHg, while in the comparison group it was 29.78 ± 3.01 mmHg. Upon application of the aortic clamp, TsRO₂ decreased to 12.65 ± 3.28 mmHg in the main group and to 7.23 ± 2.21 mmHg in the comparison group ($p = 0.042$). One hour after surgery, the TsRO₂ value in the main group was 34.52 ± 3.12 mmHg ($p = 0.036$), while in the comparison group it was 27.36 ± 3.85 mmHg ($p = 0.042$). The dynamics of TsRO₂ are presented in Figure 1.

Comparative analysis of blood gas composition parameters

No significant differences in arterial blood gas parameters were observed when comparing the comparison group and the main group. Comparison of venous blood pO₂ values between the main group and the control group revealed no differences at the stage before clamping ($p = 0.2205$). A significant difference was found during clamping ($p = 0.0441$) and after restoration of blood flow due to an increase in pO₂ in the main group ($p = 0.0046$).

Figure 1 – Dynamics of TsRO2 in the studied groups

Figure 2 – Dynamics of pO2 values

The dynamics of pCO2 values in the main group at the stages before aortic clamping ($p = 0.0454$) and during clamping ($p = 0.0011$) were significantly higher than those in the control group. And only after restoration of blood flow are the pCO2 values statistically indistinguishable ($p = 0.5314$).

Figure 3 – Dynamics of pCO₂ values

Venous blood pH values in both the main group and the comparison group do not differ at any stage of the operations. In the comparison group, the pH of both arterial and venous blood before clamping shifts toward moderate alkalosis due to respiratory hypercapnia (lung ventilation), with arterial blood pO₂–128.73 ± 12.40 mmHg. During clamping and after reperfusion, pH levels stabilize and decrease to normal values. It is worth noting the more stable values in the main group, which remain within physiological norms.±

Figure 4 – Dynamics of pH values

Comparative assessment of blood lactate levels

Differences in regional venous blood lactate levels before aortic clamping between the main group (2.36±0.18 mmol/L) and the comparison group (2.50±0.15 mmol/L) are minor, and the observed differences are not statistically significant (p =

0.065). Following aortic clamping, lactate levels in regional venous blood increased in both groups, reaching 2.53 ± 0.13 mmol/L in the main group and 4.26 ± 0.12 mmol/L in the comparison group. Differences in venous blood lactate levels between the main and comparison groups were statistically significant, as were differences across study stages within the comparison group ($p = 0.0114$). One minute after aortic declamping, a sharp increase in venous blood lactate was noted in both groups. At the reperfusion stage, a statistically significant increase in blood lactate was observed in both the main group and the comparison group, reaching 4.89 ± 0.12 mmol/L ($p = 0.042$) and 8.01 ± 0.22 mmol/L ($p = 0.031$), respectively (Figure 5).

Figure 5 – Dynamics of regional venous blood lactate

The comparison group exhibited a persistent increase in lactate during both the aortic clamping stage and the blood flow restoration stage. Stable lactate levels in the main group indicate stable metabolic activity of tissues distal to the aortic clamping level, attributable to preserved oxygenation. An increase in lactate levels in the control group indicates oxygen debt and progressive ischemia of the lower half of the body. An increase in lactate in the control group following aortic declamping and restoration of main blood flow suggests the washout of residual lactate from tissues and reflects significantly greater tissue ischemia at the time of occlusion.

CONCLUSION

1. The degree of tissue hypoxia in the lower half of the body during aortic clamping, in cases of insufficient collateral circulation, reaches critical levels ($TsRO_2$ less than 10 mm Hg), $p = 0.042$.

2. A method for preventing reperfusion complications during the surgical treatment of chronic atherosclerotic lesions of the aorto-femoral segment through pre-operative intravenous administration of Perfctoran, which helps prevent a critical

reduction in transcutaneous oxygen tension in the tissues of the lower half of the body during the aortic clamping stage, $p = 0.042$.

3. A single intravenous administration of Perftoran at a dose of 5 ml/kg of patient body weight during the preoperative preparation phase limits the incidence of reperfusion complications in the early postoperative period: the rates of cardiac, pulmonary, and renal complications decrease by 25.5%, 19.2%, and 6.9%, respectively, $p = 0.037$.

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**INDICATORS OF RESPIRATORY MECHANICS IN PATIENTS
WITH SEVERE COMMUNITY-ACQUIRED VIRAL-BACTERIAL
AND PNEUMOCYSTIS PNEUMONIA AGAINST
THE BACKGROUND OF SURFACTANT APPLICATION
AND THE LUNG RECRUITMENT MANEUVER TECHNIQUE
COMBINED WITH PRONE POSITIONING**

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Abstract. *The aim of our study was to investigate the dynamics of respiratory mechanics indicators in patients with severe community-acquired pneumonia receiving surfactant therapy combined with lung recruitment maneuvers and prone positioning.*

The study material comprised examination results from 69 patients with severe community-acquired viral-bacterial pneumonia and Pneumocystis pneumonia in the setting of HIV infection complicated by acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS). The article presents an optimized treatment protocol for improving outcomes in patients with severe community-acquired viral-bacterial pneumonia and Pneumocystis pneumonia associated with HIV infection and ARDS.

Conclusions. *Intensification of the treatment protocol for patients with severe community-acquired viral-bacterial pneumonia and Pneumocystis pneumonia in*

HIV infection with ARDS significantly reduced the incidence of multiple organ failure, septic shock, and other complications, and prevented fatal outcomes.

Keywords: *severe pneumonia, acute respiratory distress syndrome, respiratory mechanics, surfactant, lung recruitment maneuvers.*

Relevance

Timely diagnosis of severe community-acquired pneumonia (SCAP), particularly of viral-bacterial and Pneumocystis etiology, adequate treatment, and prevention of mortality from this pathology remain urgent challenges in pulmonology. It is important to note the increasing mortality rate (up to 35–45%) from complications of SCAP, viral-bacterial pneumonia, and Pneumocystis pneumonia (PCP). Studies have shown that optimization of patient management protocols for SCAP, combined with lung recruitment maneuvers, prone positioning, and glucocorticosteroid therapy, can significantly reduce mortality in these conditions (A. V. Vlasenko et al., 2008; 2012; 2021; V. F. Ushakov et al., 2015, among others). However, treatment approaches for SCAP of viral-bacterial and Pneumocystis etiology complicated by ARDS and multiple organ failure remain controversial, and respiratory mechanics parameters in such patients remain insufficiently studied.

Study Objective

To investigate respiratory mechanics indicators in patients with SCAP of viral-bacterial and Pneumocystis etiology receiving lung recruitment maneuvers combined with prone positioning.

Materials and Methods

The study included patients from the main group ($n = 23$) and control group ($n = 23$), aged 18–58 years, diagnosed with viral-bacterial pneumonia complicated by ARDS, multiple organ failure, and other conditions. All patients tested positive for influenza A (H1N1) virus, confirmed by PCR detection of viral RNA antigen in nasopharyngeal swabs or aspirates. Additionally, pneumococcal pneumonia was diagnosed in 7 and 5 patients, respectively, and staphylococcal pneumonia in 16 and 18 patients across the two groups.

A separate analysis was conducted on medical records of patients with severe Pneumocystis pneumonia (PCP) in the setting of HIV infection. The main subgroup comprised 15 patients with severe PCP and ARDS associated with HIV infection, mean age 32.6 ± 2.6 years. The second (control) subgroup included comparable patients ($n = 16$). The diagnosis of systemic lung injury (SLI)/ARDS was established according to criteria approved at the American-European Consensus Conference on ARDS in 1994. SCAP diagnosis followed criteria established by the Research Institute of Pulmonology of the Russian Federation.

Unlike the control group, patients in the main group received lung recruitment maneuvers combined with prone positioning, methylprednisolone (300 mg/day) or

hydrocortisone (300 mg), antioxidants, and immunomodulators. Mechanical ventilation was performed using a DRAGER “SAVINA-300” ventilator (Germany).

Lung injury severity was assessed using the J. Murray scale ($\text{PaO}_2/\text{FiO}_2$ – oxygenation index). Diagnostic criteria followed the “Berlin Definition of Acute Respiratory Distress Syndrome, 2012.” Patient condition severity was evaluated using the APACHE II scale.

Data systematization and calculations were performed using Microsoft Excel spreadsheet software; statistical analyses were conducted using Microsoft Statistica version 6.1. Significance of differences was assessed using the paired Student’s t-test.

Results and Discussion

The study findings revealed that baseline $\text{PaO}_2/\text{FiO}_2$ values (mmHg) were significantly below normal in both the main group (146.5) and control subgroup (148.0), with no significant intergroup differences, corresponding to Stage II acute respiratory failure.

During treatment – including infusion therapy, optimized respiratory support, antibacterial, and antiviral therapy – the condition of patients in the main group remained critically severe, with progression of severe hypoxemia, intoxication, and ARDS signs.

By the end of the first 24 hours, following hemodynamic stabilization, improvement in systolic-diastolic cardiac function, reduction of vasopressor doses, and endobronchial surfactant administration into each bronchus, the oxygenation index significantly increased ($p < 0.001$) to 250.0 (Table 1). Within 1–2 days of emergency therapy, the fraction of inspired oxygen (FiO_2) was reduced to 45–55%, and positive end-expiratory pressure (PEEP) decreased to 7–9 cm H_2O .

Under the optimized intensive care protocol, normalization of the $\text{PaO}_2/\text{FiO}_2$ ratio was observed: 317 mmHg at day 6 and 320 mmHg at day 12 ($p < 0.001$). This rapid and sustained positive effect, maintained throughout ICU stay, can be attributed to increased volume of functioning lung parenchyma due to recruitment of unstable alveoli into gas exchange, improved respiratory biomechanics, ventilation-perfusion relationships, and reduced hypoxemic pulmonary hypertension. In the main group, FiO_2 was reduced to 35–50% and PEEP to 7–9 cm H_2O within the first 24 hours of optimized therapy.

A different pattern was observed in the control subgroup (Table 1), where the $\text{PaO}_2/\text{FiO}_2$ ratio increased more gradually: to 170 mmHg by day 1, and to 231 and 265 mmHg by days 12 and 16, respectively.

Analysis revealed that patients in the main subgroup (unlike the control group) demonstrated more pronounced and rapid improvement in pulmonary biomechanical characteristics: a significant increase ($p < 0.001$) in lung compliance from 23.2 ± 1.3 to 32.6 ± 1.4 mL/cm H_2O within 24 hours (Table 1), with progressive improvement to 36.2 ± 1.6 mL/cm H_2O at day 6 ($p < 0.001$) and 48.3 ± 1.3 mL/

cm H₂O at day 16 ($p < 0.001$), accompanied by reductions in peak airway pressure from 35.0 ± 1.3 to 34.2 ± 2.1 ; 26.3 ± 1.9 ; and 16.3 ± 1.9 cm H₂O ($p < 0.001$), and mean airway pressure from 25.2 ± 1.5 to 22.3 ± 1.3 ; 18.2 ± 1.2 ; and 11.5 ± 1.3 cm H₂O ($p < 0.001$).

Table 1. Respiratory Biomechanics Indicators in Patients with Severe Pneumonia and ARDS During Treatment

Parameter	Baseline	After 24h	After 6 days	After 12 days	After 16 days
Minute Ventilation (L/min)	13.8 ± 0.9 / 14.2 ± 1.4	13.8 ± 1.0 / 14.2 ± 1.2	10.8 ± 1.1** / 13.0 ± 1.1***	10.4 ± 0.6** / 13.0 ± 0.8***	10.2 ± 0.8** / 12.0 ± 0.4**
Peak Airway Pressure (cm H ₂ O)	35.0 ± 1.3 / 34.6 ± 1.6	34.2 ± 2.1 / 34.8 ± 1.8	26.3 ± 1.9*** / 34.6 ± 1.4***	23.4 ± 1.8*** / 25.2 ± 1.8	16.3 ± 1.9*** / 26.3 ± 1.6***
Mean Airway Pressure (cm H ₂ O)	25.2 ± 1.5 / 24.6 ± 1.8	22.3 ± 1.3 / 23.2 ± 1.6	18.2 ± 1.2*** / 23.4 ± 1.8**	15.4 ± 1.1*** / 22.4 ± 0.8***	11.5 ± 1.3*** / 18.6 ± 0.7***
Static Compliance (mL/cm H ₂ O)	23.2 ± 1.3 / 25.4 ± 1.2	32.6 ± 1.4*** / 24.3 ± 1.2***	36.2 ± 1.6*** / 25.4 ± 1.5***	45.2 ± 1.2*** / 28.6 ± 1.1***	48.3 ± 1.3*** / 34.5 ± 1.4***
Lung Injury Score (J. Murray), points	3.4 / 3.4	3.3 / 3.4	3.0 / 3.4	1.4*** / 3.0*	1.2*** / 2.0*
PaO ₂ /FiO ₂ (mmHg)	146.5 (84.6;155.2) / 148 (131.8;160)	250 (224.7;260.2)*** / 170 (129.9;192.1)***	317 (260;340.6)*** / 231 (189;260)***	320 (244.7;390.0)*** / 265 (199.5;340.7)***	– / –

Note: Numerator = main group indicators; denominator = control group indicators; * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$; *** $p < 0.001$ for comparisons of baseline vs. 6, 12, 16 days (numerator), and for comparisons between main and control groups.

In contrast, patients in the control subgroup showed slower and less pronounced improvements in respiratory mechanics parameters. Lung compliance values in the main subgroup were significantly higher ($p < 0.05$ to $p < 0.001$) than in the control subgroup at treatment stages 2–5, while peak and mean airway pressures were significantly lower ($p < 0.001$) at stages 3–5. Additionally, the “lung injury score” decreased more substantially in the main group (2.8-fold reduction) compared to the control subgroup (1.7-fold reduction).

In patients of the main subgroup receiving comprehensive etiopathogenetic therapy including mechanical ventilation with prone positioning maneuvers, more rapid and pronounced improvements in pulmonary biomechanical parameters were observed: a significant increase ($p < 0.001$) in static lung compliance from 21.4 ± 2.1 to 30.5 ± 1.6 mL/cm H₂O within 24–72 hours, with further improvement to 35.5 ± 1.8 mL/cm H₂O at day 6 ($p < 0.05$) and 38.4 ± 2.1 mL/cm H₂O at day 10. Concurrently, against the background of reduced pulmonary infiltration and edema and recruitment of alveoli into gas exchange, significant reductions ($p < 0.001$) in peak and mean airway pressures were observed: from 36.2 ± 2.34 to 24.6 ± 2.2 and 24.3 ± 2.1 cm H₂O within 24–72 hours, decreasing further to 20.6 ± 1.8 and 11.6 ± 1.4 cm H₂O at day 6 ($p < 0.05$), and to 19.4 ± 1.6 and 11.2 ± 1.3 cm H₂O at day 10. Thus, elevated mean airway pressures were no longer required for adequate ventilation of recruited alveoli. Notably, the oxygenation index in the main subgroup increased to 264.9 (214; 316) mmHg within 24–72 hours and normalized to 323.3 (226; 388) mmHg by days 6–7. This rapid and sustained therapeutic effect, maintained throughout ICU stay, can be explained by increased functioning lung parenchyma volume due to recruitment of unstable alveoli, improved respiratory biomechanics, ventilation-perfusion matching, and reduced hypoxemic pulmonary hypertension.

In contrast, the control subgroup demonstrated slower and less pronounced improvements in respiratory mechanics. Static compliance increased significantly ($p < 0.05$) compared to baseline only at day 6 (from 22.6 ± 2.2 to 26.8 ± 1.6 mL/cm H₂O), with moderate further increases to 26.9 ± 2.1 and 28.2 ± 2.3 mL/cm H₂O at days 10 and 15, remaining significantly lower ($p < 0.001$) than values in the main subgroup at all time points. Peak and mean airway pressures in the control subgroup decreased more gradually, with significant changes observed only at days 10 and 15, and remained significantly higher ($p < 0.05$) than in the main subgroup throughout treatment.

In patients with SCAP complicated by ARDS and systemic lung injury, only comprehensive treatment incorporating lung recruitment maneuvers, prone positioning, adequate antibacterial therapy, antioxidants, and immunomodulators enabled accelerated resolution of ARDS and the infiltrative syndrome.

Reductions in peak and mean airway pressures, decreased intrapulmonary shunting, and increased oxygenation index (to ≥ 300) in the main group served as markers of pronounced therapeutic efficacy and criteria for resolution (cure) of SCAP with ARDS.

Conclusions

1. In patients with viral-bacterial PCP and SCAP complicated by ARDS, the use of lung-protective mechanical ventilation combined with lung recruitment maneuvers and prone positioning is associated with more rapid resolution of

ARDS and multiple organ failure, as well as improved respiratory biomechanics and gas exchange parameters.

2. When implementing an optimized management protocol for patients with viral-bacterial SCAP and ARDS, key markers of positive treatment response include improvements in respiratory mechanics parameters and the oxygenation index.

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THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF HEALTHCARE DIGITALIZATION

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Abstract: *The article is devoted to a comprehensive analysis of the process of healthcare digitalization as a key factor in the modernization of the modern medical system. The paper examines the theoretical and methodological foundations of digital transformation, based on a systematic approach and the principles of patient-centeredness, interoperability, and information security. Particular attention is paid to the analysis of the regulatory and legal framework of the Russian Federation governing the implementation of telemedicine technologies, electronic document management, and the protection of patients' personal data.*

Keywords: *healthcare digitalization, digital transformation, telemedicine, medical information systems, artificial intelligence, regulatory and legal regulation, information security, patient-centeredness.*

Healthcare digitalization is a comprehensive process of introducing modern information technologies and digital solutions into the system of medical services for the population. This phenomenon is characterized by the transformation of traditional approaches to organizing medical care through the use of electronic management systems, the automation of clinical processes, and the introduction of innovative methods of diagnosis and treatment [11]. The theoretical understanding of healthcare digitalization processes requires an interdisciplinary approach that combines the achievements of medical science, information technology, management disciplines, and legal regulation.

The conceptual basis of healthcare digitalization is a systematic approach to industry modernization, which involves the creation of a unified information space for all participants in the medical process. The digital transformation of healthcare encompasses all levels of medical care delivery – from primary care to high-tech

medical centers – ensuring the integration of various information systems and databases [15]. Modern theoretical concepts view digitalization not as a simple introduction of computer technologies, but as a fundamental restructuring of the organizational processes and working methods of medical institutions.

The legal foundation of healthcare digitalization in the Russian Federation consists of a system of federal laws regulating various aspects of the application of information technologies in the medical field. The basic regulatory act is the Federal Law «On the Fundamentals of Protecting the Health of Citizens in the Russian Federation,» which defines the principles of healthcare organization and establishes requirements for the information support of medical activities [2]. Of particular importance is the Federal Law «On Amendments to Certain Legislative Acts of the Russian Federation Regarding the Application of Information Technologies in the Field of Health Protection,» which created the legal basis for the development of telemedicine technologies and electronic document management in medical organizations [6].

The regulation of personal data protection in healthcare is carried out on the basis of the Federal Law «On Personal Data,» which establishes special requirements for the processing of medical information as a special category of personal data [4]. This regulatory act defines the principles of legality, fairness, and adequacy in the processing of patients' personal data, which is of critical importance for ensuring the confidentiality of medical information in the context of digitalization [9]. Additional requirements for information security are established by the Federal Law «On Information, Information Technologies, and the Protection of Information,» which regulates the creation and operation of personal data information systems [3].

The use of electronic signatures in medical documents is regulated by the Federal Law «On Electronic Signatures,» which ensures the legal validity of electronic medical documents and creates the foundation for paperless document management [1]. The organization of the provision of public services in electronic form in the healthcare sector is regulated by the relevant federal law, which defines the principles and procedures for providing medical services through digital platforms [5]. Experimental legal regimes in the field of digital innovation create opportunities for testing new technological solutions in healthcare within special legal conditions [7].

Theoretical models of healthcare digitalization are based on the concept of an integrated medical information system that unifies the various components of the industry's digital infrastructure. The central element of such a system is the unified state healthcare information system, which ensures interaction between medical organizations, healthcare management bodies, and patients [8]. This system represents a multi-level architecture encompassing federal, regional, and municipal levels of medical information management.

Sidorkin P. V. holds that the concept of patient-centeredness is of fundamental importance for the theoretical understanding of healthcare digitalization, implying the creation of digital services and platforms that are maximally convenient for citizens to use. Modern theoretical approaches view the patient not as a passive recipient of medical services, but as an active participant in the treatment process, having access to their own medical information and the ability to manage their data [20]. The implementation of this principle requires the creation of personal medical accounts, mobile applications, and other digital tools that ensure interaction between the patient and the medical organization.

The classification of digital technologies in healthcare includes several main categories, each addressing specific tasks of medical service delivery. Management information systems for medical organizations represent the basic level of digitalization, ensuring the automation of administrative processes, the maintenance of electronic medical documentation, and the management of institutional resources, as noted by Milomaev A. S. and Grankin A. N. [12]. Medical information systems address the tasks of clinical activities, including the maintenance of electronic medical records, support for medical decision-making, and integration with diagnostic equipment.

Tomchik N. V. indicates that telemedicine technologies form a separate category of digital solutions ensuring the remote provision of medical care and patient consultation. These technologies include video conferencing systems for conducting teleconsultations, remote health monitoring platforms, and mobile applications for physician-patient interaction [21]. A special place is occupied by technologies for the remote monitoring of vital signs, enabling continuous observation of patients' conditions at home, as noted by Mikheev A. A. [13].

In the work of Savina A. G., artificial intelligence and machine learning represent the most promising category of digital technologies in healthcare, ensuring the automation of complex intellectual processes in medical practice. The application of artificial intelligence algorithms encompasses tasks of medical diagnostics, disease progression forecasting, treatment personalization, and the optimization of medical organization operations [19]. The theoretical foundations of applying artificial intelligence in medicine are based on the principles of machine learning, big data processing, and the creation of expert systems to support medical decision-making.

A systematic approach to the implementation of digital solutions in healthcare involves a comprehensive examination of all aspects of the industry's digital transformation – technological, organizational, legal, and social. The technological aspect includes the selection of optimal digital platforms, ensuring their integration and scalability, the creation of reliable IT infrastructure and information security systems, as noted by Parshikova D. Yu. [17]. The organizational aspect encompasses issues of business process reengineering in medical organizations, training personnel to work with digital technologies, and changing organizational culture.

Korsun T. A. identifies the methodological basis of the systematic approach to healthcare digitalization as the concept of change management, which involves the planned transformation of traditional processes of medical care delivery. This approach requires the creation of detailed digital transformation plans, the identification of key performance indicators for the implementation of digital technologies, and the development of mechanisms for monitoring the achievement of set goals [10]. Special attention is paid to ensuring continuity of medical care during the transition to digital technologies.

The theoretical principles of healthcare digitalization include the principle of interoperability, which ensures the compatibility of various information systems and the ability to exchange data between them. This principle, according to Mokhnacheva T. E., is of great importance for creating a unified healthcare information space and ensuring the continuity of patient medical services [14]. The implementation of the interoperability principle requires the use of standardized data exchange protocols and unified reference guides and classifiers of medical information.

The principle of scalability implies the ability to expand digital healthcare systems as the volume of processed information grows and the number of users increases. Frangulyan A. D. notes that this principle is especially important in the context of developing federal and regional healthcare information systems, which must serve millions of patients and thousands of medical organizations [22]. The technical implementation of the scalability principle is based on the use of cloud technologies, microservice architecture, and modern load management methods.

In the work of Kaminer D. D., Milushkina O. Yu., and Shein N. I., the principle of information security is stated to constitute the fundamental basis of healthcare digitalization, given the particular importance of protecting patients' medical data. Ensuring information security requires a comprehensive approach encompassing technical, organizational, and legal protective measures [23]. Technical measures include data encryption, multi-factor authentication, intrusion detection systems, and regular data backups. Organizational measures involve the development of information security policies, training personnel in the fundamentals of information protection, and monitoring compliance with security requirements.

The economic aspects of the theory of healthcare digitalization are related to assessing the effectiveness of investments in digital technologies and determining optimal models for financing the industry's digital transformation. Novoselova A. P. bases the theoretical approaches to the economic justification of digitalization on an analysis of the total cost of ownership of digital systems, the calculation of return on investment indicators, and the assessment of the socioeconomic effects of implementing digital technologies [16]. Of particular importance is the analysis of the long-term effects of digitalization, including improvements in the quality of medical care, reductions in treatment costs, and improvements in the accessibility of medical services.

The social aspects of the theory of healthcare digitalization encompass issues of the influence of digital technologies on relations between participants in the medical process – physicians, patients, and the administration of medical organizations. Pyslary E. A. holds that digitalization is transforming traditional models of interaction in the healthcare system, creating new opportunities for communication and collaboration [18]. The theoretical understanding of the social consequences of digitalization includes an analysis of changes in the professional activities of medical workers, the transformation of the patient’s role in the treatment process, and the influence of digital technologies on the quality of medical services.

International experience in healthcare digitalization provides rich material for the theoretical analysis of various models and approaches to the digital transformation of the medical industry. A comparative analysis of national healthcare digitalization strategies makes it possible to identify common patterns and specific features of various approaches to modernizing medical systems [22]. The study of foreign experience facilitates the adaptation of best digitalization practices to the conditions of the Russian healthcare system and helps to avoid typical mistakes when implementing digital technologies.

Promising directions for the development of the theory of healthcare digitalization are related to the integration of new technological solutions, including blockchain, the Internet of Things, augmented reality, and quantum computing. These technologies open up new possibilities for improving medical services and require the development of corresponding theoretical approaches to their application in healthcare [24]. Special attention is paid to issues of the ethical regulation of the application of new technologies in medicine and ensuring equitable access to digital medical services for all categories of the population.

Thus, the analysis conducted has shown that healthcare digitalization is a multifaceted phenomenon requiring an interdisciplinary approach and a systematic understanding of the processes of transforming the medical industry.

The study of the legal foundations of healthcare digitalization has revealed the existence of a well-developed regulatory and legal framework governing various aspects of the application of information technologies in the medical field. Federal laws create the legal basis for the introduction of electronic document management, telemedicine technologies, the protection of patients’ personal data, and the organization of the provision of public services in electronic form. Of particular importance is the legal regulation of experimental legal regimes, which create opportunities for testing innovative digital solutions in healthcare.

Conceptual approaches to healthcare digitalization are based on the principles of systematicity, interoperability, scalability, and information security. Theoretical models of digital transformation in the medical industry involve the creation of a unified healthcare information space that ensures the integration of various levels

of medical care and participants in the medical process. The classification of digital technologies in healthcare includes management information systems, medical information systems, telemedicine technologies, and artificial intelligence-based solutions. A systematic approach to the implementation of digital solutions encompasses the technological, organizational, legal, and social aspects of healthcare digital transformation. The methodological foundation of the systematic approach is the concept of change management, which presupposes a planned transformation of traditional healthcare delivery processes, taking into account the principles of patient-centeredness and ensuring the quality of medical services. The economic and social aspects of the theory of healthcare digitalization are related to assessing the return on investment in digital technologies and analyzing the impact of digital transformation on the relationships between participants in the medical process.

Based on the foregoing, the theoretical foundations of healthcare digitalization form a scientific and methodological basis for the practical implementation of digital transformation of the medical system, providing a conceptual framework for the development and implementation of healthcare modernization strategies.

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MATERIALS SCIENCE ANALYSIS OF NEW GENERATION COMPOSITES USED IN THERAPEUTIC DENTISTRY

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Abstract. *The present study provides an analysis of the properties of modern composite materials used in therapeutic dentistry, as well as identifies the criteria applied by specialists in the selection of materials for dental restoration. The study conducted at the Department of Therapeutic Dentistry of Altai State Medical University (ASMU) aimed to establish the fundamental principles for selecting contemporary filling materials for tooth restoration. Statistically significant results of the clinician survey ($p < 0.05$) underscore the necessity of an adaptive approach to material selection that considers the individual characteristics of the clinical scenario. The obtained data highlight the current challenges and influencing factors in the field of modern restorative dentistry.*

Keywords: *Restoration, composite material, survey, insulating liner, adhesion.*

Introduction

In contemporary dental practice, improving the quality and durability of restorative materials remains a key priority. The development of new composite materials, the technologies for their application, and their compliance with modern requirements for aesthetics, biocompatibility, and mechanical strength necessitate continuous scientific and clinical analysis [5, 6]. Currently, the issue of optimally combining aesthetic and functional characteristics of restorations, along with

minimizing the risk of complications related to inappropriate materials, remains particularly important [3]. The study by L. T. Pulatova (2024) outlines the latest advancements in biocompatible materials, their properties, clinical applications, and future development perspectives. The author underscores the importance of appropriate selection from a broad spectrum of composite materials to ensure the safety and longevity of restorations, as well as to reduce potential adverse biological responses. Medical materials science is regarded as a distinct interdisciplinary field encompassing the study of materials, their quality control, and methods of application. Composite materials are of fundamental importance, combining mechanical strength with biocompatibility. The article provides a detailed description of biocompatibility criteria, encompassing the chemical, physical, and biological stability of materials, as well as compatibility with body tissues and the absence of allergic reactions. The focus is on the development of biocompatible composite materials based on hydroxyapatite compounds, resins, ceramics, and nanofillers that improve physical and aesthetic properties [1].

The article by Hassan B. S., Razumovskaya S. N., and Velichko E. V., published in 2020, addresses the pertinent issue of the adoption and clinical application of composite materials in dentistry, as well as the prospects for their development. The authors analyze modern approaches, properties, advantages, and disadvantages of various composite materials, allowing for conclusions regarding their role and prospects in dental practice. The article provides a detailed classification of composite materials based on filler types, including their sizes and concentrations. Conclusions are drawn concerning the key properties of restorative materials, such as mechanical strength, biocompatibility, shrinkage, adhesion to dental tissues, and aesthetic parameters (translucency, color stability), noting that these properties are continuously enhanced through the incorporation of nanotechnologies and novel components. The significance of the correct selection of composition and restoration technique for achieving optimal outcomes is also emphasized [7].

Alekseev V. V., Maksut N. B. In their article (2023), an analysis of key trends was conducted, enabling an understanding of the developmental trajectory of the entire restorative dentistry field at the current stage. Materials for restorations were examined for the anterior tooth region (with a focus on aesthetics), for the posterior region (with a focus on strength and wear resistance), for small cavities (flowable composite materials), and for deep cavities (Bulk-fill systems) [8].

The continuous advancement of restorative techniques and the expansion of clinical indications underscore the necessity for a systematic study and evaluation of modern materials to ensure the utmost efficacy and safety of dental restorations. Accordingly, the relevance of this topic is driven by the rapid progress in scientific research, the implementation of innovative technologies, and the imperative for ongoing professional development of specialists [1, 2, 4].

Objective: To analyze, based on survey data, the properties of modern composite materials used in therapeutic dentistry and to determine clinical preferences in their selection depending on defect localization.

Materials and Methods

For the analysis of the properties of modern composite materials, a questionnaire dedicated to materials science aspects of contemporary composite materials was developed at the Department of Therapeutic Dentistry of the Astrakhan State Medical University, within the framework of the Dental Clinic of the same institution. The study involved 115 dentists, of whom 60% had over ten years of clinical experience, as well as 70 fourth-year students, 65 fifth-year students, and 8 residents. Various statistical methods were applied for the processing of survey data depending on the type of random variables and the research objectives. To evaluate the type of distribution of variables, asymmetry and kurtosis indices characterizing the shape of the distribution curve were used. The Shapiro–Wilk test was employed to assess the distribution type of the variables. Normally distributed continuous variables are presented as $M \pm SD$, where M is the sample mean and SD is the standard deviation. In cases of a normal distribution, the paired Student's t -test was used to compare means. For distributions not conforming to a normal distribution, the nonparametric Wilcoxon signed-rank test (for related samples) was applied. Differences were considered statistically significant at $p < 0.05$, where p represents the probability of a type I error in testing the null hypothesis. When comparing multiple groups, the Bonferroni correction for multiple comparisons was applied.

Results

Analysis of the survey results identified several significant trends and challenges faced by practitioners:

1. Classification of Composite Materials: A Practical Approach

The analysis of responses demonstrated that respondents predominantly classify composite materials according to two principal criteria: polymerization method ($42.60 \pm 5.48\%$): chemical, light, or dual curing, and consistency ($36.83 \pm 7.25\%$): packable or flowable. This tendency indicates that in routine clinical practice, clinicians and students orient themselves toward practical aspects of material handling, such as ease of placement ($28.35 \pm 3.35\%$), modeling ($20.59 \pm 4.56\%$), and particularities of the curing process ($42.60 \pm 5.48\%$). These factors directly influence the effectiveness and speed of restorative procedures.

Significantly fewer respondents employed the classification according to filler particle size (microfills, macrofills, hybrids, nanohybrids) ($18.54 \pm 2.12\%$), which may indicate that for the majority of specialists, a detailed understanding of the material's microstructure is of lower priority than its direct clinical performance characteristics.

2. Selection of composites for the anterior teeth group.

In restorations of the anterior teeth group, the overwhelming majority of respondents preferred nanohybrid composites (68.54±2.12%). Compomers were selected significantly less frequently (14.92±6.71%). The most significant criterion for material selection in this area was identified as color stability (75.78±3.25%). Therefore, practicing clinicians and students intuitively or consciously select materials with the best aesthetic characteristics for the anterior tooth region, which represents a sound clinical strategy.

3. Restorations of the posterior teeth.

Nanohybrid composite materials have also been considered the 'gold standard' for restorations of the posterior teeth (45.68±3.18%), which is attributed to their successful combination of several key properties: high mechanical strength (56.46±4.25%) including compressive and flexural strength (36.12±2.25%), essential for withstanding elevated masticatory loads.

4. Primary challenges in performing restorations

Specialists most commonly encounter two interrelated challenges during restorative procedures: post-operative pain (55.49±2.34%), which may result from disruption of the marginal seal or from tissue stress within the tooth induced by polymerization shrinkage of the material; and compromised marginal adaptation (25.32±3.48%), which promotes the development of recurrent caries, marginal discoloration, and decreased longevity of the restoration. Both of these issues are typically attributable to polymerization shrinkage (45.32±5.63%) of the composite material and inadequate adhesion (35.89±4.56%). Understanding these causes allows clinicians to adopt a more informed approach in selecting materials and insertion techniques, as well as in adhering to adhesive preparation protocols.

5. Selection of an insulating liner in the treatment of initial pulpitis.

A separate section was devoted to the selection of an insulating liner in the treatment of initial pulpitis (pulp hyperemia). 33.54±5.72% of respondents stated that the mandatory use of an insulating liner with exclusively glass ionomer cement (GIC) is required, while 43.67±3.86% indicated that most respondents acknowledge the necessity of an insulating liner. However, there is a divergence of opinions concerning which specific material is preferable. Nearly one quarter of the respondents, 22.15±4.67%, do not use an insulating liner at all. This observation may indicate a lack of sufficient understanding of the biological foundations of treating initial pulpitis and the role of insulating materials in safeguarding the pulp from the toxic effects of monomers and thermal irritation.

6. Factors influencing the selection of restorative materials:

In public clinics, domestic materials (Dentlight) are more frequently used, accounting for 68.89±5.45%. In private clinics, foreign materials predominate at 89.90±2.23%, with Estelite Quick being the most popular at 47.56±1.26%.

The price factor is not decisive in material selection, comprising $14.34 \pm 1.15\%$. More significant are the personal experience of the clinician at $45.78 \pm 3.15\%$ and the marketing promotion of specific products at $30.23 \pm 2.18\%$.

Conclusion

An anonymous survey conducted among dentists, students, and residents of AGMU identified key challenges and preferences in contemporary restorative dentistry. The primary issues remain postoperative pain and compromised marginal adaptation, resulting from polymerization shrinkage and inadequate adhesion. There is a necessity to enhance awareness regarding the role of insulating liners in the management of initial pulpitis. The selection of restorative materials is determined not only by their physical and mechanical properties but also by the personal experience of the dentist and relevant marketing factors. Further research and educational programs should be focused on resolving the identified problems and enhancing the quality of dental care. In general, the study demonstrates that despite significant advances in dental materials, practicing dentists and future specialists encounter a number of pertinent challenges that necessitate a systematic approach for their resolution. Raising knowledge levels, improving practical skills, as well as focused work on the development and adoption of high-quality materials, both domestic and foreign, are key factors in ensuring high-quality dental care and patient satisfaction. Further research and implementation of advanced methodologies and materials, combined with active participation in educational programs, will help reduce identified problems and enhance the effectiveness of contemporary restorative dentistry.

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CLUSTERING OF COSMETOLOGICAL INTERVENTIONS AS A TOOL FOR IMPROVING THE EFFICIENCY OF INTERNAL QUALITY CONTROL AND SAFETY OF MEDICAL ACTIVITIES

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Introduction. *The growing popularity of invasive cosmetic procedures requires the introduction of reliable safety control mechanisms. However, in many clinics, internal quality control (IQC) remains fragmentary, and a differentiated approach to risk management is absent.*

Objective. *Based on the analysis of medical records, staff opinions, and patient opinions, to develop a classification of cosmetic procedures by degree of invasiveness and risk and to assess the possibility of its application for a differentiated approach to internal quality control and safety of medical activities.*

Materials and Methods. *A retrospective study from 2020–2025 based on a privately owned medical organization providing medical care in the “Cosmetology” profile. An analysis was conducted of 105,950 procedures, 40 staff questionnaires, and 150 patient questionnaires. A grouping of services with clustering by risk level (from K1 – high to K4 – minimal), complication analysis, audit of standard operating procedures (SOPs), medical records, and questionnaire results was performed.*

Results. *The proportion of high and increased risk procedures was 17.5% of the total volume, the overall frequency of registered complications for all procedures reached 4.24%. The most frequent adverse events were dissatisfaction with the result (36.32% of complications), allergic reactions (24.29%), infections and pigmentation disorders (15.09% each). The absence of SOPs for certain high-risk procedures was identified; in 60% of records, the parameters of device exposure were not recorded, in 40% – implant serial numbers, in 35% – informed consent was not signed. The questionnaire showed a low level of safety culture and time*

deficit among staff, as well as a high need of patients for improved information and post-procedural support.

Discussion. Systemic defects of IQC are associated with the lack of standardization, incomplete recording of complications, and insufficient attention to patient expectations. The proposed classification allows for targeted strengthening of control in high-risk areas.

Conclusion. A differentiated IQC model based on risk clustering can reduce the frequency of preventable complications and increase patient satisfaction.

Keywords: *cosmetological services, internal quality control, risk-based classification, standard operating procedures, patient safety, complications, informed consent.*

Introduction. In recent decades, the market for cosmetological services has shown steady growth, accompanied by an expansion of the range of invasive and hardware techniques. Injection techniques, laser interventions, thread lifting, and other procedures have become widely available, which increases the flow of patients and at the same time requires stricter control of the safety of interventions. According to the literature, the frequency of complications during cosmetological procedures varies from 0.5% to 15% depending on the type of procedure, but real rates may be underestimated due to the absence of unified registration systems. [1;2].

In the Russian Federation, the procedure for providing medical care in the “cosmetology” profile is regulated by Order No. 381n of the Ministry of Health and Social Development of Russia dated April 18, 2012, however, internal quality control and safety of medical activities (hereinafter – IQC) in most clinics remains fragmentary. The absence of a differentiated approach to risk management, low safety culture of medical personnel, and documentation defects are systemic problems requiring scientifically based solutions, since many organizations limit themselves to formal compliance with licensing requirements without implementing risk-based control mechanisms [3].

This study is devoted to a comprehensive analysis of the volume and structure of cosmetological services and assessment of the state of IQC, including assessment based on the opinions of staff and patients in a single medical organization providing cosmetology care in an outpatient setting.

Objective of the study: based on the analysis of medical records, staff opinions, and patient opinions, to develop a classification of cosmetological procedures by degree of invasiveness and risk and to assess the possibility of its application for a differentiated approach to internal quality control and safety of medical activities.

Materials and methods. The study was conducted in 2020–2025 on the basis of a privately owned medical organization providing medical care in the “Cosmetology” profile in an outpatient setting. A retrospective analysis of statistical data

on 105,950 procedures was carried out, the volume and structure of services were studied based on outpatient medical records, forms of informed voluntary consents, and logbooks. Services of initial consultation (cosmetologist's consultation) were excluded from the analysis, since they included only collection of complaints and treatment planning, which obviously could not have negative consequences. An expert assessment of the presence and content of standard operating procedures (SOPs) in the medical organization was performed.

An anonymous questionnaire survey was conducted of 40 medical workers (doctors, nurses, administrators) and 150 patients. The sample of respondents from among patients and medical personnel was carried out by the continuous method; the study included all persons who gave consent to the questionnaire and who were among the personnel of the medical organization (personnel group) or who sought medical care in the "Cosmetology" profile at the medical organization selected as the base for this study. The questions in the questionnaires for the patient and personnel groups clarified the same aspects concerning the provision of cosmetology care in the medical organization; minor differences in the questionnaires were due to the role of the respondent (personnel or patient). The questions concerned standardization, documentation, safety culture, information, and satisfaction. Statistical processing included calculation of mean scores on the Likert scale (1–5), correlation analysis (Pearson), and one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA).

Results. Based on the probable risk, clustering of all services was carried out into 4 categories: K1 (high risk) – injection technologies for volume modeling (fillers, botulinum toxin, mesothreads); K2 (increased risk) – biopsy, removal of neoplasms, laser resurfacing, photodynamic therapy, cryodestruction; K3 (standard risk) – subcutaneous and intradermal injections, peels, epilation, physiotherapeutic interventions; K4 (minimal risk) – dermatoscopy, confocal microscopy, topical application of agents, topical anesthesia, cryomassage. Then, based on the level of invasiveness and methodological approach, all services were divided into 9 groups (from non-invasive diagnostics to surgical and podological interventions). This model of service division allows taking into account not only the potential danger of the procedure, but also the specific technique of execution, which is important for the development of detailed standard operating procedures (SOPs) and algorithms for responding to complications.

The largest share in the structure of services was occupied by procedures of minimal and standard risk: K4–33.13%, K3–49.37% (total 82.5%). Procedures of increased (K2) and high (K1) risk accounted for 13.02% and 4.46%, respectively (total 17.5%). Thus, procedures with a potentially high level of danger constitute about one fifth of the total volume of services provided in the clinic, therefore focusing the IQC system on them seems logical.

The following 9 groups were also identified: 1 – non-invasive diagnostics (dermatoscopy, confocal microscopy); 2 – minimally invasive diagnostics (skin biopsy); 3 – injection correction methods (mesotherapy, fillers, botulinum toxin); 4 – superficial chemical and physical interventions (peels, cryomassage, topical applications); 5 – hardware physiotherapeutic and energy interventions (laser, epilation, UHF, photodynamic therapy); 6 – minor surgical interventions (removal of neoplasms, cryodestruction); 7 – specialized podological interventions (removal of the nail plate by laser); 8 – general and local cryotherapy methods (cryochamber); 9 – auxiliary procedures (anesthesia). Such detail made it possible to compare the frequency and structure of complications with specific technological stages and identify “critical control points” – for example, the need for strict adherence to asepsis in group 6 or mandatory photo documentation in group 3.

The total number of registered adverse events during the study period was 4.24% of all procedures. By severity, they were distributed as follows: mild (resolved within 48 hours) predominated – 65%, moderate (required correction) were less common – 30%, and severe (hospitalization or persistent changes) adverse events were most rare – 5%.

The structure of complications (as a percentage of the total number of complications) is represented by the following shares: dissatisfaction with the result – 36.32% (most often occurred after injection and surgical procedures (K1 and K2), which may be due to a mismatch between patient expectations and the achieved effect); allergic reactions – 24.29% (were often associated with anesthetics and bio-reinforcement drugs, and when analyzing the medical records, in several of these cases there was no marking about the tests performed); infectious complications (local) – 15.09% (were recorded mainly after minor surgical interventions, such as removal of neoplasms, biopsy) and pigmentation disorders – 15.09%. Slightly less common were vascular complications (4.72%) and scar changes (4.48%).

Internal audit of medical records and SOPs, which were approved in the clinic only for some services, had a multidirectional result. A positive aspect was the presence of SOPs for dermatoscopy, biopsy, laser epilation and superficial peels, however, a critical drawback was the complete absence of SOPs for the administration of hyaluronic acid-based fillers, intradermal contouring (mesothreads, biostimulators), laser skin resurfacing, photodynamic therapy, cryodestruction of neoplasms and removal of the nail plate by laser, that is, algorithms were absent for many high-risk procedures. At the same time, the analysis of the manipulations for which SOPs existed also revealed a number of systemic defects in implementation: for example, the analysis of protocols for botulinum toxin administration did not reveal a clear algorithm of actions for vascular complications (use of hyaluronidase), and for hardware procedures, the criteria for stopping exposure in case of a burn or pronounced vasodilation were not specified.

Slightly more than half of the cases (60% of medical records) of performing hardware procedures were not accompanied by subsequent recording of exposure parameters (wavelength, energy density, exposure time); in 40% of medical records, information about serial numbers of implanted materials (fillers, mesothreads) was absent; in 35%, the patient's signature on informed voluntary consent for injection methods was absent. Thus, maintaining medical records was not always correct and carried out in full.

Staff questionnaire (n=40, average work experience in the clinic was 4.2 years) showed the following key results: knowledge of the existence and compliance with approved protocols – mean score 2.7 (only 25% rated 4–5 points); self-assessment of documentation quality – mean score 2.4 (60% gave low scores of 1–2 points); internal audit and reporting on complications – mean score 1.8 (85% rated as unsatisfactory); safety culture (absence of fear of punishment when reporting errors) – mean score 2.2 (65% low ratings); equipment provision – mean score 4.1 (in this questionnaire, this is the highest rating).

The assessment of staff responses in the questionnaire forms established insufficiently high levels of legal and professional knowledge: 65% of employees could not indicate the current numbers of regulatory documents governing their work; 40% of medical personnel admitted that when performing new procedures they are guided by generally accepted clinical practice rather than by the regulations approved in the medical organization. The main reasons for violations cited by employees were time shortage (80%) and inconvenience of existing documentation forms (70%). A critically low result was shown by staff involvement in the IQC system: only 15% understood their role in it, the majority (70%) considered IQC to be exclusively the task of management.

During the patient questionnaire (n=150 people), the mean scores of responses were significantly lower for high and increased risk clusters compared to standard and minimal risk procedures ($p<0.05$). The lowest scores were given to: completeness of information received about the procedure – mean scores 2.8 for K1 and 3.0 for K2; feeling of safety – mean scores 3.0 for K1, 3.1 for K2; post-procedural attention – mean scores 2.5 for K1, 2.8 for K2.

Correlation analysis showed a strong positive relationship between the feeling of safety and the willingness to recommend the clinic ($r=0.82$, $p<0.01$). The second important identified correlation was more frequent dissatisfaction (mismatch between result and expectations) among patients in high-risk clusters (mean scores 3.2 for K2 and 3.0 for K1 versus 4.1 in K4).

Discussion. The conducted study allowed identifying a number of systemic problems of IQC in a medical organization providing medical care in the “Cosmetology” profile in an outpatient setting. The results obtained in the study show that the main “growth point” for IQC is improving information provision, patient

support at all stages of receiving a medical service, and achieving standardization of cosmetology care. The stratification of medical services proposed in this work has shown its effectiveness as a foundation for further assessment of various aspects of the IQC system. Such practice is actively used in providing medical care in other profiles and shows good results [4]. The proposed classification into 9 groups and 4 risk clusters allows a differentiated approach to the organization of IQC in medical organizations providing medical care in the “Cosmetology” profile. For minimal risk procedures (K4), standard control of SOP compliance is sufficient. For standard risk (K3), regular documentation audit is required. For increased (K2) and high (K1) risk, the implementation of enhanced measures is necessary: mandatory presence of detailed SOPs with algorithms for action in case of complications, photo documentation of stages, mandatory informed consent with an extended list of risks, and a post-procedural call center for 24–72 hours.

The staff questionnaire in this study showed the absence of a functioning system for recording and analyzing complications: 85% of employees do not have information about internal audit, and the reporting of adverse events is extremely low, which is likely due to fear of punishment because of a low safety culture. This situation is typical for many private medical organizations, where commercial efficiency is often a priority rather than quality [3;5].

The lack of standardization (absence of SOPs for high-risk procedures or violation of existing protocols) leads to variability in the performance of interventions and dependence of the execution technique on the subjective experience of the physician. This increases the risk of errors, especially in the event of non-standard situations or the development of complications. This is confirmed by the significant proportion of allergic reactions, infectious and scar complications identified in this study. Our data are consistent with the work of other authors indicating that the frequency of serious complications with injection techniques can reach 0.5–2%, and with laser techniques – up to 5–10% [1;2].

The third problem is documentation defects. The absence in 60% of records of hardware exposure parameters makes it impossible to reproduce the procedure and analyze the causes of complications. Failure to record serial numbers of implants (40%) violates the rules of traceability of medical devices. And the absence of signed informed consent (35%) creates legal risks for the clinic [3;5].

Finally, the significant proportion of patient dissatisfaction (36.32% of all complications) demonstrates that the medical aspect of safety is inextricably linked to the communicative aspect. Patients who received insufficient information about possible risks, rehabilitation periods, and probable alternatives are more likely to rate the outcome as negative, even if there were no objective medical complications [6]. The strong correlation between the feeling of safety and the willingness to recommend the clinic, as well as the more frequent dissatisfaction among patients

in high-risk clusters, opens another direction for differentiated implementation of IQC [6]. **Limitations of the study.** The work was carried out on the basis of a single medical organization, which limits the generalization of the conclusions. The frequency of complications (4.24%) is based on registered cases, but actual figures may be higher due to incomplete reporting. In this study, some services (consultative appointments) were not included in the analysis. Nevertheless, the obtained results appear practically significant for building a risk-based model of IQC in cosmetology.

Conclusion. Clustering and stratification of cosmetological services based on risk, level of invasiveness, and methodological approach allows for differentiated internal quality control and safety of medical activities in a medical organization providing medical care in the “Cosmetology” profile. The main systemic defects – insufficient patient information and their support by medical personnel at all stages of receiving medical care, defects in standardization and documentation, the system of complication analysis, and low safety culture – have a particularly negative impact when performing high and increased risk procedures, which requires a more detailed approach to their control. At the same time, patients pay sufficient attention to these aspects when assessing their satisfaction and willingness to recommend the clinic. Thus, the model proposed in this study allows for differentiated internal control, focusing resources on high-risk areas, which can significantly reduce the frequency of preventable complications and increase patient satisfaction. The results of the work can be used in improving the regulatory framework **and local acts of medical organizations providing cosmetology services.**

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EATING BEHAVIOR OF MEDICAL STUDENTS

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Introduction

Eating behavior is a complex, multi-component process that determines not only individual dietary preferences but also reflects personality traits, cultural background, and lifestyle. Daily eating decisions are influenced by a complex set of determinants: biological, psychological, social, and cultural [1]. Recent decades have seen a steady increase in scientific and clinical interest in the study of eating behavior, particularly in the context of eating disorders, which have a significant negative impact on physical health and quality of life. Eating disorders (EDs), such as anorexia nervosa, bulimia nervosa, and binge-eating disorder, are complex psychoemotional conditions that require a multidisciplinary approach to diagnosis and treatment. These disorders affect various age and social groups, often developing latently until they develop into pronounced clinical and psychopathological consequences.

The relevance of this study is driven by the annual increase in the number of individuals suffering from eating disorders, which negatively impact not only physical health but also psychoemotional status, interpersonal relationships, and overall adaptation. According to the WHO, eating disorders are becoming a global health problem, affecting millions of people worldwide [3]. In the context of constant media pressure and the idealization of certain body standards shaped by social media, many young people face difficulties in accepting their own bodies and developing sustainable healthy habits [5]. This contributes not only to the

development of clinical eating disorders but also to associated affective disorders (depression, anxiety). Understanding gender-specific factors in eating behavior allows for the development of preventive programs and personalized therapeutic strategies, and also promotes a culture of responsible health among students.

Objective: to study the features eating behavior of first-year students of the Federal State Budgetary Educational Institution of Higher Education Leningrad State Medical University named after St. Luke of the Ministry of Health of the Russian Federation and to identify gender differences.

Tasks:

- conduct a survey of first-year students of the Federal State Budgetary Educational Institution of Higher Education Leningrad State Medical University named after St. Luke of the Ministry of Health of Russia;
- to identify and statistically evaluate differences in eating behavior indicators between males and females;
- To develop scientifically based recommendations for the prevention of maladaptive eating strategies for students.

Materials and methods

The study was empirical and cross-sectional. The sample included 66 first-year students of the Federal State Budgetary Educational Institution of Higher Education, Leningrad State Medical University named after St. Luke, Ministry of Health of the Russian Federation (42 girls and 24 boys) aged 18–19 years ($M = 18.5 \pm 0.4$ years).

A validated version of the Dutch Eating Behavior Questionnaire (DEBQ) was used to assess eating behavior. Eating Behavior Questionnaire), which measures three key scales: emotional eating – the tendency to consume food in response to negative emotional states; external eating – reactivity to external food stimuli (sight, smell, availability of food); restrictive eating – cognitive control over food consumption for the purpose of weight regulation.

Statistical data processing was performed using SPSS v.26. Samples were described using mean values and standard deviations ($M \pm SD$). Since the distribution of the indicators was not normal, the nonparametric Mann-Whitney U-test was used to compare independent groups. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$. Effect size was calculated using Cohen's d .

Limitations of the study include the relatively small sample size, the use of self-report measures, and the cross-sectional design, which precludes establishing causal relationships. Longitudinal observation using a clinical sample and objective biochemical markers is warranted.

Results:

During the study, descriptive and comparative indicators were obtained for three eating behavior scales (Tables 1, 2).

Table No. 1. Descriptive indicators by scales

Scale	Women (n=42) M±SD	Men (n=24) M±SD	Difference	p-value
Emotional eating	2.31 ± 0.89	1.97 ± 0.76	+0.34	0.08
External power supply	2.89 ± 0.94	2.41 ± 0.82	+0.48	0.03
Restrictive nutrition	2.91 ± 1.02	2.26 ± 0.91	+0.65	0.01

Table 2. Gender differences in eating behavior indicators (N=66)

Scale	Women (n = 42)	Men (n=42)	U	p	d
Emotional eating	2.31 ± 0.89	1.97 ± 0.76	398	0.08	0.41
External power supply	2.89 ± 0.94	2.41 ± 0.82	352	0.03	0.55
Restrictive nutrition	2.91 ± 1.02	2.26 ± 0.91	318	0.01	0.68

For the emotional eating scale, differences between groups did not reach statistical significance ($p = 0.08$), but there was a trend toward higher values in girls ($d = 0.41$, medium effect size). For the external ($p = 0.03$) and restrictive ($p = 0.01$) eating behavior scales, significant gender differences were found: girls demonstrated statistically significantly higher scores compared to boys. The effect size for restrictive eating was estimated as medium-large ($d = 0.68$), indicating the practical significance of the identified difference.

Discussion

The findings are consistent with current understanding of gender-specific eating behavior. Higher scores on the restrictive eating scale among females ($p = 0.01$) reflect a tendency toward cognitive control over diet, which in student settings is often associated with the internalization of sociocultural standards of thinness and the use of diets as a strategy for managing body image [2]. Under conditions of high academic stress and time pressure, such practices can develop into rigid restrictive patterns that increase the risk of developing anorexia nervosa or orthorexia nervosa.

A statistically significant increase in external eating indicators among girls ($p = 0.03$) indicates a heightened reactivity to food stimuli. Combined with a tendency toward emotional eating ($p = 0.08$), this creates a vulnerability profile in which external triggers and negative affect can mutually reinforce each other, contributing to the development of compulsive overeating [4]. Boys, on the other hand, demonstrate a more balanced profile, which may be explained by their lesser involvement in dietary practices and different social expectations regarding body image.

From a clinical perspective, the identified patterns require specialist attention. Chronic dietary restriction in the absence of nutritional literacy leads to metabolic disorders, micronutrient deficiencies, and dysfunction of the hypothalamic-pituitary axis. Emotional overeating, in turn, is associated with an increased risk

of metabolic syndrome, gastrointestinal dysfunction, and comorbid anxiety and depressive symptoms [1].

Conclusions

1. The aim of the study was achieved: gender characteristics of eating behavior of first-year medical students were identified.

2. Girls demonstrated statistically significantly higher scores on the scales of external ($p = 0.03$) and restrictive ($p = 0.01$) eating behavior, as well as a tendency to more frequently use food as an emotional regulation strategy ($p = 0.08$).

3. The obtained data confirm the need for a gender-differentiated approach to the prevention of maladaptive eating strategies in the student environment.

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THE IMPORTANCE OF FALLOW LANDS AS A SOURCE OF BIOLOGICAL RESOURCES

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Abstract. *The relevant problem of post-agrogenic ecosystems is examined. Post-agrogenic ecosystems are systems with which humans coexisted and interacted as one of the stages of slash-and-burn farming in the taiga zone. This stage is characterized by specific biodiversity that has been utilized by humans over an extended period. The ecological significance of post-agrogenic lands as sources of biological resources is examined, including widely utilized timber species, medicinal plant raw materials and plant-derived substances, melliferous vegetation, and game animals.*

Keywords: *post-agrogenic ecosystems, fallow lands, biological resources, post-agrogenic succession, biodiversity*

Since the 1990s, large areas of abandoned agricultural lands have appeared, subsequently overgrowing with woody vegetation. According to the 2021 census, about 16% of agricultural lands in the Northwestern Federal District are identified as fallow land [1]. At present, lands overgrown with woody vegetation are regarded as an indicator of inefficient use of agricultural land.

Nevertheless, this phenomenon is by no means new. Human activity within the territory of Northwest Russia has a long-standing history covering several millennia [2]. Significant anthropogenic landscape changes emerged with the onset of slash-and-burn farming. The practice of this method of interaction with nature persisted until the early 20th century [3]. The agricultural cycle consisted of burning woody vegetation, a brief period of cultivating the burned plot for agricultural needs (3–5 years), followed by leaving it fallow with subsequent long-term (20–120 years) overgrowth by post-agrogenic woody vegetation dominated by species uncharacteristic of or rarely occurring in native ecosystems. According to modeling data [4], the slash-and-burn agricultural practice restores soil carbon significantly better than the fallow system and, during a prolonged (40–120 years) recovery phase involving

succession by woody vegetation, is comparable to a three-field crop rotation system with regular fertilizer application.

Lands previously cultivated with agricultural crops and now overgrown by woody vegetation were an integral part of the agricultural cycle under the slash-and-burn farming system. Thus, humans were in constant proximity not only to agricultural ecosystems but also to those that had ceased agricultural use and became overgrown with woody vegetation – post-agrogenic ecosystems. Being in continuous proximity to these ecosystems, humans regarded them not only as a stage in soil fertility restoration but also as an important source of resources. Human activity alters the species composition of ecosystems left behind following the completion of land use. Such ecosystems differ significantly in species composition from indigenous, undisturbed biogeocoenoses.

Therefore, post-agrogenic ecosystems constitute an equally important component of human activity in Northwest Russia as anthropogenic ecosystems.

Post-agrogenic ecosystems are primarily colonized by early successional, ruderal, segetal species, as well as species associated with pyrogenic successions. With the introduction of humans into the region's vegetation, alongside species directly related to agricultural activity (cultivated species: rye, wheat, etc.; weeds; ruderal species; and disturbance indicator species), the proportion of native woody plants capable of rapidly colonizing abandoned agricultural lands (birch, pine) increases, while the proportion of other principal forest-forming species (spruce, fir) decreases. The increase in the proportion of birch within forest stands has been associated with human activity over an extended period [5, 6, 7]. It has been established that the representation of birch in slash-and-burn agriculture systems is higher in soil layers exhibiting signs of agricultural use [8, 9, 10].

As one of the principal forest-forming species of post-agrogenic succession, birch has been utilized in numerous ways [11]: as a primary source of firewood and charcoal; its outer bark (birch bark) for various household items, clothing and footwear, and handicrafts. obtaining birch tar and sap, their use in traditional and contemporary medicine, as well as numerous other applications. Perhaps owing to such multifaceted utilization, birch features prominently in the folklore of many peoples [12]. Forests dominated by birch, as ecosystems, also represent sources of a range of valuable resources [13].

Synanthropic plants associated with post-agrogenic and anthropogenic ecosystems (including weed, ruderal, segetal, and pasture flora) are listed in the State Pharmacopoeia of the Russian Federation and constitute sources of medicinal plant raw materials and plant-derived substances, containing several valuable biologically active compounds [14]. A significant portion of plants currently used as medicinal are confined to habitats altered to varying degrees by humans (38 out of 94 species of herbaceous plants – wild species included in the current State Pharmacopoeia of

the Russian Federation – are species associated with anthropogenic ecosystems). The following factors may explain the diversity of medicinal plant species associated with anthropogenic habitats:

1) Post-agrogenic, anthropogenic habitats include representatives of native wild species, introductions from other regions, and escaped cultivated plants.

2) These ecosystems support species that are rare in the wild due to strong competitive pressure from ecosystem engineers (for example, *Potentilla erecta* commonly occurs near meadows and forest roads, in wheel ruts).

3) Plants with which humans have more frequently come into contact and that grow nearby have been more commonly used as medicinal plants.

In the taiga zone, post-agrogenic ecosystems, as well as other ecosystems formed following anthropogenic disturbances (logging, burnings, fallow lands, forest edges, etc.), constitute an important factor for the viability of beekeeping in Russia. This type of agricultural activity would be limited without anthropogenic transformations of taiga ecosystems. Natural taiga ecosystems without human activity possess a limited range of honey plants (willows, heather species, and aphid honeydew accumulations) [15]. Active human agricultural practices lead to the formation of post-anthropogenic ecosystems, in which a variety of valuable honey plants are widespread: narrow-leaved fireweed, raspberry, members of the Apiaceae, Rosaceae, and Asteraceae families. Our research has demonstrated that the highest nectar potential is characteristic of post-agrogenic ecosystems during the first 7–15 years of succession; following the colonization by woody vegetation, the honey-bearing potential declines [16]. Therefore, regular human activity in the taiga region, accompanied by the continual formation of new post-agrogenic ecosystems, constitutes a necessary condition for the advancement of beekeeping within this zone.

In terms of game management, the contribution of post-agrogenic ecosystems to the increase in populations of certain game species is also acknowledged by several researchers [17]. A high density of woody-shrub saplings leads to an increase in the populations of hazel grouse, white and grey ptarmigan, and moose. In certain areas of Northwest Russia, until the early 20th century, forest burning was practiced to increase moose populations.

Thus, human activity and culture were shaped not merely by the accommodating landscape, but by a landscape transformed by humans themselves to serve their needs. At the same time, ecosystems left after the completion of the agricultural cycle in slash-and-burn farming continued to serve as an important source of valuable properties and resources for humans. They remained utilized as a source of valuable plant species due to increased biodiversity, the appearance of species new to the locality, and the expansion of specific plant and animal species significant for economic activities.

These ecosystems were:

1. A source of important resources such as birch with the full diversity of its uses, medicinal plants, and the habitat of melliferous plants.

2. A method of restoring soil fertility.

3. As a method to increase biodiversity and enhance the population of several game species.

The potential use of post-agrogenic ecosystems as a source of biological resources should be viewed as a promising aspect of economic activity. It also inevitably raises the issue of conserving these ecosystems as a critical factor in natural resource management.

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RIGHT-SIDED MICROPHTHALMIA WITH MULTIPLE EYE ABNORMALITIES IN A SEVEN-YEAR-OLD CROSSBRED MARE

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Abstract. Microphthalmia is a rare congenital disorder arising from genetic abnormalities, the impact of teratogenic factors at various stages of fetal development, or injury during the embryonic and early post-embryonic periods. In horses, it is characterized by severe degeneration of ocular structures and blindness.

The objective of this work is to describe a clinical case of congenital right-sided microphthalmia in a crossbred mare.

The study material consists of a seven-year-old black-coated crossbred mare with right-sided microphthalmia.

The investigation included the collection of anamnesis of the disease and the animal's history, clinical and ophthalmological examinations, as well as ultrasound examination of the left eyeball and the right abnormal eye, and radiological examination of the skull in the direct projection.

Based on the results of clinical and ophthalmological examinations, it can be concluded that the abnormal eye is non-functional and has distinct morphology; its accessory apparatus is underdeveloped, yet it is innervated and fully operational, and is associated with a typical left eye. Right-sided blindness does not have a significant negative effect on the development and viability of the subject under study.

Ultrasound examination showed that the right abnormal eye is located atypically — deeply recessed within the orbital tissues, with an indiscernible shape. Due to low intraocular pressure, the contours of the abnormal eyeball are not visualized and cannot be evaluated. The cornea is visualized with low clarity, its shape mirrors the contour of the probe; the anterior chamber contains a lens with multiple

hyperechoic inclusions, and the iris is not visualized. The capsule is thickened; the vitreous body, containing hyperechoic inclusions, is visualized with low clarity; the retrobulbar region cannot be evaluated.

Radiological examination of the skull in the direct projection allows clear visualization of the asymmetry in the development of the facial bones and the orbital region, excluding previous trauma owing to the absence of bone calluses, sclerotic changes, and bone tissue lysis.

Conclusion: this study described a clinical case of congenital right-sided microphthalmia in a seven-year-old crossbred mare. Microphthalmia in this case cannot be associated with trauma of the facial skeleton and orbital region during the embryonic and early post-embryonic periods of the animal's life.

Keywords: *horse, veterinary ophthalmology, microphthalmia, teratogenesis, ultrasonography, radiological examination.*

Introduction

Congenital malformations are structural or functional abnormalities present at the birth of an animal. They are caused by factors of diverse etiology and occur at various stages of embryonic development [11].

A large number of congenital malformations have been reported in horses. Thus, for instance, in a retrospective study of congenital defects in horses, microphthalmia was observed in 4.6% of cases, craniofacial deformities in 4.3%, cleft palate in 4%, and hydrocephalus in 3% [7]. However, in this paper, we will focus on one of the congenital defects, microphthalmia.

Microphthalmia is a congenital developmental anomaly of the eye, characterized by a reduction in the size of one or both eyeballs. The abnormal eye may be small, and in rare cases fully developed and partially functional; however, in most instances, the eye is non-functional due to pronounced degeneration of its structures [6].

This pathology is also observed in other mammals, such as dogs [2] and sheep [4].

In horses specifically, the clinical manifestations of microphthalmia include a decrease in eyeball size with its abnormally deep positioning in the orbit, which can disrupt the normal anatomical proportions of the facial skull region and also result in asymmetry. Affected animals often present with epiphora related to impaired tear drainage or conjunctival irritation. In some cases, microphthalmia is accompanied by the formation of cysts and tumor-like masses in the orbital region, which may contribute to pain and inflammatory reactions [6,].

The three main causes of microphthalmia include mutations in specific genes [1, 7, 8], exposure to teratogenic factors during embryonic development stages [7, 10], and trauma to the orbital area and its structures [3].

It is rarely possible to definitively determine the etiological factor of the pathology in each specific clinical case.

The aim of this study is to describe a clinical case of congenital right-sided microphthalmia in a seven-year-old crossbred mare.

Among the numerous scientific publications and literature devoted to equine ophthalmology, only a critically low number of clinical cases of microphthalmia have been described. Moreover, the cases of microphthalmia in foals reported in the accessible literature do not document their subsequent life with the pathology, as such animals were subjected to euthanasia at an early age [5]. In this regard, one of our tasks is a detailed description of a clinical case of right-sided microphthalmia in a mare, living with this pathology from birth to the present. It is also necessary to assess the extent of damage to the ocular structures, the possibility of visual function, to note the impact of the pathology on the animal's life, and to propose a hypothesis regarding the cause of microphthalmia in the presented clinical case.

The study material consisted of a seven-year-old crossbred mare with right eye microphthalmia of bay coat color, possessing a “star”-shaped marking on the frontal region and two markings encompassing the entire area of the fetlock and hoof joints, extending proximally to the midpoint of the metatarsus on both pelvic limbs, as well as her sire and dam.

The sire is a seven-year-old stallion of Karachay purebred breed with a black coat, exhibiting no evident conformation faults or other pathologies.

The dam is a dun-colored Akhal-Teke purebred mare demonstrating slight asymmetry in the size of the eyeballs (the right being slightly larger than the left), as well as a weakened tendinous-ligamentous apparatus of the hock and fetlock joints, resulting in significant postural defects of the pelvic limbs. Pregnancy occurred for the first time at 16 years of age after several unsuccessful insemination attempts. During gestation, the mare did not receive supportive nutrition, vitamin-mineral supplements, nor was she subjected to necessary examinations and regular monitoring. Parturition took place under human supervision in a secure setting, thereby excluding fetal trauma as a potential cause of microphthalmia. It is noteworthy that a postpartum complication occurred – retention of the placenta lasting 18 hours.

At the time of the foal's birth, its skull was markedly deformed on the right side in the region of the zygomatic and lacrimal bones, the orbital process of the frontal bone, and the frontal process of the maxilla. The soft tissues of the nose, the upper lip, and the right nostril were elevated aborally and slightly shortened. The right eye exhibited no mucous or bloody discharge, swelling, or fullness; it was represented by a fissure with smooth, leathery edges formed by the upper and lower eyelids, along which there was an irregular row of eyelashes of varying lengths. Palpation of the closed eyelids caused indentation of the eyelids toward the internal structures proportional to the applied pressure. Upon eyelid separation, a pale amorphous dense mass covered with healthy mucous membrane was visualized.

Fig. 1. Frontal region of the mare at six months of age. A marked asymmetry between the left and right orbital regions is evident. The arrow indicates secretions from the abnormal eye.

The overall condition of the foal was assessed as satisfactory. He was in poor condition, weighing about 25 kilograms despite the mare foaling on time, which was two weeks beyond the expected term. The foal was weak and unable to stand three hours after birth. The forelimbs and hindlimbs were severely deformed due to marked weakness of the tendon-ligamentous apparatus, observable until six months of age.

Development proceeded harmoniously within a group of other horses, without veterinary examination or observation, as well as without support from special feeding, vitamin-mineral supplements, or targeted exercise.

As the mare reached the age of seven, she demonstrated increased activity levels and heightened interest in various surrounding objects, including some familiar ones. Distinguished by heightened excitability of the nervous system, with predominance of excitatory responses over inhibitory responses. Exhibits acute reactions to auditory, tactile (particularly on the right side), visual, and olfactory stimuli. The examined animal predominantly utilizes the left side during its activities and is characterized by agility and briskness. Demonstrates excellent spatial orientation; in rare instances, the right side of the head or body may collide with physical obstacles.

Over the course of seven years, periodic inflammations of the mucous membrane within the right palpebral fissure, increased lachrimation, frequent conjunctivitis, and formation of pale-yellow exudate causing itching and discomfort to the animal were observed.

The investigative methods included analysis and data collection regarding microphthalmia in horses, clinical and ophthalmological examinations, ultrasound examination of the left eyeball and the right abnormal eyeball using a Mindray Z-60 device (China), radiological examination of the skull using an EcoRay Orange 1060 X-ray apparatus (South Korea) with a flat-panel detector by PZ Medical (China), as well as a detailed morphological description of right-sided microphthalmia in a crossbred mare and the anamnesis of her life.

Study results. Following the general clinical examination, the animal's condition was satisfactory. Body condition score was six, with harmonious conformation; slight hypertrophy of the brachiocephalic and rhomboid muscles of the neck on the left side and hypotrophy of the corresponding muscles on the right side were observed. Asymmetry and deformation of the skull on the right side became more pronounced with age, accompanied by enlargement of the frontal, nasal, and maxillary bones. The right eye exhibits excessive lacrimation.

Fig. 2. The abnormal right eye of the mare at seven years of age. There is a noticeable reduction of the bony landmarks of the orbit, deformation and hypoplasia of the upper and lower eyelids, as well as mild inflammation of the mucous membranes within the palpebral fissure. The rudimentary cornea fused with the iris is visible, the third eyelid occupying more than half of the palpebral fissure, as well as crusts formed from exuding exudate in the area of the medial canthus.

Sensory function is maintained throughout the orbital region, including the upper and lower eyelids, both externally and on the mucosa-covered internal surface. The lower and upper right eyelids are functional and are synchronously involved in blinking together with the left eyelids. Upon excessive opening of the left eyelids due to fright, synchronous movement is also observed: the right palpebral fissure widens, revealing amorphous formations located in the area normally occupied by the eyeball.

Fig. 3. Frontal region of the mare at seven years of age. Abnormal dimensions and shapes of the facial skeletal projections are evident: zygomatic, lacrimal, and portions of the maxillary bones.

During the ophthalmological examination, the mare demonstrated a negative menace response and absence of reaction to exposure of bright light to the right eye. Exposure of bright light to the left eye elicited pupillary constriction and an avoidance response from the animal. A test with a bandage covering the healthy left eye demonstrated the animal's inability to navigate an obstacle course consisting of a series of plastic cones, exacerbated its response to auditory and tactile stimuli, and induced marked distress, which may indicate complete absence of visual function in the right eye.

Ultrasound examination of the left eye revealed good visualization of its structures. The contours of the globe are smooth, its positioning is normal, and the shape is round. The cornea is distinctly visualized, with a rounded shape; the anterior chamber of the eye shows no alterations; the iris is unchanged; the lens is in a typical

position; hyperechogenic inclusions are absent; the vitreous body is completely echolucent; the retina has a typical shape, is not thickened, and shows no signs of detachment; the retrobulbar space is unchanged.

Ultrasound examination of the abnormal right eye is characterized by poor visualization due to decreased intraocular pressure. The contours of the eyeball cannot be assessed, the location is abnormal – deeply embedded in the orbital tissue, and the shape is undefined.

The cornea is visualized with low clarity, its shape mirrors the contour of the probe; the anterior chamber contains a lens with multiple hyperechoic inclusions, and the iris is not visualized. The capsule is thickened; the vitreous body, containing hyperechoic inclusions, is visualized with low clarity; the retrobulbar region cannot be evaluated.

Fig. 4. Ultrasound examination of the left (L.) and right (R.) eyeballs. All structures of the left eyeball are clearly visualized and are typically positioned.

Contours of the right eyeball cannot be assessed; the red arrow indicates a hyperechoic posterior capsule, in front of which, in the area of the presumed anterior chamber, there is opaque lens substance with multiple hyperechoic inclusions.

A radiological examination of the skull was performed. The skull radiograph in the direct projection clearly visualizes asymmetrical development of the facial skull bones. The structure of the right and left maxillary sinuses differs somewhat: the septum of the right maxillary sinus is considerably less developed than that of the left. The volume of the right sinus is slightly smaller than that of the left. The orbital process of the right zygomatic bone is absent. It should be noted that these asymmetries are difficult to unequivocally associate with microphthalmia of the animal's right eye, since, for example, the maxillary sinus septum can be underdeveloped or entirely absent as an individual characteristic of the animal [9].

The bone contours are smooth and well-defined. On the bones of the right half of the facial part of the skull, in the orbital region and throughout the facial area, there are no osseous calluses, sclerotic changes, bone tissue lysis, or other signs of previous bone trauma, which allows us to conclude that trauma sustained by the animal during intrauterine development, parturition, or the first hours of life cannot be considered the cause of microphthalmia in this case.

Fig. 5. Skull radiograph in anteroposterior projection. A slight asymmetry between the right and left sides is observed.

Conclusion

In the present work, we described a clinical case of right-sided microphthalmia in a seven-year-old crossbred mare.

Based on the anamnesis of the pathology and life history of the examined animal, clinical and ophthalmological examinations, ultrasound examination of the left eyeball and the right abnormal eye, as well as radiographic examination of the skull in anteroposterior projection, it can be concluded that the mare is blind in one eye but has adapted to the typical lifestyle of its species. The conducted studies allow us to exclude trauma to the bones of the orbital region of the facial part of the skull as the cause of right-sided microphthalmia in this clinical case.

Discussion

We consider it necessary to perform additional investigations of the genetic material of the examined mare in order to determine the exact cause of microphthalmia, as this pathology most likely arose due to mutations in the genetic material of the germ cells of the dam or sire, as well as during the early stages of embryogenesis of the examined animal. Mutagenesis, in turn, may have been induced by exposure to teratogenic factors affecting the pregnant mare, or it may have occurred spontaneously. The search for the true genetic cause of microphthalmia in this case constitutes the objective of our future research.

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EVALUATION OF THE PROPERTIES OF SPONTANEOUS FERMENTATION STARTERS BASED ON WHOLE GRAIN FLOUR

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Abstract: *The study investigated the organoleptic and physicochemical properties of two samples of spontaneous fermentation starters prepared using whole wheat and rye flour. The rye starter was characterized by a higher dry matter content, greater active acidity, and a more active fermentative microflora, as well as a more pronounced sour-milk flavor. Both types of starters may be considered promising semi-finished products for the production of bakery goods with diverse sensory profiles and enhanced nutritional value.*

Keywords: *whole grain flour; spontaneous fermentation, starter culture, properties, nutritional value.*

In recent decades, the global baking industry has been actively developing products with enhanced biological value [1]. Due to changes in lifestyle and the increasing prevalence of nutrition-related diseases, particular attention has been paid to foods rich in dietary fiber, vitamins, and minerals [2]. One of the approaches to improving bread quality, including its nutritional value, is the use of starters based on whole grain flour.

Spontaneous fermentation starters are semi-finished products in which fermentation occurs due to natural microflora. Such a process ensures the formation of a complex of flavor and aroma compounds, improves digestibility, and increases the nutritional value of bread [3]. When whole grain flour is used, this effect is enhanced due to the preservation of grain bran layers containing biologically active substances.

Whole wheat and rye flours differ in their chemical composition. Wheat flour contains higher amounts of proteins and carbohydrates, whereas rye flour is richer in pentosans, minerals, and specific aromatic compounds. These differences are reflected in the characteristics of the starters and final bakery products, making this research topic relevant for the further development of baking technologies [4].

According to a number of studies, whole grain flour positively affects bread quality due to its increased content of dietary fiber and B vitamins [5]. However, such products are characterized by a darker color and distinctive aroma, which may limit consumer acceptance [4].

Lactic acid bacteria and yeast naturally present in whole grain flour actively develop under spontaneous fermentation conditions, producing organic acids and volatile compounds. This process ensures not only dough leavening but also improvement of the sensory properties of bakery products. Scientific literature indicates that the use of rye flour promotes the accumulation of larger amounts of acids, giving bread its characteristic sour taste and dense texture [6]. Whole wheat flour, in contrast, contributes to a milder flavor and a more porous crumb structure.

The aim of the study was to perform a comparative evaluation of the properties of spontaneous fermentation starters produced from different types of flour. The objects of the study were two samples of spontaneous fermentation starters prepared using whole grain flour: Sample № 1 – a wheat-rye starter, and Sample № 2 – a rye starter.

Numerous spontaneous fermentation starters described by various authors were analyzed [3]. The analysis of existing approaches to starter cultivation made it possible to summarize and systematize the accumulated experience. Based on the obtained data, stages for the cultivation of wheat-rye and rye starters were proposed, taking into account the peculiarities of microflora development, fermentation conditions, and component ratios, thereby ensuring process stability and the production of starters with the required technological properties (Figures 1 and 2). The semi-finished products were evaluated for moisture content, active acidity, leavening power, and organoleptic characteristics (during the stage of stable starter renewal).

The organoleptic analysis demonstrated that Sample № 1 possessed a mild sour-milk flavor, whereas Sample № 2 was characterized by a more pronounced sour-milk taste and richer aroma. In terms of color and consistency, the wheat-rye semi-finished product had a beige color and a homogeneous, moderately viscous structure, while the rye sample exhibited a brown color and a denser, more viscous consistency. These differences are associated with the baking properties of the flour and the chemical composition of the raw materials.

The analysis of physicochemical indicators of the studied starters showed that the temperature values ranged from 26 to 28 °C (Table 1).

Figure 1 – Stages of wheat-rye starter cultivation and its renewal

Figure 2 – Stages of Rye Starter Cultivation and Its Renewal

Sample № 2 was characterized by a higher dry matter content. The difference in active acidity between the samples was 0.17 pH units, which can be explained by the chemical composition of the flour used and the peculiarities of the stepwise starter cultivation process, characterized by different fermentation durations. The leavening power value of Sample № 2 was 2 minutes lower than that of Sample № 1, reflecting differences in the activity of the fermentative microflora.

Table 1 – Physicochemical quality indicators of the starters

Indicator	Starter samples	
	№ 1	№ 2
Starter temperature, °C	27±1,0	27±1,0
Starter moisture content, %	54,5±0,5	51,0±0,5
Active acidity, pH units	4,05±0,04	4,22±0,04
Leavening power, min	16,0±1,0	14,0±1,0

Thus, the studied semi-finished products demonstrate significant advantages due to the use of whole grain flour in their production technology. This approach ensures a high level of nutritional value owing to the increased content of dietary fiber, vitamins, and minerals characteristic of whole grain flours. In addition, these starters may be used in bakery production for the manufacture of functional food products with improved quality.

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CONSTRUCTIVE SOLUTIONS FOR URBAN TUNNELS IN DIFFICULT ENGINEERING AND GEOLOGICAL CONDITION

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The article is devoted to the study of the active development of the transport infrastructure of the coastal zone and the need to overcome the difficult terrain in the cramped conditions of urban development. Coastal zones are often characterized by high seismic activity (up to 8–9 points), intense monsoon moisture, the presence of tectonic fault zones and deep seasonal freezing, which requires the use of unique design and technological solutions.

Keywords: *Urban tunnels, difficult engineering and geological conditions, new Austrian Tunneling Method (NATM), Coastal zone, Khabarovsk, Seismic activity, Groundwater level, Waterproofing, Traffic capacity, Transport infrastructure, Deformation calculations, GTS NX, Frost heaving, Environmental and economic efficiency*

Introduction

The construction of urban tunnels in coastal areas is characterized by difficult engineering and geological conditions. Designers and builders are faced with various types of ground conditions, high seismicity, significant groundwater levels and a specific climate, which necessitates the development and application of non-standard engineering solutions. In light of the rapid growth of cities and the

urgent need to modernize transport infrastructure, the issues of tunnel design and construction in this region are of paramount importance.

Determining the site for the construction of an urban tunnel

As an initial task, in order to determine the location of an urban tunnel in difficult engineering and geological conditions of urban development, a condition is necessary that allows for an increase in capacity, while there are no alternative options. In this article, we will explore the possibility of simplifying traffic by building a tunnel on one of the busiest streets in Khabarovsk, namely Karl Max Street. Karl Marx Street is one of the busiest in the city, suffering from daily traffic jams. The reasons for this are: an increase in the number of cars, insufficient capacity, an abundance of intersections with traffic lights, lack of alternative routes and chaotic parking. All this leads to long-term congestion, environmental degradation, reduced safety and economic losses.

The solution to the problem may be the construction of a tunnel under the street. This will make it possible to divide traffic flows by sending transit traffic underground, and significantly increase capacity. As a result, the environmental situation will improve, noise levels will decrease, and the freed-up surface space can be used for pedestrians and public transport. The New Austrian method (NATM) is optimally suited for tunnel construction. This state-of-the-art technology minimizes excavation, speeds up the process, reduces costs, ensures high safety and reliability, and adapts to various geological conditions. Thus, the use of NATM for the construction of the tunnel on Karl Marx Street is an effective, cost-effective and modern solution that will make the urban environment more comfortable and functional.

Soil characteristics and geological features of the territory of Khabarovsk Karl Marx Street: – soil type: loamy and clay soils predominate in the city, including on Karl Marx Street. Their humidity and density vary.

These soils are subject to frost heaving (an increase in volume during freezing) and may lose their bearing capacity with excessive moisture;

– freezing depth: In Khabarovsk, there is a significant depth of freezing of the soil, reaching 2–2.5 meters. This circumstance requires a careful approach when designing underground structures in order to prevent structural deformations caused by the forces of frost;

– Groundwater level: Depending on the specific site, the groundwater level may be high. This increases the risk of flooding and necessitates the use of reliable waterproofing for tunnels and foundations;

– anthropogenic impact:

Active urban development and the operation of highways lead to changes in the natural properties of soils, making them more susceptible to deformation and subsidence.

In Khabarovsk, there is an increase in man-made geological processes, especially in areas with a disturbed natural geological environment;

- slope and erosion processes: in some areas, there is a risk of landslides and erosion, especially with the destruction of vegetation and inefficient drainage system;
- seismic activity: Khabarovsk is located in a zone with moderate seismic activity. When designing underground structures, it is necessary to take into account the possibility of earthquakes.

Figures 1 and 2 below show the engineering and geological conditions of the tunnel site.

Fig. 1. Engineering and geological composition of the site under consideration.

Fig. 2. Dangerous geological conditions of the site under consideration.

Key requirements for construction:

- it is necessary to provide for the strengthening of soils and ensure effective waterproofing;
- the depth of freezing and potential heaving phenomena should be taken into account.;
- It is recommended to use technologies that minimize the impact on the existing infrastructure and prevent the activation of dangerous geological processes.

For example, the New Austrian method allows for flexible adaptation to changing geological conditions during the construction process. The engineering and geological conditions on Karl Marx Street in Khabarovsk are characterized by the presence of difficult soils, significant depth of penetration and high sensitivity to anthropogenic factors. Tunnel construction in such conditions requires an individual approach that takes into account all these aspects. The use of the New Austrian construction method will ensure the safety and durability of the structure under construction.

One of the main advantages of the Austrian tunnel construction method is its exceptional adaptability to diverse geological conditions. For example, when encountering unstable soils or high groundwater levels, the technology allows you to quickly make adjustments directly during the work process. The design of the tunnel structure is carried out in stages, which gives engineers the opportunity to choose the most effective solutions to strengthen the rock and prevent collapses. This approach guarantees high reliability of the structure even in the most difficult conditions.

The Austrian method is characterized by a small amount of excavation and minimal interference with existing urban development. Compact equipment is used, and production sites are located outside residential areas, which reduces the risk of damage to existing buildings and structures. The most important element of the technology is continuous monitoring of the stress-strain state of the surrounding rocks. If deviations from the calculated parameters are detected, the design is promptly corrected, which helps to prevent potential accidents. Compared to traditional methods such as drilling and blasting, the Austrian method allows tunnels to be built faster and more economically. Since the work processes are executed sequentially, there is no need to wait for the complete completion of some stages before starting others. This significantly reduces the construction time and accelerates the commissioning of facilities. The Moscow metro stations, built in record time, are an example of the successful application of NATM. Reducing the construction time of new stations has a positive effect on the project budget and meeting the needs of city residents.

Although the cost of construction depends on many factors, NATM allows you to minimize costs in several ways:

- Logistics optimization: there is no need for large-scale transportation operations, as materials are delivered in small batches as needed;
- reduced equipment costs: due to the compact size of machines and tools, the amount of equipment used is reduced;
- saving resources: optimizing the processes of laying coatings and protective structures leads to savings in energy resources and materials.

All this helps to reduce the total cost of the project, which is especially important in conditions of limited budgets of city administrations. The environmental aspect also plays a significant role in choosing the tunnel construction method.

The use of NATM helps to preserve the environment by reducing noise pollution and emissions of harmful substances into the atmosphere. There are no significant dust clouds typical for traditional sinking methods. Reducing the amount of construction waste and debris is also an important factor.

The Austrian tunnel construction method has proven to be effective and appropriate for dense urban environments. Its flexibility, safety, economic advantages and environmental acceptability make it possible to successfully implement projects of varying complexity, providing residents with comfortable living and movement conditions.

Performing tunnel calculations

To confirm the effectiveness of the tunnel construction, calculations were carried out in the GTS NX program. With the given initial data shown in the table below:

Table 1. Initial data of materials for tunnel design

Materials	E	γ
Steel	2,10E+08	78
Concrete	3,25E+07	25

Table 2. Initial soil data for tunnel design

Soils	E	γ
Sand	50000	19
Clay, loam, sandy loam	50000	25

Fig. 3. The first variant of the tunnel design is a plug with a bottom.

Fig. 4. The second variant of the tunnel design is a round seal.

After entering the initial data, we get the calculated schemes:

Fig. 5. Design scheme of deformation under its own weight – tunnel construction with a closed bottom.

Fig. 6. Design scheme of deformation under its own weight – tunnel construction with a closed bottom, side view.

Fig. 7. Design scheme of deformation under its own weight – the design of a round tunnel.

Fig. 8. Design scheme of deformation under its own weight – the design of a round tunnel, side view.

Based on the results of the calculations, we obtained tables of soil movement within the tunnel and saw visual deformations with an enlarged scale.

Table 3. Calculations of z-axis displacements in a circular section.

Node (Variant1)	Moving (Option 1)	Node (Option 2)	Moving (Option 2)
16585	-0,026010683	230481	-0,016431222
16586	-0,025970003	230483	-0,016358221
16587	-0,026025599	230504	-0,016346209
16588	-0,025882857	230505	0
16589	-0,026042722	230506	0
16590	-0,025988489	230507	-0,016425291

Node (Variant1)	Moving (Option 1)	Node (Option 2)	Moving (Option 2)
16591	-0,02586635	230508	0
16592	-0,025772838	230509	0
16593	-0,025724599	230510	0
16594	-0,021120163	230511	-0,016376663

Conclusions:

1. Tunnel construction is an effective solution to the transport problem of this busy highway. It will allow:

- divide the traffic flows;
- increase the capacity of the street;
- improve the environmental situation and reduce noise levels;
- free up space for pedestrians and public transport.
- the experience of using NATM in Moscow (construction of subway lines in clay soils) confirms the reliability and effectiveness of the method in difficult engineering geological conditions.

2. The New Austrian tunnel construction method (NATM) is optimally suited for the project implementation, as it:

- adapts to difficult geological conditions (unstable soils, high groundwater level);
- minimizes the amount of excavation and interference in urban development;
- ensures high safety and reliability of the structure;
- allows you to quickly adjust the project during the construction process (thanks to step-by-step design and continuous monitoring);
- reduces time and costs compared to traditional methods (e.g. drilling and blasting).

3. The economic advantages of NATM include:

- optimization of logistics (supply of materials in small batches);
- reduction of equipment costs (using compact equipment);
- saving resources (materials and energy).

4. Environmental benefits of NATM:

- reduction of noise pollution;
- reduction of emissions of harmful substances and dust clouds;
- reducing the amount of construction waste.

5. The introduction of NATM for tunnel construction will allow:

- to ensure the safety and durability of the structure, taking into account local conditions (freezing depth, seismicity, etc.);
- create a more comfortable and functional urban environment;
- to meet the growing needs for modernization of transport infrastructure.

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A PERSONALIZED ADAPTIVE MULTIMODAL INTERFACE MODEL FOR PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL GAMES

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Abstract. *The article proposes a personalized adaptive multimodal interface model for a preschool educational game. The model combines audiovisual signals, game telemetry and an individual interaction memory of a child player. The main scientific result is a formal description of the control loop “observation-interaction state-child memory-safe interface action”. Unlike systems that adapt tasks only by the correctness of answers, the proposed model considers the current dynamics of engagement, difficulty, fatigue and data reliability. The article introduces an adaptive interaction profile as a technical characteristic of interaction with the game, not as a psychological diagnosis or a personality label. The model is designed with regard to current technical tools for face and behavior analysis and with regard to legal and ethical constraints on children’s data and emotion recognition in education. The results can be used for designing a prototype of an explainable and privacy-aware educational game for preschool children.*

Keywords: *adaptive interface, multimodal interface, preschool education, educational game, audiovisual signals, game telemetry, child memory, affective computing, user model.*

Introduction

Digital educational games are increasingly used in preschool education. They support speech development, attention, memory, elementary mathematical concepts and early learning motivation. At the same time, the design of adaptive educational interfaces should be considered in the broader context of affective computing and multimodal human-computer interaction [1; 2]. However, many applications adapt the learning path mainly by visible performance indicators: whether the answer was correct, how many attempts were made, and how quickly a task was completed. This approach is useful, but it is not sufficient for preschool children, because the result of a task does not fully describe the child’s state during interaction.

For children aged 3 to 7 years, the process of solving a task is as important as the final answer. Pauses, response tempo, repeated errors, use of hints, voice activity,

gaze direction, facial dynamics and signs of fatigue may change the pedagogical meaning of the same answer. This corresponds to research on affective states during learning and to interdisciplinary work on affect detection [3; 4]. A child can give a correct answer while experiencing tension or overload. Conversely, an error may be caused not by lack of knowledge, but by fatigue, distraction, an unclear instruction or an excessive interface tempo. Therefore, an adaptive educational game should consider not only cognitive performance, but also the dynamics of interaction.

Current educational and behavior analysis systems show that this problem remains open. Khan Academy Kids and Lingokids are aimed at young children and use age-appropriate game scenarios [6; 7]. At the same time, such applications do not normally perform real-time multimodal estimation of a child's interaction state. On the other hand, tools such as MediaPipe Face Landmarker and FaceReader provide advanced facial or behavioral analysis [8; 10], but they are not complete pedagogical systems for preschool learning. This creates a research gap between cognitive personalization in educational apps and multimodal affect-aware adaptation in child-computer interaction, which is also consistent with reviews of Child-Computer Interaction methods and tools [5].

The purpose of this article is to propose a formal model of a personalized adaptive multimodal interface for a preschool educational game. The model is based on three principles. First, the system should estimate the state of interaction rather than assign a rigid emotion label. Second, the system should maintain a limited and transparent memory of interaction with each child. Third, every adaptive action should pass through safety, privacy and pedagogical constraints.

Methods

The study uses theoretical modeling and comparative analysis of existing software solutions. The proposed model is built as an information process that links observations, state estimation, individual memory and interface action. The main sources of data are audio, video and game telemetry. The model does not require specialized physiological sensors because such equipment is difficult to use in ordinary preschool settings.

Let i denote a child player and t denote the current time point or the current analysis window. The multimodal observation vector is defined as:

$$O_i(t) = \{A_i(t), V_i(t), G_i(t), Q_i(t)\},$$

where $A_i(t)$ is the audio feature vector, $V_i(t)$ is the video feature vector, $G_i(t)$ is game telemetry and $Q_i(t)$ is the vector of data quality indicators. Audio features may include speech activity, pauses, volume, pitch, speech tempo and signal-to-noise ratio. Video features may include facial landmarks, facial blendshape coefficients, head direction, gaze-related indicators and frame quality. Game telemetry contains answer time, number of attempts, errors, hint requests, pauses and level progress.

The video component relies on currently available tools. For example, MediaPipe Face Landmarker is described in the official documentation as a task for detecting face landmarks and facial expressions in images, videos and live streams [8]. The implementation uses 478 normalized face landmarks for blendshape prediction [9]. This detail matters because older references to 68 facial landmarks do not correctly describe the current MediaPipe Face Landmarker pipeline.

The main data sources and their functions in the model are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Data sources and their functions in the model

Data source	Examples of features	Function in the model
Audio $A_i(t)$	Speech activity, pauses, loudness, tempo, pitch, signal-to-noise ratio	Estimation of activity, readiness to answer, possible tension and reliability of the audio channel
Video $V_i(t)$	Face landmarks, blendshape coefficients, head direction, gaze-related indicators, frame quality	Estimation of visual attention, facial dynamics and reliability of the video channel
Game telemetry $G_i(t)$	Answer time, repeated attempts, errors, hints, pauses, progress of a level	Task context and objective signs of difficulty
Quality $Q_i(t)$	Noise level, face visibility, light quality, missing data, confidence of detectors	Control of modality weights and fallback decisions

The memory of interaction is described as:

$$M_i(t) = \{B_i, L_i(t), H_i(t), R_i(t), C_i\},$$

where B_i is the individual baseline of the child, $L_i(t)$ is the learning progress, $H_i(t)$ is the history of adaptive actions, $R_i(t)$ is the history of reactions to support, and C_i is the set of consent, privacy and safety constraints. This memory is not a psychological file and should not contain diagnostic labels. It is a technical structure needed to avoid average-based decisions and to support the child in a more consistent way.

The components of the interaction memory and their purpose are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Structure of interaction memory $M_i(t)$

Memory component	What is recorded	Purpose
Baseline B_i	Typical response tempo, pause duration, speech activity, normal interaction rhythm	Distinguishing the child's usual behavior from a current change

Memory component	What is recorded	Purpose
Learning progress $L_i(t)$	Completed topics, repeated mistakes, success dynamics	Choosing a suitable level of task difficulty
History of adaptations $H_i(t)$	Hints, pauses, tempo changes and modality changes already used	Avoiding ineffective or excessive interventions
Reaction history $R_i(t)$	What usually helps: example, visual cue, repeated instruction, praise or short pause	Selecting a personalized support strategy
Constraints C_i	Parental consent, allowed data types, retention rules, safety restrictions	Protecting privacy and limiting unsafe automation

The model also introduces an adaptive interaction profile. This term is used instead of “personality type”. The profile describes only how the child interacts with the game: preferred modality of support, usual tempo, tolerance to repeated attempts, reaction to hints, fatigue dynamics and effective forms of encouragement. It is not intended for psychological classification, medical diagnosis or labeling of the child.

Results

The main result is a structural and formal model that links multimodal observations, child memory and a safe adaptive action of the interface. The state of interaction is defined as:

$$S_i(t) = (E_i(t), D_i(t), F_i(t), Cg_i(t), P_i(t), \rho_i(t)),$$

where $E_i(t)$ is engagement, $D_i(t)$ is difficulty or confusion, $F_i(t)$ is fatigue, $Cg_i(t)$ is cognitive load, $P_i(t)$ is task performance and $\rho_i(t)$ is confidence in the estimate. This state vector does not reduce the child’s behavior to a single emotion label. It is more appropriate for an educational interface because it connects the observed reaction with the learning task and data reliability.

Multimodal fusion is performed with attention to the quality of each channel. If the room is noisy, the audio channel receives a lower weight. If the child turns away from the camera or the lighting is poor, the video channel is used more carefully. If both sensor channels are unreliable, the system should temporarily rely mainly on game telemetry and conservative pedagogical rules. A normalized weighted fusion can be written as:

$$h^{fuse}_d(t) = \alpha_i(t)h^A(t) + \gamma_i(t)h^\beta(t) + \beta_i(t)h^G(t),$$

where $h^A(t)$, $h^\beta(t)$ and $h^G(t)$ are latent representations of audio, video and telemetry, respectively. The modality weights satisfy $\alpha_i(t) + \gamma_i(t) + \beta_i(t) = 1$ and $\alpha_i(t), \gamma_i(t), \beta_i(t) \geq 0$. These weights are adjusted according to the data quality indicators $Q_i(t)$: the audio weight decreases under noisy conditions, the video weight decreases when face visibility or lighting is poor, and the telemetry weight increases

when sensor channels are unreliable. This normalized formulation preserves consistency when all three modalities are used.

The decision module selects an interface action from a safe set of actions:

$$u_i(t) = \arg \max J(u \mid S_i(t), M_i(t), \text{Ctx}(t)), u \in U_{\text{safe}}$$

where J is the utility of an action, $\text{Ctx}(t)$ is the current task context and U_{safe} is the set of allowed interface actions. The utility function considers learning progress, engagement support, reduction of overload, interface stability and the risk of a wrong intervention. In practice, U_{safe} should be defined by pedagogical rules and privacy restrictions before any machine learning optimization is applied.

Examples of safe adaptive interface actions and their restrictions are shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Examples of safe adaptive interface actions

Situation	Possible adaptive action	Restriction
High success and high engagement	Slightly increase difficulty or tempo	Avoid sudden changes of difficulty
Errors with preserved engagement	Give a guiding hint or repeat the instruction	Do not replace the child's own action
Increasing signs of difficulty	Reduce complexity or change the hint format	Do not label the child as unsuccessful
Signs of fatigue	Suggest a pause or a shorter task	Do not intensify stimuli only to keep attention
Low data confidence	Switch to telemetry-based conservative adaptation	Do not infer emotional state from unreliable data

The novelty of the proposed framework lies in the integration of four elements: multimodal observations, interaction memory, adaptive interaction profile and a safety-limited decision policy. This makes it possible to move from simple personalization by correct answers to a more complete and explainable adaptation of preschool educational interaction.

Discussion

The proposed model shows that personalization of a preschool educational game should not be limited to the history of correct and incorrect answers. A more useful approach links current reactions, the task context and the individual memory of interaction. At the same time, affect-aware technology in education must be used carefully. The interface should not claim that it diagnoses emotions or personality. It should only estimate interaction-relevant states and data confidence for the purpose of safer support.

The legal and ethical context is especially important when the user is a child. In the United States, the amended Children’s Online Privacy Protection Rule was published in the Federal Register on April 22, 2025, and became effective on June 23, 2025; regulated entities have until April 22, 2026, to comply with most new requirements [12]. In the European Union, Article 5(1)(f) of Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 prohibits AI systems that infer emotions of individuals in educational institutions, except where the system is intended for medical or safety reasons; these prohibitions entered into application on February 2, 2025 [11]. Broader child-centred AI guidance also emphasizes safety, privacy, transparency and accountability in systems used by or affecting children [13]. Therefore, the proposed model avoids the language of “emotion diagnosis” and focuses on interaction support, data minimization and explainable adult supervision.

Reinforcement learning can be used only in a restricted form. In a real game with preschool children, it is not acceptable to let an agent freely test arbitrary strategies in order to maximize a numerical reward. Safer options include offline learning from anonymized logs, simulation-based testing, contextual bandits with a restricted action set and final verification by pedagogical experts. In the operating prototype, every action should be filtered through safety rules and should be explainable to an adult.

The limitation of this article is its theoretical character. The next research step should be the development of a prototype and an empirical study with children of the target age group. Such a study must require informed consent from parents or legal representatives and should use data minimization. Evaluation metrics should include not only recognition accuracy, but also quality of adaptation: fewer repeated errors, stable engagement, fewer unnecessary hints, absence of abrupt interface changes and clarity of explanations for adults.

Conclusion

The article proposes a personalized adaptive multimodal interface model for a preschool educational game. The model combines audiovisual signals, game telemetry and a limited memory of interaction with a particular child. The scientific contribution comprises two elements: (1) formalization of the control loop “observation – interaction state-memory-safe interface action”; and (2) introduction of the adaptive interaction profile as a privacy-preserving alternative to psychological personality labeling.

The model can be used for designing educational games that adapt to the child’s individual tempo, support history, preferred hint format and current data quality. At the same time, the model preserves important restrictions: it does not assign diagnoses, does not use psychological labels, does not require constant storage of audio and video data, and includes an explainable role for an adult. Further development should focus on prototype implementation, experimental validation and refinement of metrics for pedagogically safe adaptation.

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TEMPERATURE COMPENSATION OF THE CHARGE VOLTAGE OF A LEAD-ACID BATTERY IN A PASSENGER COACH

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Abstract. *The article analyzes the charging process and the need to use charge-voltage temperature compensation for a lead-acid battery in a passenger coach, considers the principle of two-stage temperature-dependent CC–CV charging (constant current – constant voltage), and presents a developed charge control system.*

Keywords: *charge-voltage temperature compensation, lead-acid batteries, passenger coach, two-stage charging, control system*

I. Introduction

At present, lead-acid batteries are widely used in many areas where guaranteed power supply is required when the voltage supplied from the main power source disappears. Such batteries are widely used in automotive equipment, railway transport, power engineering, as well as in backup and autonomous power supply systems.

Lead-acid batteries are of particular importance in railway transport [1]. In passenger coaches, they are used as a backup power source that supplies consumers when the main source of electric power is unavailable or faulty. The main consumers in a passenger coach include electric lighting, ventilation and electric-heating units, electric heating appliances, household devices, and signaling and control circuits [2]. Depending on the power source, four main types of passenger-coach power supply systems are distinguished: autonomous, mixed, centralized autonomous, and centralized high-voltage.

The autonomous power supply system of a passenger coach has two power sources: a generator and a battery. When the train moves at a speed of 35–40 km/h, the consumers are supplied by the under-car generator (AC or DC), while the battery is in charging mode. At speeds below 35 km/h, power is supplied from the energy stored in the battery. **The mixed** power supply system includes both

a generator and a battery, and is additionally supplied from the under-car high-voltage line (3000 V) fed by the electric locomotive. The 3000 V voltage is used as an electric power source for coach heating. In the **centralized autonomous** power supply system, small-capacity batteries and a special power-station coach are used as electric power sources. Such coaches can be of two types: motor-generator coaches (when operating on an electrified section) and diesel-generator coaches (when operating on a non-electrified section). The electric power generated by the power-station coach is sufficient to supply all coaches in the train. In the **centralized high-voltage** system, a special power supply unit is used instead of a generator. This unit is supplied from the electric locomotive at 3000 V; if this voltage is absent, electric power is supplied by the battery. This system can be used not only on electrified sections but also on non-electrified sections, provided that power is supplied by a diesel locomotive with a special generator [3; 4].

Thus, batteries are present in all types of power supply systems. The reliability of a lead-acid battery is determined not only by its design and characteristics, but also by the correctness of the charging algorithm. The most common charging method is the two-stage CC–CV (Constant Current – Constant Voltage) charging mode: in the first stage, charging is performed with current limitation, and after the specified voltage has been reached, charging is performed with voltage limitation. In addition, for correct charging of a lead-acid battery, it is important to account for the temperature inside the battery box and, depending on it, regulate the charge voltage in order to prevent accelerated battery aging [5].

II. Methods

The charging process of a lead-acid battery is accompanied by restoration of the active materials of the electrodes and an increase in electrolyte density. In the initial stages of charging, the battery can accept a comparatively higher current without a rise in voltage. As charge accumulates, the internal resistance and polarization change, and the terminal voltage increases. As the battery approaches full charge, the probability of side processes, such as gas emission, increases significantly [6].

Therefore, a two-stage charging mode is used for charging lead-acid batteries [5]. In the first stage, charging is carried out with limited current. This is necessary to return the main part of the capacity quickly without overloading the power source and without overheating the battery itself. After the established limiting voltage has been reached, the process switches to the second charging stage – the voltage-limitation mode, in which the charging current gradually decreases as the battery becomes saturated. This is also necessary to reduce the thermal load on the battery and to prevent overcharge, which reduces the capacity of the battery itself and, consequently, its service life.

If only constant-current charging is used until the process is fully completed, then at the end of charging the intensity of water electrolysis inevitably increases,

electrolyte losses rise, corrosion of the positive grids accelerates, and the battery service life decreases. If only constant-voltage charging is used, a deeply discharged battery will charge for too long and may not reach full charge [5].

Electrochemical processes in a lead-acid battery strongly depend on temperature [7]. When temperature decreases, electrolyte viscosity increases, the diffusion rate decreases, and the internal resistance of the battery increases. Accordingly, a higher charge voltage is required to achieve the necessary state of charge; otherwise, the battery will be consistently undercharged, which will lead to the accumulation of sulfate formations on the plates, a reduction in available capacity, and deterioration in the charging rate.

When temperature increases, chemical reactions proceed more readily, internal resistance decreases, and the previous charge voltage becomes excessive. If the charge voltage is not reduced, gas emission increases, water losses accelerate, battery temperature rises, and the risk of overheating increases.

Charge-voltage temperature compensation [7] makes it possible to regulate the battery charge voltage properly, preventing adverse chemical reactions and extending the service life of the battery itself. Accordingly, at reduced temperature the charge voltage is increased, while at elevated temperature it is reduced.

III. Results

Based on the principles described above, a battery charge control system has been developed with allowance for the two-stage charging mode and charge-voltage temperature compensation; its structure is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Battery charge control system

The following designations are used in this control system:

- V_{bat} – current terminal voltage of the battery;
- V_{ref_temp} – permissible battery charge voltage at the current temperature;
- V_{dc_err} – battery voltage error;
- K_v – coefficient converting the voltage error into a current command;
- I_{ref} – reference battery charging current;
- I_{charge} – current battery charging current;
- V_{charge} – battery charge voltage.

The presented battery charge control system is implemented in the semiconductor battery charge control unit of a passenger coach and provides limitation of the charging current in the first charging stage, transition to the voltage-limitation mode in the second stage, and regulation of the charge voltage depending on the current temperature in the battery box.

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